

D7.1: Market Analyses

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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1. Glossary of terms and acronyms used.

Acronym / Term	Description
AFL	AgriFood Lithuania DIH
AFSC	Agri-food supply chain
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
AP	Active Packaging
API	Application Programming Interface
B2B	Business-to-Business
BDIS	Big Data Infrastructural Services
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CPT	Cold Plasma Technology
EC	European Commission
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
EuPIA	European Printing Ink Association
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FAO	The United Nations Food and Agriculture Organisation
FCMs	Food Contact Materials
FCTA	Fundación Corporación Tecnológica Andaluza
FEBA	European Food Banks Federation
FIR	Far-infrared
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FMIS	Farm Management Information Systems
FSC	Food Supply Chain

FW	Food Waste
GA	Grant Agreement
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
GMP	Good Manufacturing Practices
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite Systems
H2020	Horizon 2020 framework
HE	Horizon Europe framework
HMCS	Handheld Molecular Contaminant Screener
HPP	High-Pressure Processing
ICP	Inlecom Commercial Pathways
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intelligent Packaging
IT	Information Technology
ITENE	Instituto Tecnológico del Embalaje, Transporte y Logística
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
MAP	Modified atmosphere packaging
MIR	Mid-infrared
ML	Machine Learning
MST	Multiscan Technologies SL
MW	Microwave
NIR	Near Infra-Red
OH	Ohmic Heating
PA	Precision Agriculture
PAT	Precision Agriculture Technology
PAYT	Pay-as-you-throw

PEF	Pulsed Electric Field
PL	Pulsed Light
PPP	Plant Protection Product
PPWD	Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive
RF	Radio Frequency
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
ROI	Return on Investment
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SFT	Smart Farming Technology
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Lab
SIRL	Systemic Innovation Readiness Level
SoTA	State-of-the-art
TNO	Nederlandse Organisatie voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TTI	Time Temperature Indicators
UAE	Ultrasonication Assisted Extraction
UTP	Unfair Trading Practices
UV	Ultraviolet
WFD	Waste Framework Directive
WIT	Waterford Institute of Technology
WP	Work Package
WWF	World Wide Fund

Executive summary

The goal of this deliverable is to report on the initial actions supporting the ZeroW commercialisation strategy. As a first step in defining the viable commercial trajectory of ZeroW solutions, focus is put on understanding the current market drivers and dynamics, requirements of the Food Supply Chain (FSC) actors, as well as governance imposed by regulatory bodies and policy stakeholders that influences the food loss and waste (FLW) industry. Therefore, the purpose of the Market Analyses report is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the state-of-the-art in the relevant FLW markets and outlooks for the future, to identify and elaborate on market drivers and barriers affecting ZeroW anticipated solutions entry, including an overview of competing solutions across the entire FSC, from Farm to Fork (F2F), including the pre-harvest stage.

This report describes ZeroW Market Analyses, as defined in *Task 7.1 Market Analyses*, of Work Package (WP) 7: *Exploitation, sustainability & commercialisation of project outputs*. Detailed market analyses are principally pivoted around the project's Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) and anticipated solutions, but also account for the FLW industry sector and associated supply chains, food packaging stakeholders, and consumer interest groups.

The Market Analyses report presented here acts as a strategic document providing key information to guide the ZeroW Exploitation & Commercialisation Strategy and foster alignment of activities of ZeroW SILLs to the identified market requirements of all FSC stages. The market research and resulting report had to reconcile two conflicting requirements: (i) to be broad enough to target all market segments corresponding to all sectors of FSC, but at the same time (ii) to be detailed enough to include the specifics for the target markets of all ZeroW anticipated solutions. To foster this, solutions are grouped within four clusters: **(1) OFLW Platform, (2) Pre- and Post-harvest Innovations; (3) Food Processing Innovations and (4) Wholesale, Retail and Consumers Innovations**. Relevant markets are addressed to reflect this clustering, employing the ICP developed Commercialisation Methodology, which includes 4 Stages of the Commercialisation Process - Customer Validation, Solution Alignment, Business Model and Growth Trajectory.

The **OFLW Platform** aims to provide an integrated solution for tackling FLW along the entire FSC by enabling knowledge sharing and collective intelligence; similar holistic solutions are not available in the market. The majority of the state-of-the-art focuses on narrower problems at discrete stages of the FSC, and are not well suited to address FLW at regional, national or European contexts; therefore, OFLW Platform will tackle a need that is currently not addressed in the FLW market. However, the lack of a uniform definition of FLW is obscuring primarily data collection, but also data exchange among relevant stakeholders. The lack of industry-wide standards and agreements on data exchange, concerns related to data ownership and security, as well as GDPR and related policies, impose restrictions on data interoperability between different systems/platforms/FLW initiatives. This in effect is inflicting limitations to develop a solution capable to cover the entire supply chain such as the proposed OFLW Platform. Nevertheless, advances in big data analytics, Blockchain technologies, computing power and IoT, will foster the digitalisation efforts and sustainability in food systems, opening the market opportunities for digital solutions like OFLW Platform and ZeroW Smart Applications. The governing strategies and ambitious targets set by regional, national, EU and global regulatory bodies encourage the adoption of smart agri-food solutions and digital transformation of the agri-food sector.

ZeroW **Pre- and Post-harvest innovations** are aiming at smart greenhouse and smart harvest markets. Drivers for both are found to be in feeding constantly increasing global population, increased adoption of smart farming technologies, and increased governmental support for implementation of novel technologies. The solution proposed by ZeroW focuses on optimising harvesting schedules for greenhouse-grown vegetables,

allowing for the precise planning and prediction of expected product yield, in addition to identification of crops that do not comply to aesthetic standards and their re-purposing to other uses early in the FSC. This solution does not centre on the automatic harvesting part, as it is the case with majority of market available solutions, but on improving conditions at the organisational level, fostering data-driven decision making and employing new tools and methods for more accurate, timely and efficient work planning. As the EU agriculture is dominated by small farms, with limited resources to invest in novel technologies and limited technical knowledge, low cost might be the major market requirement; governmental support for the implementation of smart agricultural and farming technologies is crucial for widescale adoption. Larger farms, although less common in Europe, have the capacity and the incentive (i.e. higher levels of possible FLW generated) to invest in this type of technologies.

The main drivers governing the **Food Processing** market are increased focus on enhancing production efficiency, optimised processes in terms of time, yield and environmental impact, and increased quality of produced food, while implementing practices to prevent, reduce and valorise FLW produced in the support of a shift towards sustainable food systems. ZeroW Food Processing innovations encompass several solutions. (i) The innovative, sustainable and smart packaging for fresh fish brings the competitive holistic solution with the potential to increase fresh fish shelf-life and improve stock management at the retail level; deployment of smart sensors as integral part of proposed solution distinguishes ZeroW innovation, as it provides real-time data for monitoring both shelf-life and quality of the packed product. (ii) The mobile processing unit anticipated to be offered as a service empowers small- and medium-sized farms to utilise the product surplus; often these were not able to avail of the currently available commercial processing units, as they are large, expensive and in most cases stationary. (iii) Ugly food early identification solution promotes efficient control of produce quality, colour, size and shape, detecting eventual issues early; inclusion of state-of-the-art sensors enables real-time, non-destructive on-line information on organic/non-organic product batches, preventing the FLW occurring due to misclassification and allowing for timely recovery practices. (iv) Advanced algorithms for control and optimisation of the production processes are offering non-destructive technology for determination of food quality parameters and subsequent optimisation of intermediate processing steps in fresh meat production. All food related innovations, but especially those affecting the common food products directly, be it through the novel ways of processing or the novel final products, face an impediment imposed by consumers acceptance of novelty. Another important barrier for adoption is the size of the companies that comprise the EU food processing industry; these are mostly SMEs that may not have the necessary capital to invest in novel technologies as the ones proposed in the project; incentives through governmental support may be required for these companies to benefit from the project's outcomes.

At present, available market solutions addressing lower stages of FSC are focusing on applications for food waste (FW) monitoring and management, dynamic pricing according to the product expiry date, management solutions for household and finally redistribution of food surplus and alternative utilisation of FW. ZeroW **Wholesale, Retail and Consumer innovations** include solutions to address the market gap related to retail-fostered valorisation of FW, focusing on development of optimised reversed logistics for FW valorisation and FW alternative deployment. This implies addressing the relatively new concept of FW use for microalgae growth; hence, similar solutions are not yet available at the market. Introducing innovations at wholesale, retail and especially consumer stages of FSC is fundamentally impacted by consumer trust, social norms and policy/regulation requirements; the acceptance of such innovations will largely depend

on education of general public, behavioural change and novel governance models. Taking this into account, ZeroW solutions anticipate to meet non-commercial actors' needs associated to optimised food bank processes for efficient demand prediction and distribution of food, as well as nudging consumers behaviour toward more sustainable food choices. Hence, the social aspect is one of the main drivers of this market; preventing the unnecessary waste of already produced food will aid governmental agendas on alleviating food insecurity and providing food for all, consequently offering major growth opportunities for FW management solutions.

Market analyses presented in this report are reflection of relevant market intelligence available per specific sector and for specific solution. More importantly, market data reported in this deliverable reflects pertinent actors and solution developers understanding of specific market and associated industry need. This was achieved through questionnaires disseminated to all SILL partners and solution developers, with the view of gaining genuine market information aligned with FSC sectoral requirements, to underpin project commercial trajectory. Inclusion of external stakeholders in the process of validating ZeroW commercial ambitions is planned to take place through the activities of Task 7.5 *Clustering and Commercial Ecosystem Creation*.

This report will inform and orient both Task 7.2 *Customer Validation & Solution Alignment* and Task 7.3 *Business Models and Business Plan*. By providing foundational market sector context, intelligence on relevant markets drivers and barriers, as well as encapsulating pertinent information from SILLs and solution developers, this report will support positioning of ZeroW solutions within the competitive FLW industry landscape, incentivising their path to market. As SILL demonstration activities are starting in M14 of the project, any additional understanding regarding ZeroW solutions that might arise upon submission of this report (M12) together with the prescriptive directions towards commercial evangelisations of selected project outputs will be captured in the follow-up commercialisation deliverables.

1 Introduction

This chapter provides a high-level summary of the ZeroW project, as well as an overview and structure of this report and relations with other ZeroW deliverables.

1.1 ZeroW project summary

Figure 1. ZeroW at a glance.

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2. ZeroW approach.

To reach its goals ZeroW is divided into 11 WPs with different goals, tasks and deliverables.

1.2 Mapping ZeroW outputs

This report is the first deliverable of WP7 - *Exploitation, sustainability and commercialisation of project outputs*. WP7 focuses on advancing ZeroW solutions commercially, including protecting strategic IP through patent filings and formulating business and market-relevant exploitation strategy anchored in robust market sector analyses.

The purpose of this section is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document.

Table 2. Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description.

ZEROW GA Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D7.1 Market Analyses	This deliverable will evidence market analyses around the FLW industry sector. (GA)	All chapters and sections	This report provides comprehensive market analyses aiming to assess FLW relevant markets for the anticipated ZeroW solutions.
TASKS			
T7.1 Market Sector Analyses	This task underpins the project’s business plan with a detailed market analyses principally pivoted around the project SILLs and the FLW industry sector, associated supply chains, the food commoditisation ecosystem, the food packaging actors, consumer interest groups and, importantly, the co-dependent and enabling EU SME and industry sector. This will include a lens on techno-economic, socio-economic and sustainability indicators through a quantitative and qualitative assessment that looks into the forward dynamics and size of the FLW market both in terms of volume and in value, revenue potential, licencing potential, the associated customer segments and buying patterns, the global competition and competitive landscape, and the economic environment in terms of barriers to entry and regulatory imperatives whilst factoring in health, safety, socio-economic and environmental dimensions. T7.1 will also factor in a core imperative of ZeroW which is towards deeper collaboration, data exchange and value sharing between and across sectoral actors as a key enablement and acceleration catalyst to aligning the sector in a direction towards mutually beneficial growth trajectories. T7.1 will provide important foundational market sector and eco-system context which informs and orients both T7.2 (Customer Validation & Solution Alignment) and T7.3 (Business Models and Business Plan). (GA)	All chapters and sections	<p>Chapters 1 and 2 provide introduction and background to the ZeroW project and its key goals, setting the scene for the market research to cover entire FLW supply chain, including EU SME sector.</p> <p>Chapter 3 provides an overview of the methodology used.</p> <p>Chapter 4 is introducing briefly the FLW market, accompanying challenges and segmentation in context of ZeroW.</p> <p>Chapters 5, 6, 7 & 8 are describing in details ZeroW proposed innovations and corresponding markets overview, including market size and dynamics, competitive landscape and economic environment. Chapters are organised to reflect the market segmentation adopted for the purpose of the ZeroW project. Each of the chapters is completed with the summary of markets relevant for ZeroW.</p> <p>Finally, chapter 9 draws the conclusion of this comprehensive analysis.</p>

1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The purpose of this report is to provide a comprehensive overview of markets relevant for the proposed ZeroW solutions, including market dynamics and driving factors, analysis of competitors, as well as preliminary PESTLE analysis to evaluate political, economic, social, technological and environmental factors that might influence placement of the ZeroW innovations on relevant markets. Finally, barriers for solutions to enter the market are explored. As an early deliverable, D7.1 Market Analyses provides an initial assessment of the above mentioned; as the ZeroW innovations develop so will the understanding of the most relevant market opportunities and market dynamics in general, including the potential barriers that solutions might be facing when entering the market. Within the future commercialisation activities (T7.2 and T7.3), a special focus will be made to ensure initial understanding of market dynamics, competitors and potential barriers is pertinent; where necessary, updates will be provided. This is mainly expected to happen as a result of the (i) customer validation and solution alignment activities; (ii) engagement with the relevant industry actors through the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem Group (T7.5) and ZeroW External Advisory Board; and (iii) stakeholders workshops aiming to assess and define the scalability potential and regional scale-up strategies (WP6). Finally, the culmination of the commercialisation activities will be presented in the deliverable D7.3 Business Models & Business Plan, where devising the go-to-market strategy and growth trajectory will include addressing the entry barriers, and overall market environment in which selected solutions are to be placed.

The structure of this deliverable is outlined below:

- Chapter 1 gives an introduction to this report, including the summary of ZeroW project and structure of the document.
- Chapter 2 links to the background of ZeroW project, consortium of Partners, position of ZeroW relative to the industry, as well as key project goals, and more specifically commercialisation goals, including Work Package 7 *Exploitation, sustainability & commercialisation of project outputs* goals.
- Chapter 3 describes the commercialisation framework developed by ICP and adopted by the ZeroW consortium to provide a comprehensive and structured 4 Stages Commercialisation Process within the ZeroW project.
- Chapter 4 provides an introduction to the FLW market, its challenges and segmentation approach adopted for the purpose of ZeroW project. Finally, the specific methodology applied for the purpose of market research is detailed.
- Chapters 5-8 describe in detail ZeroW proposed innovations and corresponding markets overview, focusing on market drivers and dynamics, competitors analysis, regulations and barriers for solution to entry the

respective markets. Chapters are organised to reflect the market segmentation adopted for the purpose of ZeroW, i.e. FLW digital solutions, including OFLW IT Platform (Chapter 5); Pre- and Post-harvest Innovations (Chapter 6); Food Processing Innovations (Chapter 7); and Wholesale, Retail and Consumers Innovations (Chapter 8). Each of the chapters provides summary of markets relevant for ZeroW.

- Finally, chapter 9 draws the conclusion of this comprehensive analysis.

Figure 3 below shows the position of this report in relation to other deliverables within the ZeroW project and other initiatives in general. SILL (Systemic Innovation Living Labs) Strategic Plans (D4.3) provided the preliminary understanding of the solution(s) each SILL will be testing and validating. This was complemented by a questionnaire developed by ICP (Annex II) and distributed to SILLs and technical partners for input. Answered questionnaires provided further details on specifics of each anticipated solution, to the best of the partners understanding at this stage of the project.

It is important to note that ZeroW SILLs plan to start testing and validating activities in M14 of the project and are were in the preparation phase while this document was being developed (year one of the project). Any additional understanding regarding ZeroW solutions that might arise during demonstration phases of the SILLs will be captured in follow-up commercialisation deliverables (D7.2 Customer Validation & Solution Alignment and D7.3 Business Models & Business Plan), as well as through the Key Exploitable Results (KER) register that will be developed in the scope of T7.4 IP Management & IP Protection. Likewise, if deemed necessary, adjustments to the market analyses to include additional market intelligence will be addressed through follow-up commercialisation activities.

Figure 3. D7.1 relation to other ZeroW documents.

Market Intelligence reports obtained through [MarketsandMarkets](#), [Statista](#), [Eurostat](#), [Enterprise Ireland](#) and other market intelligence sources were utilised in development of this report. Additionally, other EC initiatives/projects targeting FLW, including policy recommendations and whitepapers, were examined to provide input and consolidate this robust deliverable.

Market Analyses will underpin ZeroW commercialisation strategy, providing important foundational market sector and ecosystem context to inform and orient both T7.2 Customer Validation & Solution Alignment and T7.3 Business Models & Business Plan. Additionally, market analyses will inform T7.5 Clustering and Commercial Ecosystem Creation, outlining the pertinent and relevant market areas for the external industry and sectoral actors to cover and provide feedback loops in support of the ZeroW commercial ambitions.

Finally, Market Analyses will support D4.5 in defining post-project sustainability and funding strategy, ensuring SILL activities beyond ZeroW and towards the development of new innovations.

2 ZeroW Project Background

This chapter will outline the background to the ZeroW, providing the project overview and its position relative to the industry, details of the ZeroW Consortium, and finally key project goals, and more specifically WP7 goals.

2.1 ZeroW Overview

As available data show, roughly 30% of total food produced is lost and/or wasted throughout the food value chain [1]. Although many initiatives to tackle FLW exist, the main food systems' lock-in effects are yet to be fully addressed and significant impact in the FLW reduction achieved. The first step toward reducing FLW is a holistic approach in targeting both structural and behavioural lock-in effects embedded in the current food systems (Figure 4), most importantly:

- (i) missing/fragmented FLW data (including lack of agreement on FLW definitions);
- (ii) principal focus at the lower layers in the FLW hierarchy (discussed later in the document, Figure 44, Section 8.2.2.5);
- (iii) limited abilities of food actors to reduce FLW, e.g. diverse food surplus or sub-standard products;
- (iv) lack of ability to impact consumer buying behaviour and steer it towards decreasing FLW;
- (v) unexploited opportunities to render low-FLW products (i.e. products possibly generating less FLW) more appealing to the consumers;
- (vi) perception of the packaging as an inevitable side waste stream instead of a FLW-reduction opportunity;
- (vii) unequal and unjust allocation of FLW innovation related costs and/or benefits among food chain actors.

The usual approach of directing the attempts to reduce food waste towards the individual consumer, has to be broadened to encompass firstly issues surrounding the material and social conditions in which food is produced/provided [2], [3], but also to rely on economic models to maximise consumers' utility outcomes [4]. As a "wicked" problem, e.g. a symptom of other problems [5], *FLW requires coherent action by various actors emphasising systemic innovations approach* [6] to testing and demonstrating innovations that are (i) interconnected and inter-dependable, innovating not only in the system but also in the ways they interact [7]; (ii) maximising synergies and minimising trade-offs between three sustainability dimensions (i.e. social, economic and environmental) [7] and (iii) leading to the

fundamental changes in both social and technical dimension but primarily in the relations between those [8].

Figure 4. Lock-in effects and the impact on FLW.

To ensure these, ZeroW will take action on the following: (i) focus on stakeholder ecosystem approach to tackle the “wicked” problem of FLW; (ii) focus on demonstrating the impact of systemic as opposed to isolated innovations to reduce FLW; (iii) establish a transparent pathway for scale-up of demonstrated systemic innovations supporting [Farm-to-Fork strategy](#) goals; (iv) advance innovative solutions commercially and ensure their sustainability beyond ZeroW; (v) provide a definition of just transition pathway towards near-zero FLW goals for all stakeholders involved in food supply chain and contribute to the forthcoming policies by providing evidence obtained through testing and demonstrating systemic innovations.

Hence, the ZeroW consortium envisioned to position *ZeroW as a major driving force in reducing the FLW by employing systemic innovations, thus supporting the dual ambition: to halve FLW by 2030 and ensure the enabling conditions for near-zero FLW by 2050.*

2.2 Consortium Overview

ZeroW consortium is comprised of 46 Partners working jointly on developing systemic innovations towards 0FLW supply chain; Partners are spread through 16 different countries, including EU countries, Israel and Serbia. All Partners are contributing to the consortium with their specific expertise, balanced in terms of complementary skills and experiences, geographical differentiation, inclusion and gender equality, and diversity between research, policy and FSC actors.

ZeroW is a highly collaborative and ambitious project, focused around enabling, supporting and assessing the innovations targeting entire FSC, from pre-harvest to consumption; these innovations are tested, validated and demonstrated within nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs), as shown in Figure 1. SILLs are further detailed in Section 2.3.1.

Figure 5. ZeroW WPs.

The project is structured in 11 WPs, each additionally divided in the respective tasks; all tasks and WPs have a dedicated Lead, who is responsible for organising the rest of the consortium to contribute to the relevant WP activities. The interlinkages and strong dependencies between different WPs exists and are illustrated in Annex I. Figure 5 depicts a high-level overview of WPs and dedicated Lead Partners.

2.3 Position Relative to the Industry

Estimates of European food waste levels show that food waste accounts for at least 227 million tonnes of CO₂ per year, which equals roughly 6% of total EU CO₂ emissions in 2012 [9]. In order to achieve sustainability, it is mandatory to tackle food loss and waste and EC has committed to halving per capita food waste at retail and consumer levels by 2030 in addition to reducing food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses (SDG target 12.3) [10]. Addressing food waste and implementing prevention procedures should be seen as a way to

attain savings for all actors involved, including consumers and operators, while redistributing food surplus in a timely manner has an important social dimension and contributes to tackling food poverty and food insecurity.

Although the general understanding of importance and urgency to act on FLW reduction exists, major obstacles are yet to be overcome in order to effectively address the complex problem of FLW. One of those challenges is the lack of common agreement on FLW terminology, where terms such as “Post-harvest Losses”, “Food Losses”, “Food Waste”, and “Food Loss and Waste” are frequently used in an interchangeable manner. Additionally, different authorities define in different ways what “food” is, what “edible food” is and this impacts the definition of “food waste” as well. The most commonly used definitions related to FLW are provided by [EC](#), [FUSIONS](#) project [11] and [FAO](#) [1]. Detailed discussions on different FLW definitions and constraints of each of them is provided in the deliverable D4.1. For the purpose of ZeroW project, we use EC definition of food waste (Amendment to Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste) [12].

FLW occurs in different amounts along food supply chain, and it is estimated as follows [13]:

- Primary production (25%)
- Processing and Manufacturing (23.6%)
- Distribution and Retail (5.1%)
- Consumption (46.3%)

It is important to note here that by EU definition of food waste, food losses at pre-harvest stage are not accounted for, as primary production stage includes only first transport and storage of harvested foods.

In an attempt to broaden the inclusion of waste from different streams that can appear in pre-harvest and harvest stages, [FUSIONS project](#) proposed to account for the crops that are matured but left in the field (Figure 6); however, this is still not inclusive of pre-harvest losses.

Figure 6. Boundaries of FW as defined by Fusion (2014) and EC (2018). Source: EC's Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy 2020 – Food waste brief.

A recent report by Feedback EU [14] showed alarming amounts of food waste produced at the primary production stage, including *harvesting waste, waste left on field, animals/produce lost to a disease, injury or poor harvesting technique* (Table 3). However, data collection and data sharing has proved challenging, with data ownership often being a sensitive topic. In addition to this, data providers need to reach the common level of both technical and semantical interoperability to efficiently implement data sharing practices and foster the design of relevant data spaces. Hence, next in the line of challenges facing complex FLW issues is to address an urgent need to improve and incentivise data collection, including comprehensive coverage of the entire FSC.

Table 3. Estimated food levels in EU. Adopted from Feedback EU (2022).

Sector	Annual Waste, In millions of tonnes	Source
Primary production	89.8 (9) ¹	WWF-UK, 2021
Processing	15.4	FUSIONS, 2016
Wholesale and retail	5.3	UNEP, 2021
Food services	10.5	UNEP, 2021
Households	32.5	UNEP, 2021

¹ Feedback estimates that roughly 10% of EU primary production food waste, nearly 9 million tonnes, will fall within the scope of the EU's current measurement methodology. This is in line with the EU's previous FUSIONS estimate of primary production food waste. This leaves 80.9 million tonnes of primary production food waste excluded from measurement (Feedback EU. 2022)

In recognition of discussed challenges of contemporary food systems, and working in support of the EC dedication to halving per capita food waste at retail and consumer levels by 2030 (SDG Target 12.3) [10], ZeroW has adopted the specific approach illustrated in Figure 7, structured around 4 pillars (presented in circles) incorporated through continuous feedback loops and sustained by 5 innovation guiding principles (presented in rectangles).

Figure 7. ZeroW concept.

To substantiate this approach, ZeroW has identified 9 demonstrators, i.e. SILLs to introduce, test and validate systemic innovations targeting entire FSC.

2.3.1 ZeroW SILLs

An overview of ZeroW SILLs, focusing on the main areas of FLW addressed, i.e. stage of the food supply chain, including pre-harvest, post-harvest, processing and retail, as well as the circular economy initiative spectrum covered, from prevention to valorisation, is presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4. ZeroW SILLs, main areas of FLW addressed and the initiative covered.

SILL		FSC segment addressed					Initiative		
No	Title	Pre-harvest	Post-harvest	Processing	Retail	Consumption	Prevention	Reduction	Valorisation
1	F2F FLW monitoring & assessment	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
2	Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh food products			✓	✓	✓	✓		
3	Wasteless greenhouse solutions for (pre)harvesting aligned with short-term downstream demand	✓	✓				✓		
4	Mobile food valorisation as a service		✓					✓	✓
5	Ugly food early identification, shelf-life assessment & alternative valorisation			✓	✓			✓	
6	Food waste reduction through advanced data-driven production process control & optimisation			✓			✓	✓	
7	Food waste reduction through efficient food bank networks			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
8	Retail food waste valorisation through algae production for high-value applications				✓				✓
9	'Fork to Farm to Fork' (3F): Informing and nudging consumers to make better choices through reverse (dietetics) and forward (FLW, sustainability, affordability) optimisation				✓	✓	✓		

2.4 Key Project Goals

As captured in the GA, "ZeroW aims to demonstrate the applicability of systemic innovations in addressing current food system's FLW lock-in effects and steer a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system". To achieve this, 9 detailed ZeroW objectives are identified, as presented in Figure 8 below. The impacts targets and assessment indicators are evaluated within the scope of WP5.

Figure 8. ZeroW Goals.

Specifically:

Goal 1 aims to (i) provide a stimulating environment for SILLs innovations to thrive; (ii) address specific innovation maturity gaps to enable innovative solutions testing and demonstration; (iii) manage SILLs and support their activities from ideation to demonstration, through organised feedback rounds; (iv) enabling coherent communication between ZeroW SILLs and the impact assessment, scaling-up, commercialisation and policy support activities; (v) enabling evolution of SILLs from initial baseline to a higher level of systemic innovation readiness.

Goal 2 aims to provide digital support for both ZeroW SILLs and future external users and solution developers working to reduce FLW.

Goal 3 focuses on development of data-driven FLW intelligent services, to be used also by external users.

Goal 4 aims to employ 3 assessment perspectives: (i) Systemic Innovation Readiness Level (SIRL) to assess the extent that the SILLs systemic innovations are improving over the course of the project; (ii) Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) to evaluate the environmental, social, and economic impacts of the SILLs during the project; (iii) Just Transition of the SILLs, implying the cost-benefit allocation to different FSC actors.

Goal 5 focuses on scale-up of the FLW systemic innovation solutions and approach, building capacity towards near-zero FLW, stimulating investment in FLW reduction by private and public actors.

Goal 6 targets to: (i) articulate a business- and market-relevant exploitation strategy; (ii) anchor the exploitation, business models, licencing models and go-to-market strategy via robust market sector analyses and commercial solution alignment imperatives.

Goal 7 aims to deliver short- and medium-term FLW policy recommendations, namely by: (i) scaling up the ZeroW SILLs results to 2030 and 2050 utilising data-driven scenarios; (ii) applying Farm-to-Fork FLW economic model to make a qualitative assessment of the alternative policies by 2050, taking into account several factors, such as FSC business practices, consumer behaviour, anticipated FLW innovations, FLW valorisation initiatives, just profit allocations amongst FSC actors, as well as FSC coordination and risk management principles.

Goal 8 aims to maximise the impact of the ZeroW results both during and beyond the project's duration, by engaging with relevant EU, National and global initiatives, as well as developing and deploying appropriate dissemination and communication strategies.

2.5 Commercialisation Goals

ZeroW has adopted a commercialisation approach that is aligned with SILLs' activities. The ultimate goal of this approach is to distinguish viable and sustainable business models, to accelerate market impact of ZeroW solutions, and to define long-term sustainable commercial exploitation models of demonstrated innovations. To enable this and accelerate the project's impact beyond the project end, ZeroW commercialisation activities will be supported by the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem (developed within the scope of task 7.5), ensuring ZeroW outputs and commercial ambitions are sector calibrated and market-relevant. The business ecosystem will also foster early outreach to relevant FLW actors, seeking and encouraging adopters at EU scale.

Although all ZeroW goals have an impact on the commercialisation activities, enabling continuous feedback from project partners and improvement of commercialisation strategy, Goal 6 is specifically focused on commercial exploitation of project outcomes:

ZeroW Goal #6: To advance ZeroW's innovative solutions commercially, and protect the strategic IP.

This Market Analyses report is first of the three expected documents (D7.1 - D7.3) that will underpin ZeroW exploitation strategy and ensure post-project commercial sustainability of project outcomes.

2.6 Work Package 7 Goals

WP7 Exploitation, sustainability and commercialisation of project outputs, aim to (Figure 9):

- (1) advance ZeroW's innovative solutions commercially;
- (2) protect the commercially sensitive and strategic IP through 3 formal Patent filings;
- (3) formulate a business- and market-relevant exploitation strategy with the end goal of self-sustaining revenues and a sustainable commercial trajectory;
- (4) anchor the exploitation, business models, licencing models and go-to-market strategy through robust market sector analyses and commercial solution alignment imperatives.

Figure 9. WP7 Goals.

These goals are to be achieved through dedicated tasks and elaborated in relevant deliverables. Details on WP7 tasks, deliverables and their relation to ZeroW objectives are presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10. WP7 tasks, deliverables and objectives.

All of the WP7 tasks and activities support the overall commercialisation viability, as well as business planning for the ZeroW innovations post-project sustainability.

3 Commercialisation Methodology

Chapter 3 introduces the principles of the commercialisation process led by ICP as the lead partner of WP7 *Exploitation, sustainability and commercialisation of project outputs*. This is a methodology ICP has employed across several research projects, and which has been adapted and tailored specifically to the challenges of ZeroW. The process will be applied across all T7.1 - T7.3 tasks to help ensure that a consistent and coherent approach to commercialisation is maintained across a very complex project with many partners and potential innovations.

The primary goal is to ensure that our analyses of the future viability of innovations emerging from ZeroW strongly focus on customer value and have a clear commercial lens applied when trying to assess the realistic prospects for future viability.

The commercialisation process employed here includes several techniques to examine the assumptions and unknowns that are inherent when forming any new start-up business. The process takes inspiration from many of the principles of a Lean Start-up Methodology and adapts them to be relevant to a multi-year, multi-partner complex research and innovation project.

3.1 Supporting principles for the Commercialisation Methodology

Attempts to translate excellent research into commercially viable products/services are often accompanied with many challenges. As the examples from practice show, many technology-related commercialisation efforts fail due to a lack of product-to-market fit. This is a critical benchmark for success as it implies that the product/service intended for market must meet the direct needs of a sufficiently large group of customers who are willing to pay for it; additionally, the price customers are willing to pay must be at a level that can ensure a sustainable business for the company offering the solution. Commonly, to achieve the product-to-market fit and prevent early failure of business, new start-ups employ principles of the Lean Start-up methodology [15] to help guide their product development.

One of the key pillars of the Lean Start-up methodology, so called “validated learning” implies the process of the main product/service hypothesis validation, relying on incremental assessment of the new product/service potential success before significant investment. User and market feedback is of major importance throughout this “validated learning” process, guiding the developers to progress their product/service from the stage of an idea to the final product/service implementation.

Eric Ries developed the concept of the Lean Start-up Methodology [15] back in 2011. The main goal of Lean Start-up process that Ries presented is to ensure development of sustainable business models, targeted product-to-market fit, and ultimately viable commercial opportunities based on a validated customer need. The process relies on tailored actions presented in Figure 11, where activities such as ideation, product/service development and data/learnings gathering are at the core of the Lean Start-up process, with a strong emphasis on customer validation throughout different iterations.

Figure 11. The Lean Start-up Process Diagram. Adopted from Lean Start-up Methodology. [15]

Although primarily envisaged as a support for the establishment of new companies and/or new products, the Lean Start-up methodology offers clear benefits when used to assess, identify and fortify the commercialisation value of early-stage research. Working within the limits of H2020 Consortia, which includes the complexities of projects spanning multiple partners, countries, different functional engagements and of limited duration, the Lean Start-up Approach provides valuable best practices and insights which are an important foundation for the approach the consortium has adopted in ZeroW. Based on ICP experience in EC funded frameworks, the approach outlined below assists complex projects such as ZeroW to: (i) evaluate innovations developed within the project and distil products/services suitable for the market; (ii) place identified innovations on the market in a faster manner compared to conventional corporate approach; (iii) distinguish sustainable business models to reinforce the commercial trajectory.

3.2 ZeroW Commercialisation Process

By integrating some of the key principles and drivers of the Lean Start-up methodology, including a focus on customers, main hypothesis validation and learning feedback loop, ICP has developed its own ICP Commercialisation Process methodology. This ICP methodology has been successfully applied to the work

packages that are focusing on commercial exploitation of the research projects, including projects funded by the EC, i.e. H2020 and HE projects.

3.2.1 4 Stages of The Commercialisation Process

This section provides a high-level overview of the 4 stages of the Commercialisation Process developed by ICP. Each of the 4 steps will be further detailed in the respective follow-up deliverables, i.e. step 1 and 2 in D7.2 Customer Validation and Solution Alignment; step 3 and 4 in D7.3 Business Models and Business Plan. Here, the introduction to the ICP Commercialisation Process is made.

Figure 12. ICP 4 Steps Commercialisation Process applied to EU-funded projects.

Figure 12 displays the 4 Stages of the Commercialisation Process. Each of the 4 core stages is designed to provide answers to the specific list of questions:

- (1) Customer validation aims to define a specific customer “pain” expressed by early adopters as the most important one to solve.
- (2) Solution alignment focuses on the consortium partner(s) who can provide the most appropriate commercial solution to the identified need, i.e. customer “pain”.
- (3) Business model targets appropriate business model to be applied and to deliver a win-win scenario for both customer and solution provider.
- (4) Growth trajectory goal is to create a business plan for revenue, emphasising the product/service that is commercially viable and potentially investable.

The comprehensive goal of commercialisation, accompanied with the key questions asked, and implemented tasks, methods and tools for each phase of the 4 Stages Commercialisation Process are reviewed in Table 5.

Table 5. Key questions, Tasks, Methods and Tools in Commercialisation Validation.

Commercialisation Validation and Acceleration Methodology				
Goal	Create a substantial body of work that provides a genuine and sustainable trajectory for the commercialisation of project outputs, aiming at developed solutions that are customer focused, validated and endorsed by commercially motivated consortium partners.			
Phase	Customer Validation	Solution Alignment	Business Model Selection	Growth Trajectory
Key Question	Segment and refine specific customer and market wants and needs	Define and align potential product(s)/service(s) to a target market	Select most appropriate business model to acquire and retain profitable customers	Develop a business plan for growth and sustainability
Key Tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Market/Stakeholder Analyses and Segmentation ✓ Solution focused Business Validation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Agree product(s)/service(s) to commercialise/exploit with commercial leaders ✓ Define Product and Service Portfolio (including Patents) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Examine range of potential models ✓ Align business model directly to commercial leader of a specific solution and early adopters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Roadmaps – Financial, People, Product, Marketing, Sales, Funding
Methods and Tools	Questionnaires Guided Discussions SILL Coordinators/WP Leads interviews SILLs feedback Technical WP feedback	Product Definition Workshop Commercial Leader Workshop	Business Model Workshops Business Model Canvas; Value Proposition Canvas, PESTLE/SWOT analysis	Financial Templates Commercial Leaders Interviews
ZeroW Timeline	M1-M24	M13-M24	M25-M46	M25-M46

As the first task in the Customer Validation phase of the ICP Commercialisation Process (and in the case of ZeroW a standalone task), comprehensive market analyses, accompanied with market segmentation and ZeroW anticipated solutions description and positioning in the relevant markets, were performed and are substantiated in the following chapters.

4 ZeroW Market Analyses

To implement a successful commercialisation process, two requirements have to be achieved; firstly it is necessary to have a commercially viable product/service to offer and secondly the offered innovation needs to find its way to the customers willing to pay, i.e. it has to fit the market need. Hence, a crucial step in the successful commercialisation process is to assess the proposed product/service market fit. In order to ensure this, an insight into the characteristics of desired markets is necessary. Additionally, understanding the target markets with associated market drivers and dynamics, facilitates the later stages of the commercialisation process, and ensures developed products/services are commercially viable and of good fit for the validated market need.

This chapter provides an overview of broader FLW market, highlights challenges encountered and elaborates on segmentation of the FLW market in the context of ZeroW.

4.1 FLW market description, segmentation & challenges

As per the GA, ZeroW targets systemic innovations towards a zero FLW supply chain, aiming to reduce FLW at every stage of the FSC, from pre-harvesting to consumption. To fully target ZeroW addressable markets, a broad ZeroW commercialisation strategy focuses on creating new market opportunities within 3 main markets:

- (1) Food Waste Management;
- (2) Green Technology and Sustainability; and
- (3) Smart Agriculture.

The Food Waste Management Market encompasses the full FSC, from F2F and it is projected to be worth \$42.3 billion by 2022 [16], with a CAGR at approximately 6% and with Europe and North America being expected to lead the growth. Similarly, the Green Technology and Sustainability Market, boosted by environmental issues the planet is facing and innovations in ICT technologies, is projected to reach \$36.6 billion by 2025, growing at a CAGR of 26.6% [17]; Europe is expected to be dominant region, projected to reach the size of above \$11 billion by 2025. Finally, Smart Agriculture Market is foreseen to grow significantly over the coming years, at a CAGR of 98.%, reaching \$22 billion by 2025 [18].

Clear market gaps can be identified to be targeted by ZeroW solutions, for example when considering innovations to valorise retail food waste, redistribute food towards food banks, measure and assess the impact of FLW on GHG emissions, monitor crops yield and provide alignment with downstream demand, or to enable ease-of-data management and interpretation by developing OFLW data-driven IT Platform, to name a few.

Figure 13. Overview of ZeroW SILLs innovations.

As ZeroW pursues a very wide scope of innovations, including development of SILLs innovative solutions not only targeting different segments of FSC, but also innovating to contribute to the different circular economy initiatives, including prevention, reduction and valorisation (Figure 13), it is important to develop an exploitation and commercialisation strategy that ensures all specific markets are included in the report, hence more detailed segmentation of relevant FLW market is necessary. The ambiguity to be faced here is to reconcile two conflicting approaches: (1) to develop market analyses broad enough to target all markets segments corresponding to all sectors of FSC, but at the same time (2) to provide market analyses detailed enough to include the specifics for the target markets of all ZeroW anticipated solutions.

Hence, to best encompass all discussed above ICP has developed ZeroW Exploitation and Commercialisation Strategy that segregates ZeroW SILLs and corresponding innovations within four different clusters. Each of the clusters is targeting specific sector(s) of FSC and have a dedicated Lead (Figure 14). Cluster 1 will focus on scalable, data-driven IT Platform that assists actors across the FSC to access the relevant information and make timely decisions to reduce FLW; this cluster will be led by TNO and WIT. Cluster 2 targets pre- and post-harvest innovations and is led by AFL, who are developing wasteless greenhouses for FL

reduction. Cluster 3, led by FCTA, aims to exploit the innovations targeting the food processing stage of FSC, exploiting several innovations including smart packaging for fresh fish products, mobile food valorisation, ugly food identifications and data-driven production optimisation. Finally, innovations in the upper levels of FSC, including wholesale, retail and consumer innovations are the focal points of Cluster 4, which is led by ITENE.

The purpose of clustering is to support individual partners, or group of partners working within the same cluster, to evangelise the commercialisation of developed solutions in alignment with the exploitation strategy of the companies involved. This will be fostered by Cluster Leads who will own the execution of the cluster-specific business plans. Additionally, this group of Cluster Leads will also form the Innovation Management Board, which will be led by the Commercialisation Manager from ICP and will report on its activities to the Council of Partners.

Figure 14. . ZeroW Exploitation and Commercialisation strategy.

4.2 ZeroW Market Analyses Approach

As described in section 2.3.1, ZeroW project consists of 9 Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs), which are anticipated to output innovative solutions spanning the entirety of the FSC; an overview of the expected solution(s) is presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Overview of SILLs innovations.

SILL No.	Solution	Solution (support) components
SILL 1	OFLW Platform	Data Space Big Data Infrastructural Services
SILL 2	Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh fish	Compartmentalised tray for oily fish Barrier and film packaging Freshness indicator label
SILL 3	Deep vision methods and machine learning algorithms to estimate ripeness and quality of tomatoes grown in greenhouses	Cameras Artificial Neural Network (ANN) algorithms to support data obtained by cameras
SILL 4	Mobile food valorisation as a service	Mobile food valorisation unit, offered as a service Regional Food Waste Data Space Healthy, tasteful, minimally processed juices, purees and smoothies
SILL 5	Ugly food early identification, shelf-life assessment and alternative valorisation, initially focused on tomatoes	Multi-sensor platform Software to support multi-sensor platform
SILL 6	Advanced data-driven production process control and optimisation	Integral technical solution composed by the portable NIR, process data modelling and optimisation.
SILL 7	Food waste reduction through efficient food bank networks	Supply and demand prediction tools Handbook of food waste reduction strategies Decision support tool for waste reduction initiatives at food banks; Donation tool for donors on products that are ready for donation
SILL 8	Retail food waste valorisation through algae production for high-value applications	In-store food waste pre-treatment process Hermetic container for transportation of the FLW in reverse logistics Optimisation of the FLW logistics
SILL 9	Informing & Nudging consumers towards reducing FLW	FLW labels for meals, meal packages, recipes A mobile application New recipes, fresh meal kits and semi-prepared packs of ingredients with low FLW impact

The aim of this market analyses report is to assess the commercialisation potential of anticipated SILLs solutions in their respective target markets. Given the broad scope of ZeroW, and in order to make a more comprehensive report, each solution was allocated to a single of the four clusters, as defined in Figure 14. As can be seen in this Figure, although some of the SILLs are addressing lock-in effects in several

clusters, the solutions are allocated in only one cluster based on the stage of the supply chain where the main clients operate and the specific solution fits the best. Therefore, details on anticipated SILL solutions are provided under the respective chapter of this report, i.e. SILL 1 is detailed in Chapter 5; SILL 3 in Chapter 6; SILL 2, SILL 4, SILL 5, and SILL 6 in Chapter 7; and finally SILL 7, SILL 8 and SILL 9 in Chapter 8. Structure of the chapters with the links to detailed analysis of the SILLs' relevant markets is provided in Table 7.

The market analyses followed a bottom-up approach (Figure 15), where the first step was to identify the solutions to be developed in each SILL, and place them in the corresponding exploitation and commercialisation cluster (as per Figure 14). The

next step was to perform an initial search of the state-of-the-art in each cluster, to understand the main markets of interest for each of the project SILLs and respective solution(s). This was followed up with the initial PESTLE analysis, in order to understand different factors, regulations, etc. that may be affecting uptake of innovations (Figure 16); at this stage of the project (year one), PESTLE analysis is performed to support initial market assessment, which will allow for the subsequent commercialisation activities to take place later in the project, i.e. Customer validation & Solution Alignment, Business Models & Business Plan.

Figure 15. ZeroW Market analyses bottom-up approach.

Finally, by comparing existing technologies with the ones proposed in the ZeroW project, it was possible to establish the most suitable target markets for the solutions, and once known, calculate the market size, its dynamics, etc.

Table 7. Structure of D7.1 chapters detailing the specifics of SILLs' relevant markets.

SILL	Cluster	Chapter	Description of innovation	Market overview	Market Drivers & Dynamics	Competing offerings	Key Differentiation	PESTLE	Barriers to entry	Market summary
SILL1 OFLW Platform	1	5	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.4.2	5.5	5.6	5.7
SILL2 Intelligent Packaging	3	7	7.1.1	7.2 7.2.4.1	7.3	7.4.1	7.4.2.1	7.5	7.6	7.7
SILL3 Wasteless greenhouse solutions	2	6	6.1.1	6.2	6.3	6.4	6.4.2	6.5	6.6	6.7
SILL4 Mobile food valorisation	3	7	7.1.2	7.2 7.2.4.2	7.3	7.4.1	7.4.2.2	6.5	6.6	6.7
SILL5 Ugly food early identification	3	7	7.1.3	7.2 7.2.4.2	7.3	7.4.1	7.4.2.3	6.5	6.6	6.7
SILL6 Data driven production process control	3	7	7.1.4	7.2 7.2.4.2	7.3	7.4.1	7.4.2.4	6.5	6.6	6.7
SILL7 Efficient food bank networks	4	8	8.1.1	8.2	8.3	8.4.1	8.4.2	8.5	8.6	8.7
SILL8 Retail food waste valorisation	4	8	8.1.2	8.2	8.3	8.4.1	8.4.2	8.5	8.6	8.7
SILL9 Informing & Nudging consumers	4	8	8.1.3	8.2	8.3	8.4.1	8.4.2	8.5	8.6	8.7

Figure 16. ICP PESTLE Analysis Diagram.

Inputs regarding market analyses were gathered from partners regularly throughout T7.1 duration, and in particular through:

- (1) WP7 organised an interactive session during the SILLs onboarding workshop, where the ZeroW Exploitation & Commercialisation strategy was introduced and inputs concerning (i) SILL placement under the respective Cluster, and (ii) initial understanding towards SILLs anticipated solutions, were collected.
- (2) Workshops organised in the scope of WP7 meetings with the aim to identify (i) solutions SILLs are developing and (ii) markets suitable for the identified solutions.
- (3) Questionnaire prepared by ICP, aiming to gather detailed inputs from the SILL/Cluster Partners on relevant market segments. (Annex II)
- (4) Feedback on ICP identified markets and market segments for each SILL, gathered during WP7 meetings and/or via email communication with relevant Partners.
- (5) Feedback and validation of the proposed approach and identified markets by Innovation Management Board (as presented in Figure 14), namely TNO, AFL, FCTA and ITENE.

Hence, the following chapters present the detailed analyses of markets for each of the anticipated ZeroW solutions; emphasis is put on the markets that partners/SILLs deemed relevant for their innovation.

5 ZeroW OFLW Platform

This chapter provides details of the market(s) relevant for the Cluster 1 of ZeroW Exploitation & Commercialisation strategy (Figure 14). Additionally, available information on data sharing platforms in the sector, as well as other types of solutions targeting FLW reduction are summarised.

As a “wicked” problem, FLW is not the consequence of actions from single sectors, but rather the result of interlinked conditions between all actors in the FSC; as such, solutions covering its entirety are required in order to prevent FLW. The digitalisation of the FSC has the potential to contribute to the FLW reduction and some of the benefits include an increased efficiency through mechanisation and automation, and enhanced decision-making, which will potentially enhance current agricultural knowledge and advice networks; these are key innovation enablers as they are responsible for transforming data into knowledge and advice, and circulate it among relevant stakeholders [19].

The digitalisation of the agri-food sector is a complex venture and depends on a number of technologies that principally enable: 1) gathering relevant data originated in the physical world; and 2) digitalising, safely storing and analysing collected data in the cloud. Some of the technologies with great potential to enable and foster digitalisation of FSC are sensors, internet of things (IoT), big data analytics, artificial intelligence or ledger technologies (Blockchain). However, at present these solutions are commercialised predominantly as isolated applications (and not as a part of an integrated solution, i.e. a platform), and aim to address different problems existing at specific stages of FSC. Certain technologies, such as Blockchain, are applied along the entire FSC, but these solutions are normally not associated with FLW. There are currently other platforms designed specifically to tackle FLW by connecting actors working at different stages of the FSC, so the surplus from one level can be used by stakeholders at a different level, thus preventing waste. However, they are often aimed at regional areas and have a narrower scope than the solution proposed in ZeroW; an example of this is the [DjustConnect](#) platform, which will be used as a foundation for the FLW-focused regional dataspace to be developed in this project (details in Section 5.1). Details on the ZeroW proposed innovation and integrated technologies are provided in the following sections.

5.1 ZeroW's proposed innovations

A **0FLW Platform** will be developed and tested under SILL 1. The IT platform will be open and data-driven, and it will be intended to monitor and assess the levels of FLW produced at all stages of the FSC; as such, the end users will be all actors in the FSC (Figure 17). They will be offered an integrated solution that is especially designed to capture, analyse and share data related to FLW. Hence, the 0FLW Data Platform aims to empower the stakeholders to make smarter and more sustainable decisions when dealing with FLW prevention and reduction, with the goal of addressing the requirements set by SDG 12.3.1. (Global Food Loss and Waste, the Delegated Decision (EU) 2019/1597 and the Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/2000). Additionally, this solution will be tested and demonstrated in two EU countries,

Romania and Slovenia, making sure to take into account geographical diversities of actors, as well as local FLW initiatives and stakeholders.

Figure 17. Anticipated potential use cases of the OFLW IT Platform.

The architecture of ZeroW platform is shown in Figure 18. A base layer and the infrastructure for the platform will be provided by the OFLW Data Space, accompanied with a proven business model foundation to incentivise data sharing opportunities within the FLW sector [20]. The OFLW Data Space establishment alongside with the methodology for designing governance and collaborative business models are to be detailed in deliverables D2.1 – D2.7.

The middle layer of the platform architecture is occupied by intelligent services, where the generic AI modules will be developed as central intelligent modules and further utilised by data-driven near zero FLW smart applications (e.g. third layer of the OFLW Platform) (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Architecture of the ZeroW platform.

Hence, in addition to 0FLW Data Space, the following elements will aid in the establishment of the 0FLW Platform:

1. **Regional Food Waste Data Space** will be developed using the sharing services provided by the [DjustConnect](#) platform and within the scope of SILL4. Regional Food Waste Data Space will help to connect identified FSC stakeholders, such as suppliers, processors, intermediaries and consumers. Potentially, new software applications can be built relying on the Regional Food Waste Data Space, generating new value and business opportunities for actors. As a part of 0FLW Data Space, DjustConnect services, together with the application services, will enable full traceability for consumers and transparency on the value distributed over the different actors. Initially, the Regional Food Waste Data Space will serve to connect customers and operators of the mobile processing unit from SILL 4 (detailed in Section 7.4.2).
2. **Federated catalogue** will be developed as a part of WP2, focusing on development of APIs required for secure exchange of information about other services and (meta)information. “Federated” refers to it being implemented as a collaboration of multiple IT services. The catalogue will be developed to be a generic component that can be used for other data space implementations, and will enable the discovery of businesses and other IT services, acting like the “yellow pages” (i.e. organised directories of relevant businesses) for services and information. This way, participants will be able to look for companies with specific offers, for example food processing companies can offer their processing capabilities, while food producers can inform of food surpluses/availability to other companies. The main advantage of this catalogue is its generic functionality.

3. **Data analytics**, i.e. development and deployment of **Big Data Infrastructural Services (BDIS)**, will also aid in development of OFLW Platform, enabling the analysis of large structured or unstructured datasets. This will allow integration of FLW data from different sources and store it so the relevant information can be easily accessible.
4. **ZeroW Smart Applications**, will be developed as the top-layer of OFLW Platform, they will utilize the OFLW Data Space functionality as well as Generic and Specific AI modules and BDIS. ZeroW Smart Applications will contribute to tackling the FLW problem by connecting the data platform and application user, thus enabling data to be collected and shared. Initially, these data will be fed into the platform through the innovations from the ZeroW SILLs, while afterwards this is planned to be extended to the external FSC stakeholders. The list of applications to be developed by the SILLs and ZeroW technical partners is presented in Table 8 below.

Table 8. ZeroW Smart Applications.

Application	Relevant SILL	Description
F2F FLW monitoring and assessment	SILL 1	SILL 1 will output these tools to assess the FLW and GHG impact.
FLW-GHG impact assessment	SILL 1	
IoT-based food shelf-life calculation	SILL 2	These will be initially based on outputs of the smart packaging designed in SILL 2, at first for salmon, but with the possibility to be extend to other food products (Section 7.1.1).
Deteriorating food alerting	SILL 2	
Optimal harvesting scheduling	SILL 3	This application will be feeding from the results on the hardware used to monitor and predict optimal harvest timing based on ripeness of tomatoes grown in greenhouses, proposed under SILL 3 (Section 6.1.1).
Deteriorating food auctioning	SILL 4	This is related to the mobile processing unit for surplus fruits and vegetables to be developed in SILL 4 (Section 7.1.2).
Ugly food identification	SILL 5	This application will use the data from the multi-sensor platform using infrared imaging, to be developed as part of SILL 5 (Section 7.1.3).
FLW-optimised food processing	SILL 6	This application will build upon the outcomes provided under the innovations developed in SILL 6 (Section 7.1.4).
Food banks demand/supply prediction and FLW optimisation	SILL 7	This application will be based on the outcomes of SILL 7 (Section 8.1.1).
FLW logistics optimisation	SILL 8	This tool aims to improve the management of food that, despite all efforts, ends up wasted and is required to be revalorised into high added value products and ingredients, which requires inverse logistics (from retailers back to the processing/revalorising facilities) (outcomes of SILL 8, Section 8.1.2).
FLW-nutrient-GHG e-labels	SILL 9	The data collected as part of the development of SILL 9 (Section 8.1.3) will be used to provide information through the platform (via e-labels) to consumers regarding the nutrient content and FLW/GHG impacts of the products they consume. Additionally, recipes to prevent FLW will be developed.
Low FLW, high nutrient recipes based on ingredient availability	SILL 9	
Food chain Systemic Innovation Readiness Assessment	All SILLs	This will be applied to all innovations developed in the ZeroW project.

The ZeroW Platform aims to provide an integrated solution for tackling FLW along the entire FSC by enabling knowledge sharing and collective intelligence. As will be demonstrated in the following market analysis, this platform will aim at fulfilling the gap in the FLW market, as the state-of-the-art focus on narrower problems at discrete stages of the FSC, mainly at retail level; they are not well suited to address FLW at regional, national or European contexts. Although many stakeholders across the FSC could benefit from the proposed solution, and it has the potential to provide societal and environmental benefits, there is not yet a well-established target market that could completely accommodate the platform. However, the market is maturing and evolving, and the factors affecting its uptake (in terms of market dynamics, regulation, competition, etc., as discussed in the following sections) have been identified according to the underlying technologies that form part of the platform, such as Internet of Things (IoT), Blockchain, data analytics, etc. This is because the launch of the platform will affect (and be affected by) these markets, potentially opening new market segments aimed specifically to tackle FLW.

5.2 Market Overview

5.2.1 Introduction

In general terms, a platform is a type of business ecosystem, which aims to bring together all relevant actors to form an economic community. Platforms were facilitated with the advent of the internet, cloud computing and big data, and have since become the focus of the mainstream business models [21]. Currently, and as already mentioned, there is no equivalent platform in the market similar to the one proposed in the ZeroW project, so it is expected not to see a specific well-established market yet for such a holistic solutions addressing the “wicked” problem of FLW. Nevertheless, advances in technologies that support digitalisation of FSC such as internet of things (IoT), cloud technologies (mainly intended to store information about food products and make it accessible to retailers and consumers through barcodes, web sites, etc.), big data analytics, blockchain (ledger) technologies, computing power, artificial intelligence and cybersecurity, will foster the digitalisation efforts and sustainability in food systems, opening the market opportunities for digital solutions like OFLW Platform and ZeroW Smart Applications. As the OFLW Platform is addressing the recognised need in an emerging market, the supporting market analysis has been focused on analysing markets associated to the individual technologies that compose the final innovation, i.e. infrastructure and intelligent services (as seen in Figure 18). This approach brings a number of market segments together, demonstrating the potential of a holistic solution. Furthermore, market analysis is emphasising the technologies and their associated markets as development and readiness of those will not only affect the launch of the platform,

but also enable the establishment of market opportunities for digital solution such as the OFLW Platform. Finally, it is probable that once it is launched, the platform will affect markets associated to the individual technologies, possibly creating opportunities to establish new market segments. The smart applications (described in the upper layer of Figure 18 and Table 8) will be analysed separately, each in the corresponding cluster where they are intended to create added value for the main end users.

5.2.2 Existing solutions

As discussed above, following technologies are supporting the building of the OFLW Platform; additionally, these technologies have been identified as points of interest for relevant partners.

5.2.2.1 *Sensors and Internet of Things (IoT)*

Sensors and IoT technologies generate large amounts of data that can be analysed using big data analytics. IoT can potentially improve communication capabilities between actors of the FSC [22].

IoT can enable the automation of multiple processes in the FSC, including data collection and storage in the cloud. These data could then be used along the entire supply chain, from farm to fork. The data generated by IoT sensors can be stored and combined with other technologies such as Blockchain (Section 5.2.2.3), enabling full traceability and automatic execution of smart contracts, which can be automatically triggered by the occurrence of specific conditions measured by the sensors [23].

Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technologies allow real-time data collection along the FSC and permit automation [24]. RFID technologies can be useful to track the remaining shelf life of perishable food products [24] and ultimately reduce food losses related to logistics/distribution [22]. Track-and-tracing resolution provided by RFID can be variable; the choice will depend on the specific application and its economic feasibility. In the case of perishable food, container-level tags are commonly implemented, but pallet- and item-level tags (these refer to RFID tags that are applied to a pallet or to individual items, respectively) are rarely used due to high costs relative to the selling price of the individual item [24]. This affects the granularity of the gathered data, which can ultimately lead to mismanagement [24]. For example, in a cold supply chain, temperature sensors can monitor differences of up to 35% between pallets, depending on their location inside the truck container; this difference in temperature corresponds to the wastage rate in cold FSCs [24]. Once at destination, a single sample from one of the pallets in the container is analysed to determine the quality of the entire shipment; the truckload will be accepted or rejected depending on the results. This can lead to either unnecessary

waste if a generally good-quality container is rejected because of a randomly selected bad sample; or to safety risks if a bad container is accepted based on just one good sample [24]. Pallet- and item-level RFID tags facilitate higher-resolution temperature monitoring, preventing food waste while ensuring quality [24].

5.2.2.2 *Big data analytics*

Big data uses algorithms to obtain insights from datasets obtained from a variety of sources. The main aim is to identify patterns, trends and associations that would not be evident otherwise. Big data can be used to improve the decision-making process in the agri-food supply chain (AFSC), mainly for crop/animal production, waste and traceability management [25]:

- Plant/Livestock management – Data coming from sensors used in smart farming (Section 6.2.2.1.2) can, for example, provide insights on plant performance in different conditions, helping farmers to make data-driven decisions to improve productivity and efficiency. In livestock farming, big data can be used for development of diagnostic and herd management tools to control health, improve animal welfare, etc.
- Waste management – Data from IoT can be analysed to identify food waste hotspots along the AFSC and devise strategies to prevent it, reducing economic loss.
- Traceability – As part of the logistics management process, it is used to capture and transmit information about a food product through each stage of the AFSC to ensure quality and safety [25]. Traceability is key to allow rapid recall of products at risk of contamination. Big data can simplify this process. Blockchain technologies are also starting to be used with this purpose in AFSCs (below).

Big data analytics and better design interfaces can potentially make the decision-making process simpler, more timely and better aligned with agricultural knowledge [19].

5.2.2.3 *Ledger technologies – Blockchain*

Blockchain is a ledger technology that emerged in 2008 as a way to make secure online transactions with cryptocurrencies, and this is still its main application [26]. However, it offers great versatility, becoming an important tool to store different types of information in a secure, decentralised and immutable way. For this reason, it is gaining popularity in research for application in several industries, in particular in the logistics and supply chain management sectors.

In the food & beverages industry, this technology allows all stakeholders in the supply chain to monitor the progress of the goods, harvest characteristics, pertinent documents, bills of lading, etc [27]. It also allows food processing/manufacturing

companies to search and select raw materials, suppliers and distributors and/or retailers for their products through blockchain-based platforms [27].

Blockchain is a decentralised ledger to record transactions in chronological order. Thanks to its attributes, it supports collaboration and resource sharing that can be used in the FSC to:

1. Track and trace. The recording of all transactions can be used to ensure the integrity of food products as they move through the supply chain. It can also be used in combination with sensors/IoT, to provide storage data of agricultural products to all stakeholders. Thus, blockchain can enable a common platform for data collection along the entire FSC for better management practices [26]. This is currently the main application of the technology in the food industry [26].
2. Enable collaboration and integration for shared information along the FSC. Blockchain can automate the process of sharing information, reducing uncertainties related to changes in demand at different stages, as well as optimisation of the FSC allowing for rapid and targeted recall of food products and better management of highly perishable goods. Interoperability problems on data sharing among different actors can be overcome using GS1 standards [26].
3. Automation. The combination of blockchain with other technologies (Electronic Data Interchange, XML, API-based B2B) can be used to improve big data integration and automation processes. This enables faster deliveries, reduced inventory and quicker responses to consumers' inquiries [26].
4. Waste management. Blockchain can improve management of FLW along the food supply chain, as it increases visibility and helps identify FLW hotspots. Additionally, better production/inventory management can reduce the risk of spoilage, while more targeted food recalls (limited to what is contaminated and a possible risk for consumption, instead of recalling a complete batch) can indirectly minimise food waste [26].

The application of blockchain in the food industry is very recent; as such, widespread implementation is still facing challenges that require to be addressed. These are related to:

- scalability – problems handling and storing large amounts of data and difficulties processing high numbers of transactions in a short time, which are characteristic of multi-tier FSCs;
- security issues – data theft and risks to confidentiality resulting from the enhanced visibility to all members of a network.

However, blockchain can enhance capabilities of other technologies such as IoT, big data, AI, etc. creating new efficiencies in Industry 4.0 [26]. Widespread implementation of Blockchain could benefit from using different languages (i.e.:

Ethereum or Hyperledger Sawtooth), that would enable faster implementation and integration with other systems, helping to overcome the challenges previously mentioned [23].

5.2.3 Market size

As it has been mentioned earlier, there is no clear existing target market for the OFLW Platform proposed in the ZeroW project because there is not any equivalent solution on the market to the best of our understanding. However, the launch of the platform will be affected by the underlying technologies that comprise it, and once operative, it will affect these markets, even opening the possibility to create new market segments for these technologies as they will be used for a new purpose, different from previous applications. The most relevant markets for the platform are:

Blockchain in Agriculture and Food Supply Chain Market – Valued at \$133.4 million in 2020, this market is still in its early stages of development, but is expected to grow rapidly: it will reach a value of \$948.6 million by 2025 growing at a significant Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 48.1% between 2020 and 2025 [27].

By application, the market is divided into product traceability, tracking & visibility, payments & settlements, smart contracts and governance, risk and compliance management (Figure 19). Although none of these fits exactly with the application proposed in ZeroW, the most relevant one in the context of the ZeroW platform is the product traceability, tracking and visibility. This segment was valued at \$61.4 million in 2020, holding the largest share of all applications. It is also expected to grow at the highest CAGR during the forecasted period to a value of \$490.2 million in 2025 [27].

Figure 19. Market value of Blockchain applications in agriculture and FSC [27].

The growth in the Blockchain in Agriculture and Food Supply Chain Market is mainly driven by the increased need for food traceability due to a rise in the number of

cases of food fraud and food insecurity [27]. The COVID-19 pandemic is further accelerating this trend as Blockchain can facilitate an optimised supply chain, provide flexible sourcing, increase safety and boost compliance [27].

Digital Transformation Market – The Digital Transformation market makes use of digital technologies to create new, or modify existing business processes, culture and customer experience to meet changing market requirements.

The Digital Transformation Market is large; it was worth approximately \$521.47 billion in 2021 and growing at a 19.1% CAGR, it will reach a value of \$1,247.5 billion by 2026 [28]. By technology, the market is segmented in mobility/social media, cloud computing, cybersecurity, artificial intelligence (AI), big data and analytics, IoT, and others (which include robotics and blockchain). The market value of these segments is summarised in Figure 20. In the context of ZeroW's innovations, the target segments are Cloud Computing, Cybersecurity, AI, Big Data & Analytics and IoT.

Figure 20. The Digital Transformation Market, segmented by technology [28].

This market currently does not include the food and beverages sector as vertical. The introduction of solutions such as the platform proposed in ZeroW will contribute to the digitalisation of the food & beverage industry, thus opening the possibility to create new opportunities in the digital transformation market with a new vertical in the FSC.

5.3 Market Dynamics

Factors that influence the markets relevant to the OFLW IT platform, including opportunities driving market growth, as well as any potential restraints and challenges, are discussed below.

5.3.1 Market Drivers

- ✓ The increasing global population is demanding better productivity from food systems, while concerns about sustainability are imposing restrictions in the use of current unsustainable agricultural practices. This will lead to the increased

adoption of new technologies aimed to optimise production while safeguarding the environment; in this sense, digitalisation is considered a key enabler.

- ✓ Globalisation is adding complexity to FSCs, which are becoming fragmented and scattered, spurring the adoption of digital solutions and data analytics to optimise them [25].
- ✓ The rise in demand for seasonal products all year round is boosting imports of food products, which have higher chances of introducing contaminated food products in the supply chain. This will favour the adoption of technologies that enable track and tracing, such as IoT and blockchain [24].
- ✓ The necessity to reduce production costs will lead food companies to optimise supply chains, favouring adoption of new technologies that allow it [25].
- ✓ Increased requirements for all stakeholders of the FSC to understand their roles and contribution towards FLW reduction and food security will drive the data analytics trend [29].
- ✓ Climate change is propelling the adoption of big data tools in agriculture to ensure food availability, as it offers better predictions under highly uncertain environmental conditions [25].
- ✓ Increasing public awareness and concerns about the magnitude and impact of FLW on the planet.
- ✓ The agri-food market is highly fragmented with numerous, often small market players at all levels of the supply chain. This has proved limiting in acquiring an overarching view on the status of FLW, mainly due to the limited capabilities of different actors to share their knowledge with other stakeholders. These issues, along with the increased awareness about the impacts of FLW, will favour the development of tools to centralise and harmonise data on FLW, design new measures to prevent it and quantify associated impacts [30].
- ✓ Tightening safety regulations and the necessity to demonstrate sustainability/origin claims of foods to gain consumers' trust are pushing the demand for traceability tools, fostering the adoption of big data/blockchain in the FSC [25], [25].
- ✓ Current food management systems face several issues such as data fragmentation and discrepancy, which often results in a lack of transparency and interoperability among different systems, consequently leading to the difficulties to track and trace products. New technologies such as blockchain can solve these problems, which will encourage adoption [26].
- ✓ Current solutions aiming to digitalise FSCs are isolated, and often intended solely as a solution to problems related to specific stages in the FSC. However, to achieve a significant reduction in FLW, instead of focusing on isolated levels of the supply chain, a tool that allows effective, data-driven FLW management covering the entirety of the FSC is required. In this sense, the use of digital

technologies will gain traction as they facilitate data sharing and collaboration among actors working across different stages of the FSC.

- ✓ The popularity of digital technologies such as Blockchain among retailers and distributors is rising due to better supervision and data management capabilities [27].
- ✓ High levels of post-harvest losses and food wastage are driving blockchain as a way to track the supplied food. Blockchain can be used by retailers/processors/logistics to track in real-time the requirements of the food products moving along the supply chain, as well as to track expiry dates at retail/food service stages; thus helping prevent FLW [27].

5.3.2 Market Restraints

- ✗ Historically the agri-food sector has had a low drive for research, and this can delay the implementation of new technologies [25].
- ✗ There is a lack of harmonisation in the definitions of FLW; this leads to difficulties to measure the scale of the problem (as discussed in Section 2.3). Different implications of different definitions may be impacting the extent of the measures taken to prevent it: current efforts centre more on reducing food waste and less on food loss.
- ✗ Digitalisation requires significant investments, which may be difficult to attain for SMEs. These constitute the majority of stakeholders in the European agri-food industry [31].
- ✗ Low levels of private investment in the EU may hamper the adoption of innovative technologies for FLW management at all levels of the food supply chain [31].
- ✗ Big data analytics and digitalisation technologies require infrastructure (internet access, computers, etc.) that may be underdeveloped in rural areas.
- ✗ Lack of awareness about the potential of data analytics in agriculture. Although adoption of smart farming technologies is increasing among farmers [32], the data is not being used to make evidence-based decisions but rather to simply adapt traditional methods to more modern practices [25].
- ✗ Lack of awareness about what benefits of digitalisation (such as Blockchain) can bring to stakeholders [27].
- ✗ Lack of regulations and standards for Blockchain are affecting uptake by organisations as they may consider it too risky to implement [27].

5.3.3 Opportunities

- ❖ Advancements in computing power and IoT are allowing the collection and analysis of sizeable datasets from different sources (sensors, online sources,

commercial/consumer tracking methods, etc.), enabling application of big data analytics in the food sector [25].

- ❖ Agricultural robotics and digitalisation could enable early labelling and tracking in the food chain. This will result in improved traceability capabilities and safety along it. This earlier labelling can help gather metadata from the lower levels of the supply chain such as retail and consumer stages (i.e. changes in demand, consumer preferences, etc.), to be sent upstream, back to the field, to optimise agricultural production and minimise waste [33].
- ❖ The ever-increasing adoption of big data across multiple industries will favour its application in other less research-driven sectors such as the agri-food industry [25].
- ❖ Digitalisation can act as an enabler for the development of platforms for the engagement of farmers with other stakeholders of the supply chain [19].
- ❖ The acceleration in adoption of smart farming technologies is generating large amounts of data that can be used to improve the knowledge about plant performance [25], potentially improving quality of produce. This can indirectly reduce food loss at farm gate.
- ❖ Higher adoption rates of information technologies along the supply chain will favour the adoption of standards and sharing of information in real-time among actors from different stages of the FSC.
- ❖ Increase in investments in agri-food Blockchain. From Jan to May 2018, venture fund investments in blockchain technology summed to \$1.3 billion, which proves that investors trust the future of the technology [27].
- ❖ Blockchain can be applied to reduce supply chain complexities in the agri-food sector by addressing organisational issues (execution of operational plans, adherence to board restrictions and sustaining the competitive nature of the market) [27].
- ❖ The increasing amounts of data generated through smart agricultural applications can be used to feed blockchain technologies, fomenting its use for traceability, smart contracts and payments [27].

5.3.4 Challenges

- ∇ Lack of standards, limiting interoperability between different systems. There are several digital platforms for data analytics from different providers, but these operate independently from one another; data cannot flow freely between platforms, hindering knowledge sharing [32, 27].
- ∇ Issues on data management and ownership: currently few companies own the majority of data and infrastructure [33].

- ∇ Limitations in the availability and quality of data (which is also fragmented) can limit implementation of analytics tools [25]. Blockchain and related protocols may help overcome this challenge.
- ∇ Privacy concerns about the data generated [25].
- ∇ The lack of a technically skilled workforce can limit the amount of data mining and analytical tasks that can be performed [25].
- ∇ Liability issues: lack of consensus about responsibility when a data-related problem arises [25].
- ∇ End users require higher skills and knowledge to be able to translate the data into better informed decisions [26].
- ∇ Mismanagement of data from precision agriculture is a challenge for the implementation of blockchain. Standardisation of data is required to achieve uniformity in operations [27].

5.4 Competitor Analysis

The summary of competitor offerings relevant for the ZeroW OFLW Platform and associated innovations, as well as key differences and advantages of ZeroW anticipated solutions are discussed below.

5.4.1 Competitor Offerings

It is important to note that most of currently available solutions aimed to digitalise the FSC are not specifically intended to address FLW, although they may be indirectly affecting it. Furthermore, only a few of them cover the entirety of the supply chain, while the majority are intended for a small subset of stages, or even for a single stage of the FSC. To the best of our knowledge, a holistic solution for gathering and sharing of data across the entire FSC and specifically designed to tackle FLW is still not available.

The list below provides an overview of relevant commercially available solutions on the market:

- **Commercially available data spaces:**
 - **JoinData**, the Netherlands (<https://join-data.nl/en>). Non-profit organisation that has developed an independent data platform offering various data sets from farmers to other users (data consumers).
 - **DKE-Agrirouter**, Germany (<https://my-agrirouter.com/en/>). This platform provides connection between farmer's machinery and different agricultural software.
 - **API-AGRO**, France (<https://api-agro.eu/en/>). This platform offers an open catalogue of reference data from heterogeneous sources in the agricultural sector.

- Agrimetrics, UK (<https://www.agrimetrics.co.uk/>). Platform dedicated to help agri-food stakeholders find food, farming and environmental data, as well as to manage it.
 - Go4Fresh Platform, India (<https://go4fresh.com/home>). This platform was created with the mission to bring together fruit and vegetable producers and consumers, simplifying the supply chain and supporting local trade and SMEs.
- Other available solutions intended to digitalise the entire FSC or different stages of it, are:
- IBM Food Trust, US (<https://www.ibm.com/blockchain/solutions/food-trust>). This solution uses blockchain to connect all actors of the food supply chain, mainly with traceability purposes, but can also address FLW by identifying those points in the supply chain that generate the most FLW, enabling targeted action against it. The system is already in use for traceability purposes by large companies such as Nestlé and Walmart.
 - SAP Leonardo, Germany (<https://www.sap.com/index.html>). SAP develop solutions for managing business operations. SAP Leonardo, zero waste option, is mainly intended as a tool for food retail businesses. It functions by forecasting the demand of perishable products, reducing food waste and maximising profits.
 - OriginTrail, Slovenia (<https://origintrail.io/>). Non-profit organisation that has created an open-source protocol based on GS1 standards for interoperability between blockchain and legacy systems. One of the use cases they are researching is the application of blockchain technologies in food traceability, in partnership with the [British Standards Institute \(BSI\)](#) [26].
 - RIPE.IO, US (<https://www.ripe.io/>). Application of IoT, blockchain and machine learning tools to obtain real-time data for management and traceability purposes. They offer solutions for actors across the entire FSC, from food producers and distributors to retailers and food service businesses. In September 2018 they secured investment of \$2.4 million from Maersk Group and Relish, to be used for scaling up operations [27].
 - Delicia, Estonia (<https://www.delicia.io/>). Decentralised food network powered by Blockchain and AI, intended to reduce FLW. It offers customers real-time search of surplus food at retail, restaurants, etc. level, for a discounted price.
 - Zest Labs, US (<https://www.zestlabs.com/>). Supply chain solution providing end-to-end visibility of food products, with the aim to increase sales and reduce food waste. This system is already in use by Costco (Zest Fresh

solution). Data collection and analysis is made autonomously using IoT sensors. The company's mission is to reduce food waste by managing the FSC in a proactive manner (prevention).

- FoodLogiQ, US (<https://www.foodlogiq.com/>). They offer solutions for the food industry: supply chain management, monitoring, track & tracing and recall.
- Agritask, Israel (<https://start.agritask.com/>). In August 2020 they received \$26 million in funding from EIT Food and Liechtenstein Group to help farmers and agribusinesses to better manage data.
- Blockhead Technologies, Canada (<https://blockheadtechnologies.com/>). They developed the STAMP Supply platform based on blockchain, to track supply chains with the aim to optimise them and simplify traceability.
- AgriDigital, Australia (<https://www.agridigital.io/>). Platform (pilot stage) intended for the grain supply chain in Australia, based on Blockchain. Their main objective is to reduce risks for farmers so they can secure payments for orders before delivering the grain, protecting them against sudden changes in demand happening downstream the supply chain. This tool may be indirectly reducing food losses that are a consequence of sudden changes in demand.
- The Climate Corporation (<https://www.climate.com/>). They developed the FieldView platform, offering critical field data to farmers, providing better monitoring and decision-making capabilities.
- Rfxcel Antares Vision Group, US (<https://rfxcel.com/>). Developed the Rfxcel Food and Beverage Traceability (rFBT), which is a system to identify and track produce to facilitate product recalls in case of a problem arising along the supply chain.
- Aqueduct, World Resources Institute (<https://www.wri.org/aqueduct>). This company offers open-data platforms at global scale for better decision making and management, especially intended for farmers.
- TE-FOOD, Germany (<https://te-food.com/>). Development of blockchain solutions for actors in the FSC, including product identification and serialisation, data capture, storage and analytics. These allow automation and optimisation of the supply chain, traceability and more targeted product recalls in case a problem arises (potentially reducing FLW).
- Foodwatch Platform, Dubai (<https://foodwatch.dm.gov.ae/>). Digital network platform developed by the Food Safety Department of the Dubai Municipality with the objective to facilitate food data sharing between stakeholders of the FSC. It uses digital monitoring, data analytics and applications to allow complete traceability of food products. It also provides

nutritional information for all foods served in participating foodservice businesses.

- Phenix, France (<https://www.wearephenix.com/en/>). Start-up founded in 2014, dedicated to reduce food waste by helping manufacturers and retailers manage their stock more efficiently, and redistributing their excess stock with a discount. They claim to have saved 10 million tons of products that would have ended up wasted otherwise.
- OLIO, UK (<https://olioex.com>). Application that connects consumers and retailers to prevent their excess food from going to waste, for example home-grown vegetables, surplus food from supermarkets, bought groceries, etc. Other products, apart from food, can also be shared through the application. The application is available worldwide.
- KARMA, Sweden (<https://old.karma.life/>). Food rescue mobile application that allows retailers to sell surplus food to consumers for a discount. The app operates in 225 cities, has 1.4 million users and 9,200 retailers. They have also developed, in partnership with Electrolux, a fridge that allows efficient storage and pickup of products by customers, without requiring staff assistance.
- Invisible foods, the Netherlands (<https://www.invisiblefoods.io/>). Company whose mission is to prevent food loss and waste at retail stage. They are developing an integral solution comprising different tools such as AI to identify food that will expire in the near future, a marketplace to match products of a certain quality with buyers seeking this quality, and a certification scheme to communicate the quantities of produce that are avoided from discarding. To match foods of certain qualities, cameras and imaging software is used in the warehouse to automatically identify items and determine whether they have imperfections, damage, etc., allowing retailers to track them and sell to the appropriate buyers before they deteriorate. The system also allows traceability, having a verifiable record of food waste and preventive efforts and CO₂ emission savings. This can be used to label the products or applied on large datasets such as the FAO's food waste dataset. The solution is offered to customers following a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) business model.
- FoodChain, UK (<https://www.joinfoodchain.com/>). Company focused on connecting food service businesses and consumers directly with suppliers, potentially reducing intermediaries, allowing fairer prices for farmers/producers while keeping competitive prices for consumers.
- FoodCloud, Ireland (<https://food.cloud/>). Mobile application that connects companies in the food industry (retailers) with charities, so the surplus of

- the first can be redistributed to the latter, helping reduce food waste. They offer technology for food banks so they can improve their operations.
- Too Good To Go, UK (<https://toogoodtogo.co.uk/en-gb>). Mobile application that connects consumers with retailers and food service companies, so the surplus food from these businesses can be sold and their sunk costs minimised.
 - MyFoody, Italy (<https://myfoody.it/>). Mobile application to find supermarkets offering discounts on products that are nearing expiration date.
 - ResQ Club, Finland (<https://www.resq-club.com/>). Mobile application that connects retail and food service companies (restaurants and cafes) with consumers, offering them surplus food such as meals, snacks or groceries with a discount of up to 50%. Operating mostly in Finland, but also in some cities in Sweden and Germany (Berlin).
 - EcoFoodly, Australia (<https://www.ecofoodly.org/>). Application that connects consumers with partnering supermarkets and grocers to sell their excess foods and those that are nearing their expiry date, for a discount.
 - Oddbox, UK (<https://www.oddbox.co.uk/>). Company connecting farmers to consumers, rescuing fresh fruits and vegetables that may otherwise be discarded due to excess production or aesthetic reasons. Company operated on subscription based model. Additionally, suggested recipes can be found on their website, including zero-waste recipes.
 - EroGo, United Arab Emirates (<https://www.eroego.com/>). Application intended for customers to access and buy products that are close to expiry date at discounted prices. The app also offers a delivery service.
 - Seva Kitchen, India (<http://www.sevakitchen.org/>). Food sharing platform that connects food donors with recipients in real time. It is aimed especially to address food surplus from large events such as festivals, parties, etc.
- Projects researching similar platforms aiming at the digitalisation of agriculture/FSC:
- The [Internet of Food and Farm 2020 \(IoF2020\) Project](#) aims to facilitate the uptake of IoT in food and farming industries, by bringing together agri-businesses and ICT suppliers. Launched in 2017, the project has raised around €30 million.
 - The [DEMETER Project](#) aims to deploy interoperable IoT for agricultural applications for increased security, privacy and confidentiality across the FSC. The project started in 2019 and features 20 pilots and 25 deployment sites involving 18 countries and 60 partners.

- The [Agricultural Interoperability and Analysis System \(ATLAS\) Project](#) is developing a digital service Interoperability Network platform for agricultural applications and a sustainable ecosystem enabling data-driven agriculture. This will enable the combination of different agricultural machinery, sensors systems and data analytics tools. The project started in 2019.
- The [DataBio \(data-driven bioeconomy\) Project](#) had the objective to increase the productivity of the bioeconomy by providing an interoperable big-data platform to be deployed on top of the end users' infrastructure so they can access the underlying high-processing capabilities.
- The [FiSpace Project](#) created a business-to-business collaboration platform and mobile application, working as a social network for agri-food businesses that allows to contact other businesses, exchange data, manage processes etc. Funded by the EU FP7 programme, it finished in 2015.
- The [Ploutos Project](#) (A Sustainable Innovation Framework To Rebalance Agri-Food Value Chains) aims to create opportunities for changes that can rebalance the value chain in the agri-food system towards more environmentally, socially and economically sustainable system. The [FoodShare](#) platform has been developed within the scope of the project, to facilitate the transfer of surplus food from farmers to socially disadvantaged groups in Serbia and North Macedonia.

5.4.2 ZeroW Solution and key differentiating points

As mentioned previously in the document, OFLW Platform aims to digitalise the entire FSC; no other available solution is aimed at full FSC but rather at isolated stages, offering indirect impact on FLW reduction. Contrary to that, OFLW Platform will offer a holistic approach to data collection, transparency, forecasting, monitoring and managing FLW while interconnecting all stakeholders across the entire FSC, from farm to fork, including pre-harvest stage. Additionally, OFLW Platform will assist systemic FLW reporting, with FLW modelling and forecasting capabilities, supporting FSC optimisation and innovations and fostering real-time and strategic decision making.

5.5 PESTLE Analysis

PESTLE analysis is performed to support the initial market assessment, helping to understand contemporary market environment around digitalisation of agri-food sector, and position ZeroW anticipated outcomes in it. In the following sections, Political Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors impacting the OFLW Platform target market are discussed.

5.5.1 Political factors

- The [EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste](#), created in 2016, aims to encourage all actors in the FSC to tackle FLW and meet the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12.3. This includes a subgroup dedicated to measuring food waste to improve the quantification of levels of food waste. The platform can act as a catalyst for the development of new big-data platforms aimed to quantify and address FLW across different stages of the supply chain.
- Currently there are no regulations or industry standards to digitalise the FSC, limiting adoption. Policies are required to streamline the business process [26].
- In the European Union, the integrated [Food Safety Policy](#) aims to ensure safety of foods from farm to fork by implementing control systems that ensure compliance with EU standards from food produced inside and outside the EU. Digitalisation can facilitate this process, boosting adoption of these technologies and consequently leading to reducing FLW.
- The [EU Code of conduct on agricultural data sharing by contractual agreement](#) has been created by Copa-Cogeca (<https://copa-cogeca.eu/>) and CEMA (<https://www.cema-agri.org/>). It aims to give support and guidance on data sharing and reusing in the agricultural sector. Based on the definitions for roles and processes, it establishes default principles related to 5 categories, which are:
 - Data ownership – referring to the underlying rights to derive data;
 - Data access, control and portability;
 - Data protection and transparency;
 - Privacy and security;
 - Liability and intellectual property rights.
- The EU's [2030 Digital Compass](#), launched in 2021, presents the vision and ways to ensure the digital transformation in the EU by 2030. It proposed the Digital Compass evolving around four cardinal points to achieve the digital transformation: government, infrastructure, skills and business.
- The [EU Data Strategy](#) aims to increase the availability of data by creating a Digital Single Market, ensuring competitiveness and data sovereignty in the EU. Common EU dataspace will ensure availability of more data and its sovereignty.
- The [Food Safety Modernization Act \(FSMA\)](#), in the United States, aims to increase the safety of the FSC to prevent foodborne diseases. This will favour the adoption of digital technologies, as these allow full traceability of food items.
- The new [artificial intelligence \(AI\) strategy](#) in the EU aims to accelerate research and industry capabilities, while ensuring people's safety and rights.
- [Champions 12.3](#) is a coalition dedicated to accelerating progress towards achieving SDG Target 12.3 by 2030. This coalition involves governments,

businesses, international organisations, farmer groups, research institutions, etc.

- The [10x20x30 initiative](#) under the Champions 12.3 coalition brings together 10 large food retailers/providers with more than 200 suppliers, committed to halving food waste by 2030, as well as measuring and publishing their FLW data [34].
- The [European Consumer Food Waste Forum](#) for collaboration between researchers and practitioners to reduce FLW at consumer stage by:
 - Establishing the drivers of consumer food waste and assess behavioural change.
 - Data collection and research to prevent food waste.
 - Defining research protocols and recommendations for effective interventions.
 - Assessing these interventions in terms of feasibility, reach and effectiveness.
 - Developing a multi-dimensional, multi-level, evidence-based set of tools to be implemented by Member States.

5.5.2 Economic factors

- Digital technologies have the potential to create new markets as the digital transition progresses. Industrial networks can expand activities using digital solutions via supply chains, infrastructure and complementary technologies [35].
- Consumers are demanding traceability of the foods they consume; they are willing to pay a premium for product that can be traced easily [24].
- The quantification of the benefits derived from data access and sharing is difficult; some studies have estimated that the indirect benefits for the public and the economy are worth between 0.1% and up to 4% of the gross domestic product (GDP). The differences depend on whether the data included only the public sector data or a combination of public and private data [36].
- The trend towards privatisation of the agricultural advisory services, especially in competitive and export-oriented countries, is resulting in higher fragmentation of the agricultural knowledge and advice networks where governance institutions have the role of market facilitators [19].
- Food recalls have a huge economic impact: it is estimated that in the US alone 300,000 hospitalisations and 5,000 deaths annually are related to foodborne diseases, with an associated cost of around €7 billion. These costs are associated with consumer communication, missed food sales (and increased associated food waste) and lawsuits [37].

- It is estimated that the green-digital transition will contribute to create up to 884,000 jobs by 2030, while some sectors may lose jobs; reskilling will be key to ensure workers can enter new or changing sectors [35].

5.5.3 Social factors

- The digital transition depends greatly on social acceptance in three areas: 1) socio-political acceptance by which the public and policymakers have to be convinced and ready to act; 2) market acceptance in terms of end users' willingness to invest in new technologies; and 3) community acceptance which requires to trust the technologies, the participation of all stakeholders, and the perception of a fair share of costs and benefits [35].
- Big data and analytics are seen as key for more efficient and optimised FSCs in their entirety [25]. The increased automation may make human operators redundant and lead to layoffs [26], but it might also attract younger employees to an aging sector (i.e. farming).
- Novel technologies aiming to digitalise the FSC have the potential to shorten it. Shorter supply chains are more beneficial for smaller farms, which dominate the European agricultural sector [22], further boosting the digitalisation process in the EU. However, investing in digitalisation might not necessarily be perceived as viable by the small farms.
- In general, the public perception of digitalisation is that it is immaterial and somewhat unconnected with the physical world. This is a consequence of certain terms, such as "cloud", which suggests something intangible or light. Data is also often seen as an unlimited resource, in contrast with other physical sources such as water, land, etc. These assumptions influence understanding and attitudes of the public, governments and policymakers, incentivising the creation of numerous data initiatives [38].
- Data is considered a resource for social improvement and growth, and a way to promote wellbeing and societal values. However, a number of ethical concerns may arise, such as privacy of users, creation of power imbalances between users and private companies and inequality in accessing data between high- and lower-income countries [38]. Additionally, a digital divide may appear, deepening the gap between those who have access to a good infrastructure and trustworthy data and those who don't.
- Digitalisation has social impacts in the agricultural advice and knowledge networks as it will increase the connectivity and transparency in their practices, and will have implications for governance (for example governance of data ownership, data curation and data analysis; additionally, it is likely that development of digital technologies will be governed by those with economical

and/or political power) [19]. Furthermore, digitalisation can enable improved connections between distinct sectors of FSC, i.e. hospitality and farming.

5.5.4 Technological factors

- The agri-food sector is characterised by its low level of research [25]; the adoption of new technologies can be slower compared to other industries.
- Big data applied in agriculture and the food industry is a relatively new and promising field: the global number of research articles published has been consistently increasing since 2014, and the trend is gaining momentum since 2017. The US leads the field, followed by China, India, Australia and UK [25].
- IoT technologies that are currently used in the agri-food industry still rely on centralised cloud infrastructures, presenting security issues and lack of transparency [23]. A technology that enables decentralisation, such as Blockchain, can help overcome these challenges.
- Blockchain is at proof-of-concept stage for applications in the food industry with the first research publications appearing in 2017. The number of articles peaked in 2019 [26].
- Standardisation and a unified framework is mandatory to enable wide adoption of Blockchain/digital technologies for their application in the FSC [26].

5.5.5 Legal factors

- The EC has laid down an obligation for the Member States to measure the levels of FLW based on a standard methodology and reporting format ([Directive 2008/98/EC](#); Delegated Decision (EU) 2019/1597; Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/2000). However, Member States are not supported by an easy-to-implement solution, and it is difficult for them to maintain such a complex process. Managing the reduction of FLW requires proper insight into the current and expected evolution of food streams, translated into actionable data-driven services.
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679, or [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#) offers protection of natural persons regarding processing of personal data and establishes the rules for free movement of personal data.

5.5.6 Environmental factors

The digitalisation of supply chains has a positive impact in terms of enhanced energy efficiency, lower transport and distribution distances and optimisation of logistics resources [39]. Additionally, it can contribute to establish new human-computer interactions that will further enhance sustainability values [19]. However, the high amounts of data generated through digitalisation are also a cause of environmental

impact as it has to be stored and managed, normally in data centres/servers. The impacts are:

- Direct impacts due to:
 - High energy consumption and emissions, increasing carbon footprint [40]. Additionally, data centres need diesel generators in case of power outages so the servers can keep working [38]. It was estimated that in 2016, data centres and enterprise networks were responsible of 160 million tons of CO₂eq [41], and have the fastest growing carbon footprint of the Information and Communications Technologies (ICT) sector [38].
 - Disposal of hardware. This is especially important in low- and middle-income countries with few environmental controls, as the recovery of certain materials such as gold or copper is made through incineration, causing high pollution levels [38].
- Indirect or rebound effects. These are associated to the users' behaviours, in which digitalisation is a cause of more environmental impact (i.e. the resources/money saved from use of digital technologies are then used to purchase/use other goods whose production is a cause of a higher footprint) [38].

The Implementation of algorithms to increase efficiency in server management, along with the use of renewable energy sources, are some of the measures that are aimed to mitigate this problem [40].

5.6 Barriers to entry

Barriers to entry into a market can relate to any form of limitations hindering the placement of the specific new/improved solution to the market. Here, some of the barriers that digital solutions such, as the OFLW Platform, may face are listed:

- The lack of industry-wide standards for data exchange may limit interoperability between different systems/platforms; this is hindering the development of a solution capable to cover the entire supply chain [42].
- The lack of trust among stakeholders to place novel technologies, such as Blockchain, at the core of their organisational processes [26].
- Concerns about data ownership and security [42].
- High complexity of information systems (i.e.: high number of features, difficult to use, etc.) may limit adoption by end users [25].
- Reluctancy to use new technologies.
- Lack of technical expertise of end users.
- Lack of a specific data model to be used to integrate available data.
- GDPR issues regarding data ownership. These need to be resolved before launching the OFLW platform.

- High costs of the technologies and skilled personnel compared with the costs of agricultural inputs may hamper the adoption of big data analytics tools upstream the FSC [25].

5.7 ZeroW OFLW Platform Market Summary

The OFLW Platform aims to provide an integrated solution for tackling FLW along the entire FSC by enabling knowledge sharing and collective intelligence. As demonstrated throughout Chapter 5, similar holistic solutions are not available in the market. The majority of the state-of-the-art focuses on narrower problems at discrete stages of the FSC, and mainly at retail level. In addition, such solutions are not best suited to address FLW at regional, national or European contexts. Therefore, OFLW Platform will address an identified need that that is currently not addressed in the FLW market.

However, obstacles for such a holistic solution to enter the market are still existent. For one, the lack of uniform definition of FLW is obscuring primarily data collection, but also data exchange among relevant stakeholders. The lack of industry-wide standards and agreements on data exchange, concerns related to data ownership and security, as well as GDPR and related policies, impose restrictions on data interoperability between different systems/platforms/FLW initiatives. This in effect is inflicting limitations to the development of a solution capable to cover the entire supply chain such as the proposed OFLW Platform. Figure 21 summarises market dynamics impacting the ZeroW proposed OFLW platform to enter the market.

<p>DRIVERS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The high complexity of the FSC is spurring the adoption of digital solutions and data analytics to optimise it. • The lack of an overarching view of the status of FLW, along with the increased awareness among stakeholders and the general public about the impacts of FLW, will favour the development of digital tools to centralise data on FLW and quantify associated impacts.
<p>RESTRAINTS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low drive for research in the agri-food sector, delaying digitalisation. • The European agri-food industry is mostly comprised by SMEs; these may be reluctant to make significant investments in digital technologies. • Low levels of private investment in the EU.
<p>OPPORTUNITIES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural robotics and digitalisation could enable early labelling and tracking in the food chain for improved traceability, allowing to optimise production and minimise waste. • Increasing adoption rates of big data in other sectors will favour applications in the agri-food industry. • Increased digitalisation levels among actors of the FSC will favour the adoption of standards and data sharing along its entirety.
<p>CHALLENGES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of standards, limiting interoperability between different systems. • Issues on data management and ownership. • Privacy concerns about the data generated.

Figure 21. Summary of market dynamics for cluster 1.

Nevertheless, advances in big data analytics, Blockchain technologies, computing power and IoT, will foster the digitalisation efforts and sustainability in food systems, opening the market opportunities for digital solutions like OFLW Platform and ZeroW Smart Applications. The governing strategies and ambitious targets set by regional, national, EU and global regulatory bodies encourage the adoption of smart agri-food solutions and digital transformation of the agri-food sector.

6 ZeroW Pre- and Post-harvest Innovations

Pre- and post-harvest innovations are referring to technologies that are applied mainly at farm stage in the FSC, either before/during harvesting or once the produce has been harvested. According to the FAO, food loss is defined as “the decrease in the quantity or quality of food resulting from decisions and actions by food suppliers in the chain, excluding retail, food service providers and consumers.” [43] According to FAO definition, at farm stage food is lost and not wasted, and in this case the loss is considered unintentional, the result of events that are difficult to predict. Defining the loss of food at farm stage in this way affects the policies and interventions taken to prevent FLW at pre- and post-harvest level. As a consequence, most innovations existing at this stage are intended to increase efficiency/productivity of the farm using automation and predictive tools. Food loss prevention is often an indirect result of the increased process optimisation.

6.1 ZeroW's proposed innovations

6.1.1 SILL 3 – Wasteless greenhouse solutions for (pre)harvesting aligned with short-term downstream demand

The ZeroW innovations addressing FLW at the pre- and post-harvest stages are related to SILL 3. In this SILL, a technology using deep vision methods and machine learning algorithms will be developed with the aim to estimate ripeness and quality of tomatoes growing in greenhouses. Thus, the solution will be comprised by hardware and software systems that, when combined, will create a unified automated monitoring system. The parts that compose the solution are:

- Hardware – Cameras: Depending on the final architecture, these will acquire spectral data in the visual range with the possibility to extend it to the near-infrared region.
- Software – Artificial Neural Network (ANN) algorithms: These are required to evaluate the status of the tomatoes, estimate the precise yield and plan the harvesting schedule.

Figure 22. SILL3: Computer-vision-based systems used to monitor greenhouse tomato.

This technology aims to address the large amounts of FLW generated in greenhouses, a consequence of the inability to estimate precisely the quantity of vegetables that will be available to match the market demand. The proposed system will provide information on greenhouse status and optimise the harvesting schedule, allowing a precise planning of the logistics required for the expected quantity of produce. Additionally, it will identify sub-standard crops (those fruits that do not comply with aesthetic standards), so they can be re-purposed for other uses early in the supply chain (i.e.: production of sauces, juice, etc., as proposed in SILL 4, Section 7.1.2).

6.2 Market Overview

6.2.1 Food loss and waste in the farm

The leading causes of FLW on farm level are summarised in the table below. These can also occur along the entire food value chain.

Table 9. Types of damage leading to food loss in the farm and latter stages of the FSC [27].

Type	Source
Pests/Disease damage	Insect larvae (fruit fly), especially in long-term stored crops (grains, cereals...)
Mechanical injury	Falls, crushing, mishandling during harvest, or due to incorrect or no packaging
Senescence	Respiration, high levels of ethylene, sprouting, transpiration, inadequate packaging.
Microbial spoilage	Fungi, yeast and bacteria growth, normally pre-harvest, due to high temperatures and/or relative humidity.
Temperature damage	Temperature extremes: freezing/chilling injuries.

In addition to those, pre-harvest factors affecting post-harvest quality (and thus, suitability for the market) are genetic conditions, nutrition status of the soil and climatic factors [44]. Food loss at farm level is mostly determined by the quality of crops at harvest; at this point they can be easily damaged, especially when using mechanised harvesting methods. Injuries cause decay due to water loss and increased respiratory and ethylene production rates, while creating an area suitable for microorganism growth. To prevent this, susceptible crops need to be manually harvested by trained workers that can recognise ripen fruits, being careful not to damage them [45].

Post-harvest conditions affecting quality are the maturity at the time of harvest, methods and time of harvest, and the use of post-harvest treatments (precooling, sorting and grading, and packaging) [44].

Levels of FLW at farms are often neglected, mainly because of the definitions of food loss and food waste: food leaving the supply chain in the farm is often considered as food loss and not waste. On the one hand, food loss is considered unintentional, consequence of a number of factors such as market conditions, poor infrastructure and agricultural practices, discard due to cosmetic imperfections, disease or weather events. On the other hand, food waste is considered to be caused by negligence or conscious choice, and applies mostly to later stages of the supply chain (mainly at retail, food service and consumer levels). Additionally, it is assumed that in developed countries FLW in the farm is not an issue when compared with other stages in the food supply chain, whereas the problem is more acute in less developed countries due to lack of access to infrastructure/technology for storage. Despite this assumption, WWF estimated that per-capita FLW at farm stage is higher in the higher-income countries (Europe, North America and some regions in Asia), comprising together around 58%, or 368 million tons, of the global harvest waste (Figure 23) [46]. In these regions, post-harvest losses are often associated with mismanagement, inadequate harvesting timing or inadequacy of handling and distribution channels [45]. Additionally, a recent report by Feedback EU (2022) [14]

showed significant losses of food at primary production stages, as shown in Table 3, Section 2.3.

Globally, food lost at farm stage is estimated to be around 1.2 billion tons (or 15.3% of all food wasted) every year, with an economic value of \$370 million. Of that amount, 8.3% of waste is produced around harvest and 7% during farm-stage post-harvest processes. These values may be underestimated due to the way FLW is measured: a part of the discarded food originally intended for human consumption is directed to other uses (i.e.: derived to animal feed or valorised into ingredients for other industries); as these other uses are considered to have better outcomes than being sent to a landfill or incinerated, they are not considered as FLW. In any case, derived uses cannot be quantified due to lack of methodology, evaluation guidelines, etc. This fact may disincentivise farmers to address the issues leading to overproduction/waste [46].

Figure 23. Per-capita FLW in high- and low-income countries, per commodity [46].

6.2.2 Existing solutions

The following sections are reviewing current solutions that could potentially reduce food losses at farm stage. It is important to note that these solutions are mostly intended to enhance resource optimisation and efficiency at farm/greenhouse stage, with the aim to maintain or increase crop yields and quality, while reducing the environmental impacts of agriculture [47]. While they do not address FLW directly, they may be doing so indirectly by improving crop quality; thus reducing the quantities of produce being discarded due to aesthetic reasons or poor nutritive content.

6.2.2.1 Pre-harvest innovations

6.2.2.1.1 Chemical treatments

Chemical treatment of fruit and vegetables are intended to improve the shelf-life of produce; thus directly tackling FLW at this and downstream stages of the FSC. These can be:

- Spray with gibberellic acid at colour-break stage. This delays colouration and maintains firmness; as such, it is used to extend the harvesting period [44].
- Foliar treatment with a solution containing calcium can improve firmness and extend shelf-life of fruits [44].
- Plant nutrition. The availability of minerals in the soil will greatly affect the quality and shelf-life of produce. The main nutrients are nitrogen (N), phosphorous (P) and potassium (K). Plant performance depends greatly on the balance of these nutrients, which may be lacking or in excess in different soils and require modifications [44]. Precision Agriculture (PA) technologies (explained in further detail in the following section) can be used to detect nutrient deficit in individual plants to precisely target the application of fertilisers, ensuring crop quality.

6.2.2.1.2 Smart Farming Technologies (SFTs)

SFTs are divided into three main categories: (i) precision agriculture systems, (ii) farm management information systems (FMIS) and (iii) reacting technologies enabling agricultural automation/robotics [48].

Precision Agriculture (PA) – This is an approach to farm management based on observing, measuring and responding to variability in crops. For this, PA utilises remote sensing, data gathering, satellite positioning data and information technology with the aim to optimise input usage for maximum quality and yield. Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) are key in the development of Precision Agriculture Technologies (PATs) [49].

PATs contribute to optimisation of in-field operations, reducing the need for agricultural inputs while improving productivity at lower costs than traditional practices [47], and is also supporting climate change resilience [47].

Current development status and the use of PA in the EU is not known; in the 90s, adoption rates were high especially in the US and Canada as market conditions were favourable. During the 2000s, the expansion has halted as the results obtained were not proving expected productivity, efficiency, etc. However, uptake is re-gaining momentum again due to better economic results and recent improvements in technology which have helped overcome remaining bottlenecks [47]. PATs are more

advanced in larger arable farms, where the main driver is profitability maximisation [49].

PATs are classified into three categories:

- Guidance systems – combinations of hardware and software that allow automatic guidance of agricultural machinery. Examples are automatic steering, field mapping, precise movement between rows of plants, precision sowing/planting/spraying or automatic weeding;
- Recording technologies – these are sensors that collect data from the field to assess the status of crops;
- Reacting technologies – combinations of hardware and software that can determine and change placement of agricultural inputs (water, fertilisers, pesticides, etc.) where needed. Examples include variable rate and nutrient sensing technologies [49].

Figure 24 provides a schematic overview of commercially available solutions enabling PA [47].

Figure 24. Overview of PATs. Open access [30].

The use of these solutions requires a high skill level to translate the data into the status of crops/soil, through Geographic Information Systems (GIS). Models need to be developed to understand interrelations between plant, soil and climate, so

agricultural inputs can be adjusted accordingly. These require Farm Management Systems, provided to farmers through consulting or through dedicated software [49].

Machine vision is a recent development in PA. It simulates human vision to analyse the crops and gives an output in a non-invasive way. The technology is already being implemented for fruit (vineyards) and vegetable monitoring.

Figure 25. Computer vision enabling automated robot operations. Open access [33].

The technology faces several challenges for implementation as it requires large datasets to train the system, and some difficulties can be expected if the fruit colour is the same as the leaves, which can also be shadowing the targets [50]. Current applications are:

- Plant phenotyping. This is used for plant identification, growth rate, grading, estimate yields, etc. [50] This is achieved by measuring different plant organs (leaves, flowers, fruits, and in some cases it is even possible to provide estimations for the roots).
- Pest and disease monitoring. In this context, research has been conducted on tomato, cucumbers, strawberry and bell pepper to detect diseases caused by fungi (mildew, blight, mould, etc.) and pests such as white fly and thrips. Machine vision can also be used for tracking field operations such as to monitor fertilising or pesticide use; with the aim to improve risk management and enable traceability [49].
- Stress detection. Currently there are no commercialised sensors to assess the balance of nutritional components in plants; this could be covered using computer vision [50].
- Robot assistance to navigate, recognise and target plants, allowing automation of various tasks.
- Fruit grading according to product quality. This is achieved by assessing characteristics such as colour, size, shape, defects, as well as the indirect estimation of internal qualities such as sugar content, acidity, etc [49]. This application has promoted further developments in the food processing

industry. Food grading has been applied for estimating quality of tomato (by ripeness, quality, crack detection) and carrot (based on the green shoulder, the system is able to detect bending, cracks and breaks). The accuracy of these applications is currently over 90% [50].

Application of PA in greenhouses – The application of PA solutions in greenhouses poses some unique challenges compared to open field applications (due to high humidity, frequent spraying, presence of metallic structures that may affect the signals emitted by the sensors, etc.). Hence, the use of PA in greenhouses requires some adjustments compared to in-field PA, specifically in the areas of connectivity, power sources, etc [51]. The PA solutions most used for greenhouses consist of the following elements:

- **Sensors:** these need to be enclosed in sensor boxes to prevent damage due to the environmental conditions. This represents a challenge as readings may be inaccurate due to different environmental conditions inside and outside the box (due to low or no air circulation [51]). Variable lighting conditions in particular can affect computer vision technologies as the lighting used in the greenhouse can make the segmentation algorithms commonly used to be inaccurate. Other problems in the application of computer vision technologies in greenhouses come from the complex environment: many supporting systems such as irrigation pipes, monitoring equipment, etc., which are adding complexity to the background and hindering recognition [50].
- **Battery:** sensors are powered by batteries. Battery lifespan may be an issue as, on average, they only last for a few months and ideally, they should last for more than a year. It is key to keep network coverage in the case of failure of a node. However, deployment of alternative sources of energy such as solar-powered solutions is complicated as they are placed under cover of the greenhouse.
- **Data transmission:**
 - Zigbee specification. Used by most PA solutions for greenhouses because it requires low power to operate and has a range of 10-100 m, enough for smaller greenhouses. Due to the short range, it may be unsuitable for larger greenhouses.
 - Long-Range modulation (LoRa) WAN protocol offers longer range capabilities and has low power requirements. Already in use in viticulture [51].
- **Data analytics tools** such as machine learning (ML), neural networks, etc. These are used to analyse the data generated by the sensors and report/predict on crop yield/quality, etc., helping in the decision-making process.

Farm management information systems (FMIS) – These are planned systems for collection, storage, management and dissemination of the data needed for the farm to carry out its activities. FMIS were developed to manage the increasing amounts

of data generated by PATs to provide an integral solution to farm management [42].

To be successful, FMIS require:

- Usability – software needs to be easy to use.
- Flexibility – this feature allows customisation to cover specific needs.
- High profitability and benefits compared to costs, effort and labour required.
- High transparency, integration and efficiency.

6.2.2.2 *Post-harvest innovations*

6.2.2.2.1 Quality assessment of food products

The quality assessment of agricultural products is key to decide post-harvest treatment, storage time and transport [52]. It will also determine market acceptance of a product.

Current trends in quality assessment are favouring techniques that allow to analyse the food products in a non-destructive way, encouraging the development of devices that can be handheld or portable. Current solutions are:

- Optical/Imaging techniques:
 - Visible (Vis) or Near-infrared (NIR) hyperspectral imaging, based on the light reflected by materials. These techniques are used to determine quality of meats (chemical composition, tenderness, microbial spoilage and contamination of different meat products), fruits and vegetables. The advantage of the hyperspectral imaging is in use of commercially available spectrometers, that after calibration and experimental procedures can be adopted to specific food products to be analysed [53].
 - Machine/Computer vision tools based on software using machine learning (ML)/artificial intelligence (AI).
 - X-ray computed tomography, used to determine the internal structure of fruits [53].
 - Laser biospeckle method, based on changes in reflected waves from the materials. This technique has been researched to determine the chemical content in apples at different stages of maturity. When combined with ANN, it can classify apples based on stiffness/juiciness [53].
 - Digital image processing, relying on use of a camera to capture RGB images and software to process them. This technique is used to measure vigour and vegetative estimation in vines [53].
- Acoustic and impact-force test methods.
 - Ultrasonic wave velocity. Method used to measure fat content in meat [53].
 - High-power ultrasound. This method is used to assess textural and physicochemical properties of meat products; commonly, it is used in combination with other techniques [53].

- Impact force measurement, to determine the firmness of fruits using a load cell [53].
- Acoustic impulse response, to detect ripeness in fruits (apples, watermelons) [53].
- Mechanical methods
 - Conductivity-based methods. Used to measure the freshness of fish (cod) [53].
 - Electronic nose sensors. Used to determine maturity of fruits and optimal harvest date [53].
 - Dielectric power spectroscopy. Used to determine sugar concentration in sugarcane at different maturity stages [53].
 - Vibrational techniques. Used to determine the freshness of bread (based on water content), firmness and springiness [53].

6.2.2.2.2 Post-harvest treatments

Post-harvest treatments vary depending on the type of produce:

- Precooling. This is a critical step for preservation of fresh produce (fruits and vegetables) as it slows down the respiration rate and senescence in a cost-effective manner. When cooling, relative humidity surrounding produce needs to be monitored to prevent condensation and moisture, which is one of the main causes of decay [45]. Available precooling solutions are:
 - Room cooling. One of the most cost-efficient methods. The crops are stored in a cold room with a fan to keep air movement. Mainly used for vegetables [45].
 - Vacuum cooling. Cooling is caused by the evacuated air, which leads to the evaporation of water in the surface of treated crops, thus reducing its weight. This method can be used for crops that do not have a thick and waxy cuticle (lettuce, leeks, etc) [45].
 - Air precooling and forced-air cooling. Both methods use cold air to reduce the temperature of the produce. In the case of forced-air cooling, the air is directed at the crop at high velocity. Air precooling is used mainly for fruits, while forced-air is used for vegetables, beans and some fruits (raspberries, strawberries, etc.) [45].
 - Hydrocooling. Use of cold water to submerge the crops. If chlorinated water is used, it has the additional advantage of inhibiting the growth of microorganisms associated to decay. Mainly for treating vegetables [45].
 - Icing – It can be applied directly in contact with the crop or with no direct contact, placing it in boxes. Mainly used for vegetables [45].
 - Evaporative cooling. Lower temperatures are achieved by passing air over a surface saturated with water. Mostly used in emerging economies as it is

low-cost and relatively efficient: crops can be stored for up to 5 days without significant losses [45].

Precooling and cold storage can produce chilling injuries, especially in cold-sensitive crops. In this case, a short heat treatment prior to cold storage can increase tolerance to refrigeration [45].

- Post-harvest handling and drying
 - Grains and cereals. Post-harvest treatments vary depending on time of harvest and foreseen duration of storage; for long-term storage, 126 litres of water/Mt of grain need to be removed. This is achieved by aeration, ventilation with heated air (5-10 °C above room temperature), or sun drying (when weather conditions allow it) [45].
 - Desiccation. Preservation using freeze-drying and hot-air drying of fruits [54].
 - Low-capacity, portable column dryer using a biomass burner, used to treat maize [54].
 - Ozonation. Used to remove pesticides and other residues, as well as microorganisms [45].
 - Treatment with chemicals such as 1-methylcyclopropene (1-MCP), with the aim to inhibit ethylene production and its associated senescence process [45], [54].
- Sorting and grading. This step aims to eliminate diseased and defective produce and is a crucial step in ensuring quality. It can be performed infield or once the product is harvested. Grading can be based on size, shape, colour or defects, and is done either manually or automatically. Sorting consists in the removal of diseased or damaged products and is normally made manually [44].
- Stored product protection (packaging), including:
 - Hermetic bags for storage of maize [54].
 - Dynamic controlled atmosphere technologies. This includes reduction of O₂ and increase of CO₂ in the air surrounding the crops to slow metabolism, respiration and ethylene production. Injuries may occur if the concentration of CO₂ is very high [45], [54].
- Automated monitoring. Use of sensors to monitor temperature or control the quality of fruits during storage using infrared hyperspectral imaging coupled with statistical evaluation models [54].
- Post-harvest loss reduction, including:
 - Use of plastic crates to physically protect the produce [54].
 - Fruit fly traps to attract and kill fruit flies [54].
 - Processing of seasonal fruits to make shelf-stable products that can be consumed year round, such as jams, jellies, smoothies, etc [54].

- Chemical treatments to disinfect the produce such as methyl bromide (MeBr) and phosphine. Current regulations aim to reduce/eliminate their use.
- Radio frequency heating – Use of radiofrequency-induced heating to reduce the risk of post-harvest losses due to pests. Application of frequencies between 10-300MHz [55].

6.2.3 Market size

The specific markets in the stage of pre- and post-harvest innovations that align with the solutions proposed under SILL 3 are the Smart Greenhouse Market and the Smart Harvest Market. The overview of these markets is provided below.

Smart Greenhouse Market – This market refers to systems that contribute to controlling and maintaining optimal microclimate conditions for plants without human intervention. This market is relatively new and expanding quickly; it was worth \$1.38 billion in 2020 and will grow at a CAGR of 9.2% in the period between 2020 and 2025, reaching \$2.14 billion by 2025 (Figure 26) [56].

Figure 26. Smart Greenhouse Market overview [56]

The Smart Greenhouse Market is further segmented by type, covering material type, offering, component, end user and region. The market segments of interest for ZeroW SILL 3 solutions are:

- **By offering.** These can be hardware, software and services. The focus is on the hardware (which refers to sensors controlling different conditions in the greenhouse) and software (which is used to manage data obtained from the sensors to improve health monitoring, stock management, etc.). Table 10 shows the sizes of each segment during the forecast period (2020 to 2025). With a value of \$1.12 billion in 2020, the hardware segment dominates the market. However the software segment will grow at a faster pace (CAGR of 8.5% vs. 12.1% for the hardware and software segments, respectively) in the forecast period [56].

Table 10. Value of the Smart Greenhouse Market, by offering (\$ million) [56]

	2020	2021	2023	2025	CAGR
Hardware	1,129	1,238	1,465	1,696	8.5%
Software	252	286	362	447	12.1%
Total	1,381	1,524	1,827	2,143	9.2%

- **By component.** This market segment is further divided into heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) systems, LED grow lights and control systems & sensors. The most relevant segment is the control systems & sensors, as SILL 3 will develop a number of cameras to monitor the growing tomatoes, providing information to the farmers to automate the decision-making process. This segment holds the smallest share, valued at \$290 million in 2020, approximately 21% of the market. It will reach \$393 million in 2025 registering a CAGR of 6.3% [56].
- **By end user.** This market is segmented in commercial growers, research & educational institutes, retail gardens and others (including biotech and residential end users). The market segment that is relevant in the context of SILL 3 is the Commercial Growers segment, which account for a share of approximately 34% (\$478 million) of the total market. This segment will witness the fastest growth with a CAGR of 12.4%, reaching a value of \$859 million in 2025 [56].

Figure 27. Market value of the Smart Greenhouse segment, by region [56]

Geographically, Europe is envisaged to reach the biggest market size of \$665 million by 2026 (), enabling the solutions like the one proposed in SILL 3 to reach the relevant customers.

Smart Harvest Market - This market covers computer-controlled machines equipped with sensors, navigation systems and cameras with the objective to harvest crops with no/minimal human intervention [57]. While SILL 3 is not developing a system to automate the harvesting process (it is planned to add a robotic arm to the platform system; however, this is out of the scope for the ZeroW project), this market is of interest for some of the aspects of the innovation in

development. The market is segmented by component, site of operation, crop type and region [57]. Those that are relevant for SILL 3 solution are:

- **By component.** This market is further divided into hardware and software components; both are of relevance.
 - The hardware segment is divided into Automation & control systems; Sensors; Imaging systems and Harvesting robots. The imaging systems segment is of particular relevance for SILL 3. Valued at \$7,723.9 million, the hardware segment dominated the market in 2018 and will reach \$12,352 million by 2023 with a CAGR of 11.57%. The imaging systems subsegment is the least mature and consequently held the smallest market share in 2018 with a value of \$258.8 million (≈3% share of the smart harvest market). However, it will be the sector with the fastest growth with a remarkable CAGR of 20.23% until 2023, reaching \$650.2 million [57].
 - The software segment will grow at a CAGR of 13.28%, from a value of \$1221.6 million in 2018 to \$2,291.8 million in 2023 [57].
- **By site of operation.** This is further divided into three categories – In-Field, Smart Greenhouse and Indoor Farming. The Smart Greenhouse segment held the smallest share in 2018 with a value of \$261.8 million (≈2.9%). The market will reach \$405 million in 2023 at a 9.12% CAGR. Smart greenhouses will be key for the smart harvest technologies as these allow manufacturers to test and operate sensors and robots to automatically harvest crops [57].
- **By crop type.** These can be relevant to fruits or vegetables. The vegetables segment was worth \$415.1 million in 2018 and will grow to reach \$978.4 million in 2023 registering a CAGR of 18.7% in the forecast period [57].

As the Smart Harvest Market is driven by the increase of adoption of new technologies in farming for the maximum profitability and production, this market is expected to reach \$15.62 million by 2021, with Europe dominating the market [57].

Figure 28. Key countries and associated growth in Smart Harvest Market [57]

6.3 Market Dynamics

Factors that influence the ZeroW Pre- and Post-harvest Innovations relevant markets, including opportunities driving market growth, as well as any potential restraints and challenges are discussed below.

6.3.1 Market drivers

- ✓ PA is linked with enhanced sustainability capabilities in agricultural practices. As sustainable practices gain momentum, all stakeholders will be more aware of the contribution of these technologies towards sustainability, accelerating the demand and public acceptance for these innovations [49].
- ✓ Increasing requirements of traceability in the European union will accelerate uptake of PA, because almost all PATs include digital geo references that enable easy/fast tracing [49].
- ✓ New regulatory requirements (i.e.: restrictions in the use of plant protection products (PPPs), fertilisers, etc) are pushing the demand for PATs as these can limit/minimise the use to the areas that really need it [58].
- ✓ The EU eco-schemes (part of the new [Common Agricultural Policy](#) or CAP: 2023-27) will benefit those farmers that implement sustainable practices, favouring the uptake of smart solutions as key enablers of sustainability.
- ✓ Tightening gross margin and profitability in agriculture [46] is driving the demand for solutions that can reduce costs without affecting or even increasing production.
- ✓ The increased penetration of GNSS technologies in Central and Eastern Europe will accelerate the adoption of PA in these regions [49].
- ✓ Labour shortages due to the depopulation of rural regions are boosting the demand for automation solutions in farms/greenhouses [57, 59].

- ✓ Increased demand for portable and easy to use devices to non-destructively assess the quality of food products so they can be used in-field by farmers, quality inspectors, etc [53].
- ✓ Increasing tech skills among primary producers due to the growing adoption of digital technologies is further driving the demand for these solutions [60].

6.3.2 Market restraints

- ✗ European agriculture is dominated by small farms, which may not be able to afford high investments in technology; these rely on contractors to cover their needs, but these are not included in the CAP. Adoption of SFTs by small- and medium-sized farms is a key enabling step. The inclusion of contractors in the CAP will allow SMEs to easier access expensive technologies [49].
- ✗ Low awareness of end users about the economic and environmental benefits of PA [47].
- ✗ High costs of implementation of PATs, which include the technology (both hardware and software), expenses in data processing (license fees), information and learning costs, as well as indirect costs such as lost opportunity costs, caused by inefficient use. Profitability may thus be limited to larger farms [49].
- ✗ Lack of standards limit exchange of data between systems; thus reducing interoperability [49].
- ✗ Europe lacks independent advisory/consultancy services for farmers. This may hinder adoption of PATs [49].
- ✗ Lack of confidence in PATs among end users may limit perception of benefits, as some previous technologies failed to meet the expected results [42], [49].

6.3.3 Opportunities

- ❖ The EC's Climate Action proposes mitigation measures of farming-related GHG emissions, accelerating market uptake of SFTs [47].
- ❖ Advancements in efficiency and accuracy of GNSS technologies are allowing lower costs and accelerating the development of PA solutions [49].
- ❖ Technology transfer from other sectors, such as GNSS, robotics or artificial intelligence, is likely to encourage new investments in their application on PA [49].
- ❖ The increasing integration of big data and AI in farming will have a significant impact on the smart harvesting technologies sector [57].
- ❖ Extensive investments in the Agri-tech area, due to the opportunities it has to offer. Globally, farm technological start-ups have seen an increase in investments of 370% since 2013 to 2019, when they reached \$4.7 billion in 695 deals [60].

- ❖ Favourable government initiatives will propel the adoption of PA and smart harvest systems. This is due to the interest of governments to increase food production with limited resources [57].

6.3.4 Challenges

- ∇ Lack of a reliable internet connectivity in rural areas can hinder uptake of SFTs.
- ∇ Lack of a holistic solution that helps farmers tackle FLW from multiple angles.
- ∇ Lack of standardised data exchange protocols may limit the adoption of FMIS by farmers, as systems from different vendors can be incompatible between each other [42].
- ∇ SFTs require more highly skilled personnel than conventional farming methods, which may deter use. Farmers may have limited technical knowledge to operate new technologies [57].
- ∇ SFTs / PATs require to be profitable to be adopted by end users [49]. A solution that is not profitable is unlikely to be successful; this may prove difficult to achieve if a solution is directly addressing FLW at farm level. This problem may be exacerbated by the current definitions of food loss and food waste; at farm stage food is lost, which has better connotations than food wasted [46]. Farmers may be less compelled to use these innovations as they may not perceive the need to do so.
- ∇ Lack of quantifiable data on environmental impact reduction of PATs; instead, adoption is frequently linked to end users' personal values/perceptions [49].
- ∇ Commercial deployment of smart harvest technologies is slow and gradual. New products need to be tested before being commercially deployed, which results in capital lockup and delays in returns [57].
- ∇ Technological challenges of applying computer vision technologies in greenhouses [50], related to:
 - Lighting conditions.
 - Complex backgrounds.
 - Shadowing of the targets by leaves and other parts of the plant.
 - Need of larger datasets to improve the accuracy of machine learning algorithms.
 - High variability among individual plants, even within the same species. Standards are required to obtain meaningful datasets for each plant species to train the algorithms and provide accurate results.

6.4 Competitor Analysis

The summary of competitor offerings relevant for the ZeroW Pre- and Post-harvest innovations, as well as key differences and advantages of ZeroW anticipated solutions are discussed below.

6.4.1 Competitor offerings

Commercial pre- and post-harvest innovations currently available are listed below:

- **RootAI, US** (<https://root-ai.com>). Development of machine vision technologies to detect fruits (tomatoes) that are ripe and automatically harvest them. This system is used at AppHarvest (<https://www.appharvest.com/>), which is one of the largest indoor farms globally.
- **MetoMotion, Israel** (<https://www.metomotion.com/>). Developed the MetoMotion Greenhouse Robotic Worker (GRoW), an autonomous system to identify, pick and pack onsite ripe fruit. GRoW uses 3D stereo vision systems for identification and artificial intelligence to analyse the images.
- **Panasonic, Japan** (<https://www.panasonic.com/>). Developed an [AI-powered tomato harvester](#). The robot moves along a rail between the rows and uses image recognition to assess ripeness and harvest it if required.
- **Xihelm, UK** (<https://xihelm.com/>). Company developing automated robots for fruit and vegetable (tomato) harvesting, for use in greenhouses. The Eagle robot, using computer vision with the omatai 3D AI data engine, is able to register approximately 300 variables in each harvesting session. The business relays on Robots-as-a-Service (RaaS) business model based on serviced volume or area, reducing costs for their customers, as they are not required to acquire the machinery.
- **MVTEC, Germany** (<https://www.mvtec.com/>). Company that develops software for machine vision, including software for applications in agriculture, enabling automation both in field and in greenhouses. It utilises technologies such as deep learning, 3D vision, optical character recognition (OCR) and optical character verification (OCV).
- **Digital Divide Data, US** (<https://www.digitaldividedata-ai.com/>). Company that applies machine learning technologies in different industries. They develop tools for data collection, cleaning and curation, video and image annotation, etc.
- **Blue River Technology, US** (<https://bluerivertechnology.com/>). Company applying machine vision to precision agriculture. They are commercialising the “See & Spray” technology, used to automatically identify weeds and apply herbicide in a targeted way, preventing herbicide resistance.
- **iUNU, US** (<https://iunu.com/>). Precision agriculture company. They have developed LUNA, a hardware-agnostic computer vision analytics tool for use in greenhouses. The system can be used to automate processes in greenhouses, predict yields, mitigate pest/disease risks and minimise losses by detecting anomalies such as leaf damage, curling, chlorosis, necrosis, etc.
- **TortugaAgTech, US** (<https://www.tortugaagtech.com/>). Company developing robotics and automatic solutions for greenhouses.

- **N.thing**, South Korea (<https://nthing.net/>). Developed Planty Cube, a vertical farming, modular solution that enables automation and scale-up by adding more modules.
- **Dogtooth Technologies**, UK (<https://dogtooth.tech/>). Start-up developing scalable and autonomous systems for harvesting soft fruit, such as strawberry. The system uses robotics, deep learning, computer vision and IoT. The company claims their system is capable to autonomously navigate along crop rows, locate, pickup and grade the fruits and place them directly into punnets.
- **Luxelare**, Mexico (<https://luxelare.com/>). Development of FMIS with the aim to manage both the farm and its operation costs.
- **Landmark Systems**, UK (<https://www.landmarksystems.co.uk/>). Company dedicated to develop software for rural business management. Their crop recording software, named Geofolia, is intended to maximise yields and performance. Used by over 23,000 farms in Europe.
- **Fieldmarging**, UK (<https://fieldmargin.com/>) is a farm management software for better decision-making processes. Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) business model, offering different subscription options.

There is also a number of EU research projects covering solutions that may be contributing towards a reduction of FLW at pre- and post-harvest stages, such as:

- The **FUTUREFARM Project** had the objective to evaluate then existing farm management tools and develop new FMIS specifications. As expected, the requirements were highly complex due to the diversity of farm operations. The resulting FMIS was easily adaptable in order to accommodate future advancements in sensor and machinery technologies. The project was funded under the FP7 programme and ended in 2011.
- The **SmartAgrifood Project** was an accelerator programme funding SMEs, aimed to transform their ideas into new applications for the agricultural sector. The areas of interest were arable farming, horticulture and livestock farming. These applications were required to use FIWARE technologies, which offers an open-cloud infrastructure for cost efficiency. The project was funded under the FP7 programme.
- The EU **ECHORD++** robotics research project had the objective to meet the demand of robotic solutions for the manufacturing industry. It was mainly intended for SMEs. In the agri-food industry, it piloted the SAGA and MARS projects:
 - The **SAGA Project** (Swarm Robotics for Agricultural Applications) tested the feasibility of using swarms of unmanned aerial vehicles (UABs) applied to precision farming.

- The [MARS Project](#) (Mobile Agricultural Robot Swarms) aimed to transfer robotic technology to farming. The consortium decided to offer the entire system, including the cloud-based platform and the swarm of small robots, as a commercial product under the name “XAVER”.
- The [SmartAgriHubs Project](#) aims to introduce digital innovations in agriculture. It consists of over 155 Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and 9 regional clusters across all Member States. The network of DIHs aims to integrate technology and businesses in a one-stop-shop approach for key actors in Europe.
- The [Quantifarm Project](#) (Byte by byte: assessing the impact of digital agriculture solutions) focuses on small-scale commercial farms, aiming at the development of digital tools by farmers and advisors for farmers and advisors. Some of the tools focus on increasing yield of greenhouse tomato production.
- Mobile robotic platforms for active inspection and harvesting in agricultural areas ([BACCHUS](#)). This project aims to combine precision agriculture with robotic technologies to increase the efficiency of agricultural production. It will result in the BACCHUS intelligent mobile robotic system for automated harvesting of grapes and for detection and elimination of infected fruits.

6.4.2 ZeroW Solution and key differentiating points

The most direct competitors for the ZeroW proposed solution are those offering machine vision technologies to assess the ripeness status and automatically harvest tomato fruits in greenhouses. The closest and most advanced solutions are “RootAI”, “Metomotion” and the “Panasonic” tomato harvester. Apart from the information on their web sites and a few videos showing the working principles of the technologies used, the true status of these projects is not clear. Key issues with the harvesters are the limited capacity, slow speed, electric capacity and charging issues.

The solution proposed by ZeroW does not centre on the automatic harvesting part as the other market available solutions, but on improving conditions at the organisational level: its value proposition is related to the optimisation of resources and increased efficiency in the greenhouse, not the reduction of human labour. This will be supported by harvesting scheduling tool (i.e. smart application, as per Table 8) to optimise the harvest scheduling and yield planning, harmonising it with short-term predicted downstream demand, thus avoiding the supply-demand mismatches and possible generation of FLW.

6.5 PESTLE Analysis

PESTLE analysis is performed to support the initial market assessment, helping to understand contemporary market environment around pre- and post-harvest innovation market, and position the ZeroW anticipated outcomes in it. In the

following sections, Political Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors impacting the SILL 3 outcomes target markets are discussed.

6.5.1 Political factors

- EU policies are required to create a level playing field for European agriculture to remain competitive, reducing dependence on imported food.
- The new [Common Agricultural Policy \(CAP\)](#) for the period 2023-2027 is reducing subsidies that support production and is moving towards providing economic help mainly to the environmentally-related public goods and services. To receive full funding, the new CAP will require a series of actions to improve sustainability while continuing to support innovation in the agricultural sector with the introduction of the Eco-Schemes. These, also called post-2020 CAP green architecture requirements, will encourage farmers to be more sustainable by adapting their practices to challenges such as ones posed by climate change.
- The [Farm-to-Fork](#) and [Biodiversity](#) strategies, part of the [EU Green Deal](#), will favour the adoption of new technologies to achieve the following goals by 2030:
 - 50% reduction in use of pesticides;
 - reduction in the use of fertilisers by 20% and nutrient losses by 50%;
 - at least 25% of agricultural land dedicated to organic farming.
- The [UN's Sustainable Development Goal \(SDG\) 12.3](#) aims to achieve a reduction in FLW by 50% by 2030; however, it is placing more importance in tackling the levels of food waste generated at retail and consumer stages of the FSC, while only calling to reduce food losses at farm stage. This may be hindering progress towards improvements at this level [46].
- The [AgriTech 2030](#) plan, created by the European Agricultural Machinery Industry Association (CEMA), aims to guide the progress of the agricultural machinery industry towards 2030. It outlines the necessity of innovations to optimise management and keep the high levels of competitiveness of the European agricultural sector [61]. One of its key objectives is to bring farming to the forefront of Digital Agriculture and PA, as the agricultural sector lags behind in the uptake of new technologies compared to other sectors due to reduced investment capabilities [61].
- The [“No Food Left Behind” initiative](#) was created by World Wildlife Fund (WWF), UC Davis, UC Santa Clara and Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), non-profits and trade associations. This initiative consists of a series of publications that address the problem of FLW at farm stage with the aim to highlight its impacts and increase awareness in the public.

6.5.2 Economic factors

- Most of European farms are small; in 2016, 67.6% of all EU farms had an economic output between €2,000 and €8,000 per year [62]. This limits their capacity to invest in technological innovations. They normally rely on contractors to access these services.
- Current market structures separate producers from consumers through a number of intermediaries, making it difficult for farmers to assess market needs and demand, often leading to mismatches in volume, time of planting and harvesting, and subsequent produce surpluses that lead to food losses [46].
- A review considering 234 studies from 1988 to 2005 concluded that the application of PATs was profitable in an average of 68% of cases [49].
- The contribution of the agricultural manufacturing to the European economy is significant: in 2016 there were over 7,200 manufacturers of agricultural machinery equipment, comprising both large multinational companies and SMEs. These produce 450 different machine types, generating a turnover of €40 billion annually. Leading countries are Germany, Italy and France, which together hold 59% of the turnover. The sector provides over 173,000 direct jobs and 125,000 indirect jobs (associated to the distribution, maintenance and service networks) [61].

6.5.3 Social factors

- Agriculture is unattractive for younger people as it is physically demanding, repetitive, and often conducted in adverse environments; these conditions can favour the adoption of automation/robotics technologies [33]. Additionally, they can overcome the increasing labour shortages caused by rural depopulation.
- The balance of power favours markets over farmers, which lack leverage to set prices for their produce, which, in turn, affects their income. There is a direct correlation between lower-income farmers and level of waste. This occurs because farmers cannot invest in farming technology or labour to prevent food waste, which may lead to supply issues. If supply is low, food prices increase and these are reserved for export or higher-income domestic markets, leading to undernutrition locally [46].
- PA manufacturing provides opportunities for employment mostly in rural areas [61].
- PATs can contribute to improve working conditions by reducing rutinary/repetitive tasks and fatigue [49].
- Adoption of advanced automation technologies has the potential to attract highly-skilled workers to the agricultural sector. This can contribute to reversing the ongoing demographic shift from rural to urban areas [33]. However, it is

necessary to be aware of potential “digital divide” and non-adopters lacking behind due to the lack of support and/or infrastructure.

6.5.4 Technological factors

- Full automation in farms is still not attainable and the investment required to reach it is only available for larger companies. This means that the transition to automation has to be achieved gradually, probably by retrofitting existing machinery. Initially, these will coexist with existing production systems [33].
- The high demand of certain components required for automation (such as cameras, laptops, and processors) has lowered their cost, allowing production at a competitive cost and favouring development of new technologies [33].
- Some technologies already used in other industries (i.e. machine vision, autonomous vehicles, etc) can be readily adapted for use in the agri-food industry, while others will need to be developed specifically for agriculture [33].
- Current SFT are addressing isolated aspects at farm level. A system capable of integrating inputs from different sub-systems would improve applicability [33].
- Most SFTs are at a very early stage of development: A study investigating the number of SFT solutions at research and commercial stages in Europe identified a total of 13,251 scientific papers in a six-year period; of these, only 4% tested a prototype in field conditions. This same study identified 94 research projects under the FP7 and H2020 frameworks and 439 commercially available products. Technologies related to fertilisation are the most numerous in the market, as well as those related to tillage and sowing. These segments are mature. Additionally, reacting and automation technologies were highly represented among commercial solutions [47].
- Controlled Traffic Farming is the most successful segment in PA as it has proven reductions of up to 75% in input and machinery costs.
- While machine vision is already being applied mainly in fruit and vegetable production, these technologies are still at early stages of development, mostly still in research stage and far from being ready for commercialisation [49].
- Computer vision is currently in use in livestock monitoring. Further advancements will greatly contribute to the development of autonomous robotic systems. Current challenges such as changing lighting conditions, image background, shadowing, etc. need to be addressed. Analysis of 3D point clouds derived from stereo imagery/RGB-D cameras are good candidates to address these problems [33].
- The [Consortium for Innovation in Post-Harvest Loss and Food Waste Reduction](#) was launched in 2019. This is an international consortium conducting research with the objective to develop processes and technologies aimed to improve

shelf-life and minimise spoilage of produce. This will help reduce FLW at post-harvest stage.

6.5.5 Legal factors

- [Directive \(EU\) 2019/633](#) on unfair trading practices (UTP) in B2B relationships in the agricultural and food supply chain. This directive aims to tackle the power imbalances between actors in the agri-food supply chain in order to protect weaker suppliers from stronger buyers. The suppliers mainly refer to farmers and farmer associations, but also to small- or medium-sized companies in other stages, such as manufacturers/distributors. The Directive applies when either the supplier or the buyer (or both) are located within the EU, and is based on relative size of operators (turnover). Among black practices (those prohibited regardless of the circumstances) is the prohibition to cancel orders of perishable food products on short notice, which would have an impact on food loss [63].

6.5.6 Environmental factors

- Generally, there is a lack of quantifiable environmental impacts associated with the use of PATs. However, evidence is starting to emerge; for example, it is demonstrated that PATs can reduce the carbon footprint associated with an increased efficiency in fuel use by targeting applications [49].
- The use of digital innovations in agriculture is considered to have a positive environmental impact by reducing the use of pesticides and fertilisers [49]; thus contributing to:
 - mitigation and adaptation to climate change;
 - improvement of water quality;
 - protection the soil and the biodiversity.

6.6 Barriers to entry

Some of the generic, but also more specific barriers that solutions developed by SILL 3 may face when entering the market are listed below:

- Underestimation of levels and impact of FLW at farm level by policymakers may hinder the adoption of technologies from farmers to prevent it; they may not feel it is necessary/do not have incentives to address the problem [46].
- Adoption of SFTs/PATs greatly depends on profitability for farmers. Technologies aimed to reduce waste may not be seen as very profitable and this may hinder adoption, especially on smaller farms: size greatly influences profitability of PATs (adoption will depend on investments depreciating over the entire farm; thus larger farms can benefit from a faster ROI than smaller ones) [49].

- The increasing average age of farm managers may be a limiting factor in the adoption of new technologies. In 2016, 32% of all farm managers in the EU were 65 years old or over [64]. Older farmers generally have lower education levels and are less skilled with modern technologies (i.e. using computers); thus, being less prone to adopt new digital technologies than younger people [42].
- Reluctance from farmers to adopt digital technologies in their everyday farming processes.
- The costs of setting up the solution can be limiting for small-scale farms (most of the farms in EU are small). However, these are not the primary target for the solutions, as their low production also means their FLW is small.

6.7 Pre- and Post-harvest Innovations Market Summary

SILL 3 proposed innovations to tackle the pre- and post-harvest FLW are aiming at smart greenhouse and smart harvest markets. Drivers for both are found to be in feeding constantly increasing global population, increased adoption of smart farming technologies, and importantly increased governmental support for implementation of novel technologies. The solution proposed by ZeroW focuses on optimising harvesting schedule for greenhouse-grown vegetables, allowing for the precise planning and prediction of expected product yield, in addition to identification of crops that do not comply to aesthetic standards and their repurposing to other uses early in the supply chain. This solution does not centre on the automatic harvesting part, as it is the case with majority of market available solutions, but on improving conditions at the organisational level, fostering data-driven decision making and employing new tools and methods for more accurate, timely and efficient work planning; this helps greenhouse farm managers organise their resources more efficiently. Summary of market dynamics associated to the pre- and post-harvest innovations relevant to ZeroW proposed solutions is presented in Figure 29.

Greenhouse farming and cultivating vegetables indoors can reduce food losses due to the adverse weather conditions and climate change. Similarly, cultivation in controlled environments such as vertical farming can foster FLW reduction and overall environmental impact of farming. Greenhouses and vertical farms can be positioned closer to the urban areas, shortening/optimising supply chain between producers and consumers in urban areas, thus minimising delivery times and consequently risk of generating FLW due to the long distribution.

<p>DRIVERS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PA is associated with higher sustainability, accelerating the demand and public acceptance for innovations. • Labour shortages due to the depopulation of rural regions are boosting the demand for automated solutions in farms/greenhouses. • The EU eco-schemes will encourage sustainable practices, favouring the uptake of smart solutions as key enablers of sustainable food systems.
<p>RESTRAINTS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High costs of implementation of PATs can limit profitability to the larger farms. • Most European farms are small and may not be able to afford high investments in technology. • Lack of confidence among end users regarding the benefits of application of PATs.
<p>OPPORTUNITIES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extensive investments in the agri-tech area. • Lower costs and enhanced efficiency/accuracy of enabling technologies are accelerating the development of PA solutions.
<p>CHALLENGES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of standardised data exchange protocols may limit adoption of PA/FMIS. • Commercial deployment of smart harvest technologies is slow and gradual resulting in capital lockup and delays in returns. • Farmers may be less compelled to use PAT if a solution is not clearly profitable; this can particularly relevant for the solutions that are directly addressing FLW.

Figure 29. Summary of market dynamics for cluster 2.

Sustainable agricultural practices are gaining momentum in the European agricultural landscape, partly due to the regulatory requirements and new schemes providing incentives for the stakeholders adopting sustainable practices, hence new solutions supporting these are required in the market. As the European agriculture is dominated by small farms, with limited resources to invest in novel technologies and limited technical knowledge, low cost might be the major market requirement; additionally governmental support for the implementation of smart agricultural and farming technologies is crucial for widescale adoption to be realised. Larger farms, although less common in Europe, have the capacity and the incentive (i.e. higher levels of possible FLW generated) to invest in this type of technologies.

7 ZeroW Food Processing Innovations

This section is evaluating the potential impact of ZeroW's innovations that are intended for food processors. Food processing refers to raw products that are transformed into ingredients, which normally have improved shelf-life. By contrast, food manufacturing is the process of using these ingredients to elaborate a more complex food product. This analysis is focusing on food processing innovations that are directly or indirectly tackling FLW at this level of the supply chain.

7.1 ZeroW's proposed innovations

The SILLs involved in food processing are SILL 2, 4, 5 and 6. The innovations that are expected from these are:

- Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh food products (SILL 2);
- Mobile food valorisation as a service (SILL 4);

- Ugly food early identification, shelf-life assessment and alternative valorisation (SILL 5);
- Food waste reduction through advanced data-driven production process control and optimisation (SILL 6).

7.1.1 SILL 2 – Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh food products

The packaging solution to be developed by SILL 2 is aiming at reducing food waste and use of unsustainable packaging at the retail and consumer level.

Figure 30. SILL 2 focusses on intelligent packaging for salmon.

Initially, packaging is intended for oily fish (salmon) and has the following features:

- Barrier and film packaging made of compostable materials to improve the isolating properties of the package. This is aimed to improve preservation of the food and, more importantly, to avoid the use of non-recyclable multilayer plastic packaging, which has a great environmental impact;
- Compartmentalised tray acting as a barrier to keep the exudates away from the fish. These metabolites produced by fish contribute to its decomposition; thus, by avoiding the contact between fresh fish and exudates, enables the quality of product to be maintained for longer;
- Freshness indicator label (intelligent packaging) with the ability to change its colour in the presence of certain metabolites related to decomposition. The label can be read with a mobile app to indicate the remaining shelf-life of the product to stakeholders (distributors, retailers); this will allow for better stock management. Additionally, consumers will be offered a more accurate indication of the remaining shelf-life of the food than the current one provided by the “use-by” date. This will contribute to reduction of FLW.

As mentioned earlier, and in the context of the ZeroW project, the freshness indicator will be initially intended to track quality of fresh oily fish (salmon) kept in anaerobic modified atmosphere packaging (MAP), with the possibility to be adapted to other fresh food products.

7.1.2 SILL 4 – Mobile food valorisation as a service

SILL 4 will output a mobile, versatile processing unit with high throughput to optimise the valorisation of large volumes of biomass (fruits and vegetables) in regions with intensive agri-food production and processing, obtaining high-added-value products like juices, purees and smoothies. The unit will help valorise what would otherwise be a source of FLW. Additionally, processing will prolong the shelf-life of these highly-perishable products.

Figure 31. SILL 4 utilises mobile processing unit to valorise edible FLW.

Currently, large quantities of produce remain underutilised (leading to FLW), or are used as lower-value inputs for other sectors such as feed production/energy generation. There is a potential to turn it into high-value-added products; however, availability of underutilised produce is variable and, hence, the processing equipment needs to be flexible and versatile. Such processing capacity is not available in most regions but is highly needed, especially at critical time points e.g., surplus production due to climatic conditions, a storm destroying fruit and vegetables rendering them unsuitable for the fresh produce market, or a crisis (e.g., Covid-19, Russian Boycott of EU import of pome fruit). Also, transporting relatively small and seasonal food surplus quantities to valorisation facilities is prohibitive due to its high cost; a mobile solution is required to reduce these costs.

The mobile processing unit proposed under the ZeroW project will be based on the output from the [FOX Project](#) (Food processing in a Box) – Mobile processing and packaging unit of fruits and vegetables, creating a short supply chain. The outputs are juices and dried vegetables. As it is mobile, the processing can be made onsite. Use of spiral filter press, a technology aimed to obtain juices and purees under vacuum conditions to ensure low oxygen, and Pulsed Electric Field (PEF) to inactivate microorganisms. These technologies combined eliminate the need to add preservatives [65]. In the context of ZeroW, the mobile unit will be downscaled and used to obtain a broader range of products, possibly juice, puree or smoothies,

which can be end products or used as ingredients for further product developments sold via B2B.

The mobile processing unit will use integrated technologies such as low-oxygen milling and fractionation technologies (GEA VacullIQ, HPP, PEF, etc.):

- Spiral filter press – Vacuum separation system to prevent oxidation and browning by ensuring oxygen-protected during juice extraction [65]; this is utilised in GEA VacullIQ.
- Pulsed Electric Field (PEF) – To preserve the juice via electroporation of microorganisms, prolonging shelf-life and improving the quality of the juice [65].
- High Pressure Processing (HPP) - A non-thermal food processing method to improve food safety and shelf-life.

The optimal processing capacity of the mobile unit is 200 litres per hour and extraction yield of 77.7% w/v. Operations include washing, crushing, solid-liquid separation, cooling down and filling [65].

In order to best utilise the services of mobile processing unit, the Regional Food Waste Data Space, that will be developed under the scope of SILL 4 and integrated within the OFLW Data Space (as described in Section 5.1), will enable data flow between interested parties. By connecting primary producers and food processors through the Regional Food Waste Data Space, timely and accurate information essential to optimise the management and utilisation of mobile food processing unit will be available.

7.1.3 SILL 5 – Ugly food early identification, shelf-life assessment and alternative valorisation

Two technologies, part of an integrated solution, will be developed under SILL 5, with the objective to identify ugly food in an automated way:

1. Hardware – Multi-sensor platform with next-generation, non-destructive sensors detecting multispectral LED illumination in the visible and infrared ranges and two high-speed cameras with pneumatic ejection at 3 outputs. These will be incorporated into a handheld molecular contaminant screener (HMCS) to enhance food safety, reduce food waste and food fraud during processing. This HMCS utilizes *the best-in-class portable mass spectrometer technology currently available*, developed by [NG Sensors](#). The system will be deployed in industrial food processing facilities.
2. Software – The multi-sensor platform will be powered by AI and real-time data processing techniques working collaboratively to identify ugly food from the input provided.

The multi-sensor platform will analyse and process tomatoes, offering the possibility to classify them under three different categories based on quality, shelf-life

parameters and organic/non-organic origin. The data service platform will control the input.

Figure 32. SILL 5 will develop multi-sensor platform for “ugly” food identification.

The innovation developed under SILL 5 aims to address several gaps in the food industry such as:

- Need to improve transparency and optimise the FSC, which can be achieved using non-destructive quality analysis and multi-attribute classification techniques.
- Requirement to improve storage and logistics management.
- Need to increase forecasting and sharing of information capabilities in the FSC.
- Increased collaboration efforts required between stakeholders in the FSC (producers, retailers and consumers).
- Need for an optimised and automated system for rapid product evaluation to support efficient decision making.

7.1.4 SILL 6 – Advanced data-driven production process control and optimisation

SILL 6 will result in the development of several algorithms based on portable near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy technology aiming to non-destructively determine specific pre-defined parameters related to food quality. Additionally, an algorithm based on intelligent data analysis will be developed to optimise the breeding process. These could be exploited either individually or as a complete control & optimisation tool for the food industry.

Figure 33. SILL 6 will test portable NIR technology applied in meat processing.

The innovations will be:

1. Advancements in the level of portable NIR technology for food applications, from TRL 5 to TRL 7.
2. Integral technical solution composed by the portable NIR, process data modelling and optimisation. These will be synchronised under the same product so they can work in a synergic way.
3. Open-source technologies, favouring integration and interoperability among different IT systems.

Proposed SILL 6 innovations aim to tackle lack of adequate data-driven monitoring and control measures in food SMEs; these measures are key to optimisation of production processes and resulting reduction of FLW. When applied to food processing, SILL 6 innovations are expected to stipulate benefits such as (i) Continuous control and optimisation of key variables and dynamics affecting the processes as well as the intermediate and final products; (ii) Estimated reduction of food losses of around 25%; (iii) Less requirements of inputs (raw materials, ingredients, energy), as well as a reduction in the number of line supervisors; (iv) Increased resilience (4 in qualitative scale 1 to 5) at food processing stage.

7.2 Market Overview

In Europe alone, the food processing industry was responsible for the generation of approximately 36.7 million tons of waste in 2018 [66]. The following sections will review the markets relevant for each specific SILL and anticipated solutions.

7.2.1 Food processing innovations

Food processing consists of a series of steps where fresh produce is transformed into food products/ingredients with added value. The food is first subject to a series of pre-processing techniques, such as washing, cleaning, drying, chilling, freezing, grading, milling and homogenisation. Once pre-processed, the product is transformed into added-value foods and/or ingredients [67].

The main aim of novel food processing technologies is to minimise the degradation impacts that affect the quality of the final product, with as little processing as possible. Current innovations in the industry are summarised in the following table:

Table 11. Novel food processing technologies. Adopted from [67]

Thermal processes				
Name	Description	Pros	Cons	Commercial applications
Radio Frequency (RF) Heating	Application of high-frequency radio waves to heat a dielectric material	Instant, uniform, selective and deep heat of food products Independent of the product's thermal conductivity, size, density Lower energy requirements than conventional thermal processes	RF-induced heat is dependent on moisture content Different dielectric properties of treated products result in variations in efficacy High implementation costs More complicated than conventional heating methods	Continuous and batch operations Applications on limited number of fruits and vegetables
Microwave (MW) heating	Electromagnetic radiation (1 – 100 GHz), generating heat	Fast energy transfer Easy to use and control Clean environment	Absorption depends on dielectric and magnetic properties Limited use: uneven heating as intensity of the MW weakens quickly Low energy efficiency	Drying Baking biscuits/breads Precooking: meals, meat & meat products, cereals Pasteurisation and sterilisation Unfreezing Vegetable blanching ²
MW + RF heating	Longer wavelengths than MW alone	Deeper penetration without overheating surfaces Customisable	High costs Low energy efficiency	Continuous and batch Same applications as MW
Ohmic heating (OH)	Heat produced due to the resistance created by an electric current passing through food	Deeper and uniform heating No degradation of nutrients Cost-efficient and lower energy requirements Eco-friendly	Direct contact between electrodes and liquid food required Emerging technology (20 commercial systems in use)	Treatment of liquid/semi-solid or large pieces of food in liquids (soup, stews, syrups, etc) Sterilisation, pasteurisation (juice), thawing blanching

² Blanching is a cooking process aimed to deactivate enzymes in vegetables and fruits, to preserve their quality (related to colour, flavour and nutritive content) for longer. It is often performed before freezing, drying or canning.

		Easy integration into existing equipment		packaging, heating of foods, etc.
Infrared heating	Energy between ultraviolet (UV) and MW radiation. Far infrared (3k-10k nm) is most suitable for food Indirect heating: depends on surface characteristics and colour	Fast heating rate: low processing time Low energy consumption No overheating as the surrounding atmosphere does not get heated Highly controllable Safe Allows compact designs	Limited heating applications: it only reaches a depth of a few mm. Not adequate for solid foods (lower heat conductivity)	Drying, cooking, blanching, peeling, pasteurisation Treatment of food and agricultural products. Emerging use for reduction of off-flavours and deterioration in fruit and vegetables
Non-thermal processes				
Name	Description	Pros	Cons	Commercial apps
High-pressure processing (HPP)	Application of uniform ultra-high pressures to food, independent of size/shape, decreasing its volume. Chemical properties do not change, while interactions by non-covalent bonds are modified.	No changes in quality Time- and energy-efficient No waste production Safe Treatment can be done after packaging Low cost (€0.1-0.15/kg)	Not enough evidence of efficient pathogen inactivation for certain strains/species, limiting adoption	Pathogen inactivation Shelf-life extension and preservation Improved shelf-life on dairy products Reduction of allergenicity of milk
Pulsed electric field (PEF)	Short (micro/milliseconds) pulses of high electric fields of a product inside a PEF chamber, creating very high pressure under water	Cell permeabilization w/o heating Increases shelf-life Maintenance of quality and nutritive content Low cost & energy consumption Easy integration into processing lines	Solid products cannot be treated (low conductivity) Small scale (proof of concept)	Microorganism deactivation Uses for liquid and semi-solid products: juices, soup, yoghurt, etc)
Cold plasma technology (CPT)	Use of ionised gases to inactivate pathogens and spoiling microorganisms	Increased shelf life High nutritional content No toxic residues/gases left on product after treatment	Emerging technology Creation of reactive species with unknown effects on some food molecules (vitamins, lipids): potential to	Sterilisation of food and packages Elimination of pesticides on surfaces (vegetables) Application on solid and liquid foods: meat, grains, fresh produce, etc.

			produce compounds that cause rancidity/off-flavour Not scaled yet	
Ultrasound	Based on cycles of compression and rarefaction using sound waves with frequency over 16kHz, causing bubbles which end up collapsing. Ultrasonication Assisted Extraction (UAE) is used to obtain bioactive compounds	Ready for commercial-scale applications	Potential deterioration of some food properties such as colour, flavour, nutritional content	Widely used in food processing: drying, homogenisation, texture enhancement, etc. Food preservation: reduction of pathogens
Radiation	Application of gamma or X rays to eliminate microorganisms without altering the product	Minimal loss of quality, depending on the dose and source of radiation No radioactive waste produced Reduces post-harvest loss Approved by FDA and some EU countries Potential to eliminate quarantine requirements for imported produce	Not suitable for food containing high contents of lipids/vitamins as it induces peroxidation of fatty acids, causing rancid taste Limited industry use due to safety concerns Low acceptance by the public	Cereals, legumes, fruit, vegetables, meat, etc.
Ultraviolet (UV) & pulsed light (PL)	Application of light with a wavelength of 100-380nm (UV) or 180-1,100nm (PL) to inactivate microorganisms	No alterations in quality Increased shelf-life Low maintenance costs Eco-friendly Flexible installation at any point of the facility	Low penetration: only for surface decontamination Regulatory requirements for each new treated food type	Sterilisation of food, surfaces, packaging and equipment Thermal pasteurisation of juices

Other minimal processing methods to prolong the shelf life are used in combination with modified atmosphere packaging or MAP (Section 7.2.3), for example the application of low temperatures, addition of antimicrobials or antioxidants, use of water/pH regulators and high-pressure processing (above) [68].

7.2.2 Food upcycling

Upcycled food is a newly coined term to refer to value-added food products destined for human consumption, elaborated from the edible parts of surplus/wasted food, for instance damaged/sub-grade produce, or by-products/scrap from food manufacturing/preparation. These products would have been otherwise allocated to non-food applications or discarded. To be considered upcycled, the food product is required to have additional processing steps. As such, surplus produce redistributed to consumers without further processing would not be considered upcycled; it would need to be transformed into a new product [69].

The [Upcycled Food Association](#) has recently introduced a programme to certify these products: to be considered as upcycled, a food product has to contain at least 10% of upcycled ingredients, by weight. Manufacturers are required to include information about the production process, traceability, and an assessment on health-related risks and GHG emissions [69].

The safety of the upcycled ingredients will depend on their source and consequently, on the level of the supply chain they are produced. To address potential safety issues, the supply chain should be auditable and the upcycled ingredients should be listed on the label [69].

7.2.3 Food packaging innovations

Food packaging is used to contain the food product with the objective to preserve its quality and reduce the chances of spoilage for a longer time. Additionally, new designs can help consumers buy portions that match their requirements, which can potentially reduce FLW from uneaten leftovers. Thus, food packaging is directly contributing towards a reduction of food waste at the expense of an associated environmental impact due to the waste it generates: packaging is produced in large volumes and the use time is often short [68]. A balance is required to achieve correct packaging to reduce spoilage without generating an excessive amount of waste.

Some food products, such as fish and meat, are highly susceptible to microbial growth at elevated temperatures, which is the main reason for spoilage. Modified atmosphere packaging (MAP) was initially developed in the 1930s to preserve fresh produce as it helps reduce respiration rates and associated ethylene production. Its application for fish and meat products has the objective to change the composition of gases in the headspace to delay bacterial activity. The gases most frequently used are O₂, CO₂ and N₂. One of the main limitations of MAP is that it cannot prevent the growth of anaerobic bacteria such as *Clostridium botulinum*, which produces botulinic toxin (one of the most potent natural toxins), especially under anaerobic conditions. Additionally, MAP has high space requirements as the ratio between gas volume and product needs to be high [68].

Smart packaging technologies such as intelligent and active packaging (IP and AP, respectively) are innovative methods that can be used to extend shelf-life of highly perishable products. These are normally used in combination with MAP.

Intelligent packaging (IP). These monitor the status of the food product and internal and external changes, and communicate it to stakeholders along the supply chain. These are further classified into:

- Indicators:
 - Time Temperature Indicators (TTI). Important in cold chain management systems. These show the cumulative effect of temperature on food quality, normally represented as an irreversible discolouration of the indicator. There are different types: diffusion-based, microbial, enzymatic, etc [70].
 - Gas/Freshness indicators. They show changes in the gas composition inside the package, such as CO₂, NH₃, H₂S, dimethylamine and trimethylamine, as quality indicators. Commercial applications are challenged as: 1) variations in the nature and/or manufacturing process of different food products require different indicators; 2) the gas indicator has to be placed into the package in direct contact with food, requiring to comply with safety regulations; 3) as most dyes are hydrophilic, they may be able to migrate into products if these have high water content [70].
 - Leakage indicators. These help ensure the integrity of the package. A faulty seal will increase the levels of O₂ and reduce CO₂ inside the package, which can be detected with pH (CO₂) or oxygen indicators [68].
- Sensors. These detect physical or chemical properties of the product and convert them into electric signals. These are further classified into biosensors (based on bioreceptors) and humidity sensors (based on hygrometers). Sensors can be coupled with radio-frequency identification (RFID) systems that allow storage data for real-time monitoring and management. Current RFID tags can store up to 1Mb of data for this purpose [70], making them suitable tools in the digitalisation of the FSC (Section 5).

Active packaging (AP). These detect changes in the environment and act accordingly to alter them, maintaining the food product in suitable conditions for its preservation. There are different types available:

- Gas control – these can be oxygen scavengers and CO₂ emitters.
 - Oxygen scavengers. These reduce the concentration of O₂ below the 0.01-0.05% range. The most frequently used are those based on oxidation of iron/ferrous salts, in sachets. They prevent oxidation of fats and certain vitamins, development of off-flavours and growth of aerobic microorganisms without additives [70].
 - CO₂ emitters. These solve the high requirements of space of MAP technologies, as the CO₂ is released in the headspace as needed, without additional gas insertion [68] , [70].

- Moisture control. These are used for food products with low water content, while they have low applicability to hydrated products such as fresh meat or fish [68]. Desiccants are applied using sachets; most are based on silica gel as it is not toxic nor corrosive. They can be placed below the product to absorb exudates [70]. Cellulose-based pads are not considered as AP by the EC as these do not actively change the conditions inside the package but passively absorb exudates from the product ([Regulation EC 450/2009](#)) [68].

Antimicrobial/Antioxidant packaging. Direct incorporation of the antimicrobial or antioxidant agents into the packaging film. These are used to prolong shelf-life of solid products such as fish or meat. The advantage is that the compounds are not required to be in direct contact with the food. The main drawback is that they may change the sensory parameters (colour, odour, taste) of the food product [70].

Packaging is crucial in FLW prevention: it is estimated that packaging-related issues are responsible for around 20-25% of food waste generated downstream the supply chain, at household stage. The issues identified by consumers are related to inadequate proportions, difficulties when emptying the packages and misunderstandings regarding use-by/best-before dates [71].

7.2.4 Market size

7.2.4.1 Markets for SILL 2

Biodegradable Films Market – This market was worth \$967 million in 2021 and it is expected it will demonstrate moderate growth at a CAGR of 7.2%, to reach a value of \$1,368 million by 2026. The increased use of biodegradable films in packaging applications is the main factor driving growth in this market. Europe dominated the market in 2021 with a production of 101ktonnes in 2021 [72].

By type, the market is segmented into polylactic acid, biodegradable polyesters, polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), starch blends and others (regenerated cellulose and cellulose derivatives) (Figure 34). PLA is the most suitable market segment as this is the main component of the packaging developed under SILL 2. This holds the largest share of the market with a global value of \$314 million in 2021. Growth, however, is expected to be slower than other segments with a CAGR of 6.4%, to be worth \$428 million by 2026. PLA is highly sought for packaging due to its higher degradability when compared with conventional plastics (3-6 months in an industrial composting system). In the food industry it is used as part of thermoformed products (bottles, takeaway food trays, etc), and it does not have an impact on food prices and is more cost effective than other biodegradable plastics [72].

Figure 34. Market size of the Biodegradable Films Market, by type [72]

By application, the Biodegradable Films Market can be segmented in Food packaging, Agriculture & horticulture, Cosmetics & personal care products, Industrial packaging and Others (composting, service ware and carrier bags). For SILL 2, the target application is the food packaging segment, which in 2021 dominated the market with a share of approximately 60% of the Biodegradable Films market size [72].

Food Packaging Technology and Equipment Market – This market includes technologies and machinery used for packaging of food products, including smart (active and intelligent) packaging. This market was worth \$19.72 billion in 2018 and will reach \$26.7 by 2023 with a CAGR of 6.46% during the forecast period [73].

Figure 35. Food packaging technology and equipment market size, by type [73].

The most relevant market segments for SILL 2 based on the type of packaging are the intelligent and the biodegradable packaging market segments (Figure 35). The intelligent packaging segment was valued at \$6,468.8 million in 2018 globally. Europe is the leader of the intelligent packaging segment: it held 32% share of the total market in 2018, with a value of \$1533.5 million. The intelligent packaging segment is projected to grow to \$2,098.8 million by 2023 at a CAGR of 6.48% in the European region. The growth in this sector is heavily linked to the active packaging segment as its performance can be measured and monitored with intelligent packaging [73].

In the biodegradable segment, North America is dominating the market with a value expected to reach \$1,054.9 million in 2023 [73]. The demand for biodegradable packaging will grow due to environmental concerns associated with the use of plastics, as these are difficult to decompose, leading to tightening regulations in the use of plastics favouring alternatives able to degrade faster [73].

By material, the Food Packaging Technology market is segmented into Plastics, Paper & paperboard, Metal, Glass & wood and Others (including polysaccharides, proteins and lipids). Of these, plastics is the most suitable market segment for ZeroW food packaging innovation. This segment dominated the market in 2018 with a value of \$18,846 million. Growth is driven by the increasing dependence of consumers on packaged foods [73].

By application, the segments are: Convenience foods; Poultry/seafood/meat products; Bakery products; Dairy/dairy products, Confectionery products; Fruits & vegetables and Others (sauces & dressings, condiments). The market segment most relevant to ZeroW is the Poultry, seafood and meat products. This segment was worth \$8,690.4 million in 2018 and is the second largest segment after Convenience foods. It will reach \$12,194.8 million in 2023, registering a CAGR of 7.01% during the forecasted period (Figure 36). The poultry, seafood & meat products segment is of special interest for the intelligent (and active) packaging sector, as these products are highly perishable and susceptible to quality loss such as discoloration, dehydration during transport and taste degradation caused by microbes: adequate, innovative packaging can be used to prevent these [73].

Figure 36. Food Packaging Technology and Equipment market size, by application [73].

7.2.4.2 Markets for SILLs 4, 5, 6

Food Processing and Handling Equipment Market was estimated to be worth \$130.7 billion in 2021, and is expected to reach \$175.1 by 2026, registering a CAGR of 6% in this period [74]. The food processing and handling equipment market is segmented by type into three segments: food processing, food service (restaurants) and food packaging equipment (Figure 37).

Figure 37. Market size of the Food Processing and Handling Equipment [74].

The **food processing** equipment segment is the most relevant in relation with the processing solutions developed withing the ZeroW project. With a value of \$58.3 billion, this segment is dominating the market, and will continue to do so during the forecast period, reaching \$76 billion in 2026 with a CAGR of 5.5%. This market is further divided into pre-processing and primary processing equipment:

Pre-processing – This contributes to prolonging shelf life of food products and increasing their added value. The types of processing included in this segment are listed below, while their market values are summarised in Table 12 below:

- **Sorting and Grading:** separation of foods according to shape, size, colour and weight. This is used to classify food products before further processing. While this process is performed manually in some developing countries, a number of machines allowing automation are beginning to be commercialised in developed countries. This market segment is of interest for the solution developed under SILL 5.
- **Cutting, Peeling, Grinding, Slicing and Washing:** intended especially for fruit, vegetables, meat, poultry and seafood. Automation in this area allows to reduce risks derived from human errors and improve safety by reducing human contact with the foods.
- **Mixing and blending:** used in the beverage sector, among others. Automation contributes to reducing the time required for batch mixing, having great impact on efficiency and are important in scaling up manufacturing.

Table 12. Market size for the pre-processing equipment segment, by type (in \$ million) [74].

Type	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	CAGR
Sorting & Grading	2,861.3	3,012.4	3,175.2	3,350.3	3,539.2	3742.8	5.5%
Cutting, peeling, etc.	8,077.1	8,482.8	8,919.2	9,387.6	9,891.3	10,433.1	5.3%
Mixing & Blending	8,020.8	8,449.9	8,911.9	9,408.6	9,943.5	10,519.9	5.6%
Total	18,959.1	19,945.1	21,006.3	22,146.5	23,374	24,695.9	5.4%

Primary processing – Main processes for food processors and manufacturers. It includes forming, extruding, coating, drying, cooling, freezing equipment, thermal, and others (filtration, pressing and homogenisation equipment).

Europe is the second largest food processing and handling market globally, following the Asia-Pacific region. The food and beverage industry is the largest manufacturing sector. The recent increase in demand for juices, and especially for fresh fruit and vegetable juices is compelling the industry to produce a wide variety of products. The company [GEA Group](#) (Germany) implements tailor-made processes and packaging plants to produce beverages. This group has patented extraction process using vacuum and commercialised the VaculiQ spiral vacuum filter; this technology is used in SILL 4 as a part of the mobile processing unit.

Fruit and Vegetable Processing Market is relevant for several SILLs like SILL 4 and SILL 5. Processing is used to prolong the shelf life to be stored canned, dried, frozen or as juices. This market was valued at \$8.7 billion in 2022, and will grow at a CAGR of 6.4% until 2027, when it is projected at \$11.8 billion. It is estimated that the vegetables segment will dominate the market during the forecast period, with a 38.6% share and growth at a CAGR of 7.2% [75].

The market is segmented by equipment type in **pre-processing equipment**, which is the most relevant for ZeroW innovations. During this stage, the fruits and vegetables are washed using agitating systems, water jets and brush washers, and then graded. It is estimated that the timely sorting and grading of fresh produce during pre-processing can significantly reduce FLW before reaching the consumers. With a global size estimated at \$1.3 billion in 2022, this market segment will grow at a CAGR of 6% to reach a value of \$1.8 billion in 2027 (Figure 38) [75].

Region	2022-e	2023-p	2024-p	2025-p	2026-p	2027-p	CAGR (2022-2027)
North America	375.3	392.4	411.0	431.4	453.6	478.0	5.0%
Europe	340.4	355.9	372.9	391.5	411.9	434.2	5.0%
Asia Pacific	477.7	511.4	548.5	589.6	634.9	685.1	7.5%
South America	126.4	133.6	141.5	150.1	159.5	169.8	6.1%
RoW*	21.4	22.4	23.6	24.8	26.1	27.6	5.2%
Total	1,341.2	1,415.7	1,497.5	1,587.3	1,686.0	1,794.6	6.0%

Figure 38. Market value of the fruit and vegetables processing equipment segment, by region [75]

IR Spectroscopy Market – This market refers to spectrometers that operate in the infrared region to assess the composition of materials, used for quality control and other applications [76].

The market was worth \$1.08 billion in 2020, and it is estimated it will grow to reach \$1.3 billion in 2025 at a 4.1% CAGR. By technology, the market is segmented in near-infrared (NIR), mid-infrared (MIR) and far-infrared (FIR) segments (Figure 39) [76].

Figure 39. Market size and forecast of the IR Spectroscopy market, by technology [76]

This market segment is largely influenced by the growing consumers concern and increased awareness of the quality of the food they are consuming. As MIR is usually used to analyse edible oils and to detect foreign components in food items, this segment is holding the largest share of IR spectroscopy market and this trend will continue during the forecast period. However, the market segment growing at a fastest pace will be the FIR technology, at a 7.34% CAGR [76].

By product type, ZeroW's target is the portable spectroscopes segment, which was valued at \$140.2 million in 2020 and will reach \$195 million in 2025 at a CAGR of 6.82%. The size for each market segment by wavelength is summarised in Table 13 [76].

Table 13. Market value of the portable IR spectroscopes market segment, by wavelength (in \$ million) [76]

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	CAGR (2020-2025)
NIR	60	64.6	69.5	74.7	80.1	85.8	7.42%
MIR	75.5	80.6	86.0	91.5	97.3	103.3	6.48%
FIR	4.7	5.0	5.2	5.4	5.6	5.8	4.36%
Total	140.2	150.2	160.7	171.6	183.0	195.0	6.82%

The IR spectroscopy market in the food & beverages industry was worth \$160.22 million in 2020. It will grow at a CAGR of 3.60% to reach \$191.20 million in 2025 [76]. This growth is mainly attributed to the increasing use of these technologies in determining the quality of food and beverages. It is also being used to detect pesticides and bacterial contaminations in food items [76].

7.3 Market Drivers & Dynamics

Factors that influences the ZeroW Food Processing Innovations relevant markets, including opportunities driving market growth, as well as any potential restraints and challenges are discussed below.

7.3.1 Market drivers

- ✓ The increasing global population requires more resilient food systems which include better preservation of food products, encouraging the adoption of innovative food processing and packaging technologies [67], [68].
- ✓ High incidence of foodborne diseases/outbreaks are boosting the demand for safer ways to protect food products [67] and for non-destructive quality testing methods.
- ✓ Higher quality requirements for food among consumers. These rely heavily on how the food is processed, driving the demand for innovative techniques that can deliver this increased quality [67]. Particularly, the increase in demand for healthy foods, coupled with advancements in processing equipment, are driving the fruit and vegetable processing market [75].
- ✓ The increase in demand for fresh food products is driving the packaging market. Food manufacturers are thus adopting advanced packaging solutions that help increase the shelf-life of the product while reducing the need for additives [73].
- ✓ High competitive pressure is forcing food companies to adopt novel processing technologies to remain competitive [67]. This problem is compelling companies to focus on improvements in production and operational efficiency, processing time and quality of food products, consequently adopting and developing new technologies capable to deliver these results [75].
- ✓ Tightening safety and environmental regulations are driving the demand for innovations in the food processing and packaging industry [73].
- ✓ Strengthening regulations and encouragement from governments on use of non-biodegradable plastic bags and packaging in general is driving the demand for biodegradable plastics [72].
- ✓ Rise in demand for hygienic food packaging that can extend shelf-life and reduce FLW [74], [75].
- ✓ Changing lifestyles are driving the demand for packaged convenience foods, which in turn is favouring the uptake of packaging that can adapt to consumers' demands [74].
- ✓ Increase in demand of eco-friendly plastic products from consumers. This will favour more sustainable options such as (bio)degradable polymers, which can break down faster than petroleum-based plastics [72].
- ✓ Enhanced interest for mobile and modular food processing innovations. Some recent examples are the development of dairy and seafood mobile processing units or a "travelling factory" built and tested by Unilever, aimed to produce liquid seasonings [65].
- ✓ Small- and medium-sized farms are searching for more profitable and sustainable practices, increasing their interest in local, regional and organic production, as well as focusing on highly valued crops. This will drive the uptake of solutions that can meet these demands [65].

- ✓ The IR spectroscopy market is driven by continuous technological improvements such as miniaturisation, automation and computerisation. These are contributing to the increased sensitivity and accuracy of the technology [76].

7.3.2 Market restraints

- ✗ The EU food and drink industry is highly fragmented with high numbers of SMEs – European food & drink companies employ an average of 17 workers [31]. This may limit the capacity to invest in new technologies.
- ✗ High costs of development of new packaging technologies may limit their adoption [73]. Raw materials also have variable costs and, depending on the supply chain, may have limited availability [73].
- ✗ Consumers' perception of a new food processing technology may hinder the adoption by the food and beverage industry, regardless of its demonstrated safety. This may be the case for irradiated foods; if the public considers them unsafe, it is unlikely that the technology will be adopted [70].
- ✗ Higher operating costs of novel food processing units, as these can have high energy consumption, labour and maintenance costs [75].
- ✗ Higher costs of biodegradable plastics compared to conventional ones, mainly due to the high polymerisation cost as the technologies are still in development and not scaled up. Current average prices for biodegradable vs conventional plastics are \$2-6/kg vs. \$1-2/kg, respectively [72].
- ✗ IR spectroscopy still poses some technical limitations, for example in the molecular structure of aqueous and complex solutions [76].
- ✗ IR spectrometers are costly and the average lifespan ranges between 5-7 years. It is possible to find used devices for resale, and this is limiting the growth of the market [76].

7.3.3 Opportunities

- ❖ Strong interest among food processing companies about processes that enhance efficiency, quality, safety and stability of food products [67].
- ❖ The creation of public-private joint undertakings can reduce the costs of developing and introducing new technologies in the market [67].
- ❖ Rise in investment opportunities for innovations in food processing technologies as a result of globalisation and trade liberalisation, opening new markets for food manufacturers [74].
- ❖ Increase in demand of food packaging in developing countries like China or India [74].
- ❖ The increased interest in sustainability among actors in the food industry will contribute towards the enhanced awareness of FLW as detrimental for sustainable food production, envisaging novel strategies and technologies intended to prevent it.

- ❖ Tightening environmental regulations aimed to prevent the environmental impact associated with packaging waste [74]. This, in turn, may be favouring the development and uptake of more sustainable packaging alternatives.
- ❖ Fast growth of the bioplastic industry in the world [72]. According to a report from [European Bioplastics](#), global production capacity in 2021 was 2.42 million tonnes, of which Europe had a share of 24.1% [77].
- ❖ Increased adoption of NIR spectrometry technologies in products quality assessment (for example seed), replacing other destructive technologies such as those based on nucleic acids or immunodiagnostics. NIR, in contrast, is non-destructive and accurate in detection of healthy and infected seeds, as well as the degree of the infection [76].

7.3.4 Challenges

- ∇ Public perception about benefits and risks of a new technology is a key element for adoption/rejection by the food industry [67].
- ∇ Some novel food processing technologies require a skilled workforce to operate them, which may limit adoption.
- ∇ High implementation and operative costs of some technologies may limit their adoption until prices are competitive.
- ∇ High requirements to adapt existing infrastructure to accommodate new processing technologies in the food industry.
- ∇ Lack of information about foods' dielectric properties can delay adoption of technologies using this material characteristic to work, such as RF [67].
- ∇ The food processing market is mature in developed regions, with highly consolidated players, limiting growth and entry for new players [74].
- ∇ Biodegradable plastics present some performance issues such as low barrier properties and resistance to heat, as well as poor mechanical properties. This is limiting the adoption for some applications [72].
- ∇ IR spectrometers are costly compared to other similar technologies such as Raman or short-wave infrared (SWIR) cameras. These high costs are due to the limited capacity to scale-up production and to R&D. However, the price is decreasing as more manufacturers enter the market, and it is forecast that the average selling price will decrease about 10% between 2017 and 2025, from approximately \$15,366 to \$13,000 [76].

7.4 Competitor Analysis

The summary of competitor offerings relevant for the ZeroW Food Processing innovations, as well as key differences and advantages of ZeroW anticipated solutions are discussed below.

7.4.1 Competitor offerings

Food processing technologies:

- **Micvac**, Sweden (<https://www.micvac.com/>). They commercialise the Micvac System, a continuous production and packaging process for ready-to-eat meals. The packaging enables in-pack cooking and pasteurisation of the meal. They have a pilot plant in Gothenburg and smaller-scale systems for home use. They claim that food processed using their system can extend shelf life up to 40-60 days.
- **Emmepiemme**, Italy (<https://www.emmepiemme-srl.com/>). Ohmic heaters manufacturers for the food industry, Applications in fruit pieces and puree, vegetables (whole or cut), creams, egg products, sauces, syrups, etc.
- **Alfa Laval**, Sweden (<https://www.alfalaval.com/>). Company commercialising industrial thermal solutions for the food industry, using different technologies, as well as custom designs and automation.
- **Hiperbaric**, Spain (<https://www.hiperbaric.com/en/>). They develop and commercialise high-pressure technologies. Hiperbaric offers solutions for processing already packed foods (HPP in-pack: H55, H135, H300, H420 and H525 systems), high volume bulk liquid foods before packaging (HPP in-bulk: H5252 BULK and H1050 BULK systems) as well as custom automated solutions.
- **JBTC**, US (<https://www.jbtc.com/>). They commercialise the Avure line of HPP systems. Some food products that can be treated by their systems are juices, meat, seafood, fruits, vegetables, salsas, salads, dairy, grains, nutraceuticals, baby food and soups.
- **Mobile fruit processor** (<https://www.appelperslerouge.be/>). Mobile apple press for the production of pasteurised apple juice in Flanders. Customers are required to bring at least 75 kg of apples to be processed. The juice is then packed in a 5-litre bag-in-box. They also offer the possibility of pressing nuts to obtain oil.
- **Fkon Consulting**, Germany (<https://www.fkon.de/en/sap-industries/sap-food-industry/>). Developing SAP technologies for applications in the food industry allowing batch management and traceability, laboratory information and management systems and specification/quality management. It allows data analytics and statistics.
- **BcFoods** from **Aptean**, US (<https://www.bcfooderp.com/>). Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) solution for the food & beverage industry built upon Microsoft Dynamics 365 Business Central. It is used to streamline processes for food processors, manufacturers and distributors.
- **Pulsemaster**, US (<https://www.pulsemaster.us/>). Pulsemaster is specialized in PEF processing and aspires to apply this innovative technology – also known as electroporation – to a broad spectrum of applications in the food industry. Not

only as a method for mild food preservation, but also as a means of improving process efficiency and product quality. They offer PEF processing for the food industry: fruit and vegetable products, potato products, meat, dairy and egg products, beer, vegetable oils, soups, fish products, sauces, dressings and marinades, baby food, algae products, seaweed and plant extracts, phytochemicals, protein concentrates, and more. US based, with global coverage, they have an office in Germany and the Netherlands.

- **Amisy Food Machine**, China (<http://www.amisyfoodmachine.com>). Supplier of food processing and packaging machines. Their product portfolio includes fruit and vegetable sorting machines (by weight), potato processors and juice machines, among others.

Commercialised packaging innovations:

- **Keep-it label**, Norway (<https://keep-it.com/>). Temperature indicator showing the remaining shelf life of the food product. The indicator is customised for each food product, including fish. The indicator is attached immediately after the fish is cut and packed. It allows to track the temperature impact on the product throughout the cold chain, providing a more dynamic and precise shelf-life than traditional expiry dates.
- **SealedAir**, US (<https://www.sealedair.com/>). Company commercialising packaging solutions such as (i) HydroLoQ barrier tray, which is recyclable and eliminates the need to use an absorbent pad in MAP by using cavities where the exudates are retained (commercialised in Australia and New Zealand); and (ii) DarFresh, an evolution of traditional MAP to vacuum skin packaging, doubling shelf-life of fresh red meat, enhancing logistic/retail efficiencies and enhancing customer experience (commercialised in the US).

Figure 40. a) HydroLoQ and b) DarFresh packaging solutions developed by *SealedAir*. (*SealedAir website, accessed 17/10/2022*).

- **Color Sensing**, Spain (<https://www.color-sensing.com/en>). Spin-off of the University of Barcelona, they commercialise FoodSensing, a freshness indicator for packaged food using smart QR codes that can be read by any camera and processed with a mobile application.

- **Ynvisible Interactive**, Canada (<https://www.ynvisible.com/>) and **Innoscentia**, Sweden (<https://www.innoscentia.com/>). Jointly developed a smart label that analyses in real-time the remaining shelf-life of a product. The labels use RFID technology to capture data in large volumes.
- **Mimica Touch**, UK (<https://www.mimicalab.com/>). Temperature-sensitive label to indicate freshness of the food product. If the product is still fresh, the label remains smooth; if it turns bumpy, the product is no longer appropriate for consumption. This solution does not require the use of a smartphone application. Current applications include juice, dairy and red meat.
- **Multivac Group**, UK (<https://uk.multivac.com/en/>). Company dedicated to commercialise food packaging and processing solutions. Their packaging solutions include thermoforming packaging, trays and film pouches.
- **Bostik**, France (<https://www.bostik.com/global/en/>). Company developing packaging and label adhesives solutions. Some of their innovative solutions includes resealable and re-closable adhesives for food packaging applications and have been authorised for contact with food (such as Bostik Food Touch H18).
- **Vesta Smart Packaging**, UK (<https://www.vestapack.com/>). Seed-stage company commercialising intelligent packaging. By using IoT, the package is capable to detect when it is running out of the (liquid) product and automatically reorder the content for a refill. This allows end users to reduce plastics.
- **Apeel**, US (<https://www.apeel.com/>). Developed a safe, edible and tasteless peel to cover fresh produce with the aim to slow down water loss and oxidation, the main reasons of spoilage in fruits. Claims to be able to double the shelf-life of avocados, limes, mandarins, apples and cucumbers.
- **Imperial College London**, UK, is testing Paper-based electrical gas sensors (PEGS). The sensor detects trace amounts of gases like ammonia and trimethylamine in meat and fish products, to calculate freshness. In addition, the information can be relayed to a customer by smartphone using NFC communication [78].
- **BlakBear**, UK (<https://blakbear.com/>). System comprised by a smart label with sensors to track freshness and associated cloud API to send data to the cloud. The company claims that it may replace shelf-life and expiry date of products.

Food quality testing innovations:

- **Viavi Solutions**, Spain (<https://www.viavisolutions.com/en-us>). They commercialised the MicroNIR PAT-Ux, a NIR process spectrometer that can be used for real-time process monitoring in different industries, including for analytical applications in food processing.

- SciO by Consumer Physics, US (<https://www.consumerphysics.com/>) is a micro-spectrometer used to test quality of grains and feed.
- Tellspec, Canada (<https://tellspec.com/>). Sensors and data analytics tools relying on AI-based cloud spectroscopy to test food products, among others, in a non-invasive, non-destructive way; one of the usages is to assess quality, ripeness and flavour of fresh fruit (FruitQC). They have also developed a mobile application, Tellspecopedia, that allows users to search ingredients/food components with the aim to assess the impact on health and make informed decisions about the food they eat. Use of Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) for traceability purposes. Received funding worth \$2.1 million.
- ImpactVision, US (<https://www.apeel.com/>). Use of hyperspectral imaging to assess quality, nutritional content, ripeness, freshness and other parameters of fresh produce so it can be graded and sorted before distribution. The company was acquired in 2021 by Apeel Sciences.

7.4.2 ZeroW Solution and key differentiating points

7.4.2.1 *Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh food products*

The closest innovations to the packaging offered by the ZeroW project are:

- Freshness sensor for fresh meat and fish developed by Imperial College London. The development is a prototype, it is uncertain whether it has been placed on the market or not. The available data shows the innovation related to the freshness indicator, however there is no information about the rest of the packaging. Thus, the ZeroW solution developed by SILL 2 is more ambitious as it includes the innovative packaging that is sustainable and smart, comprising three innovations, (i) barrier and compostable film packaging suitable for contact with food products, (ii) compartmentalized compostable tray with functionality to retain fish exudates, and (iii) freshness indicator and complementing mobile application. This holistic packaging solution have the potential to increase fresh fish shelf-life and improve stock management at the retail level of FSC.
- Keep-it technologies. They develop time temperature-indicators which work only with temperature measurements, hinting problems in the cold chain but not directly measuring food decay. The intelligent packaging developed in ZeroW can directly measure in real-time the quality of the fish it contains.
- SealedAir. They offer packaging innovations that can compete with the one proposed in this project. However, these do not include any smart or active indicators.

7.4.2.2 Mobile food valorisation as a service

The most similar solution to the one utilised by SILL 4 is Mobile fruit processor. This solution has a similar approach to treating surplus of food and vegetables like the one adopted by ZeroW proposed solution, although it is focusing mainly on apples, but can treat also other fruits and vegetables. However, the main difference when compared with ZeroW SILL 4 Mobile processing unit is in technology used.

The technologies used in the FOX Project will be downsized and integrated to fit into a container to allow mobilisation by trailer for the purpose of ZeroW project. These include low-oxygen milling and fractionation technologies such as GEA VacuIQ, HPP, PEF, etc. for fruit processing, resulting in healthy, nutrient-dense, dietary-optimized and attractive products. Commercially available mobile units use conventional juice pressing equipment (decanter, horizontal rotary press, belt press), which results in lower-quality juices. Also, preservation requires the use of higher temperatures that impact the stability of health beneficial compounds like phenolic compounds, vitamins, etc (Figure 41).

Figure 41. Comparison between conventional fruit processing units and the innovation proposed in FOX/ZeroW projects. [65]

At present most of the commercial processing units with innovations similar to those proposed by ZeroW are large, expensive and cannot be placed in a mobile setting, leaving them out of reach for use by small- and medium-sized farms due to transport costs, seasonality, etc. In this case it may be simpler for potential customers to just derive their surplus/sub-optimal produce to other lower-value uses or discard it. ZeroW's solution will bring the processing unit to their door, simplifying the process and reducing costs, while contributing to reduce FLW. They will not need to make significant investments as the unit will be offered as a service. Previous studies have shown that the FOX system is 20% more environmentally friendly than similar small-scale stationary juice processing units (for apples), mainly

because of the increased extraction yield compared with conventional stationary processors [65].

7.4.2.3 Ugly food early identification, shelf-life assessment and alternative valorisation

NIR spectroscopy, which covers approximately 780 to 2500 nm, has many applications in quality assessment in the fruit and vegetable processing industry. This technique allows to assess soluble solids and water contents, stiffness or presence of internal damage, among other parameters. However, technology developed in the ZeroW project incorporates [SpinSort](#) technology, combining innovative vision and transport systems to detect quality, colour, size and shape problems more efficiently. This technology, developed by SILL 5 Partner MST and [unique in the world](#), makes it possible to maximise the inspected surface area of the fruit by rotating it completely, for an [integral 360° analysis](#); this is a [differential value](#) compared to other sorting and grading systems that ensures high efficiency in obtaining quality products. The incorporation of a sensor providing real-time, non-destructive on-line information on misclassified organic/non-organic batches is also assessed as a part of SILL 5 solution. The sensor consists of a compact quadrupole mass spectrometer with membrane inlet probe and patented vacuum chamber capable of detecting unauthorised pesticide or non-organic fertiliser use at ppt (parts per trillion) accuracies.

The data service platform has also significant differences compared with the current state-of-the-art. The ZeroW proposed solution is more focused on physical integrity to identify the key features found in “ugly food” products. Additionally, it is oriented towards recovery practices to prevent FLW, as well as the improvement of storage and logistics management.

7.4.2.4 Advanced data-driven production process control and optimisation

The closest portable NIR spectroscopy solutions available on the market (Tellspec, MicroNIR and SciO) use proprietary software and calibration algorithms, which do not allow for customisation. The calibration process, necessary to implement in order to adopt the use of portable spectroscope for a new food product has to be done through the proprietary company.

The solution proposed by SILL 6 will use open-source software (for example R and Python). The calibration will use cutting-edge machine learning techniques such as ANNs, Random Forest, (Stochastic) Gradient Boosting, etc., which goes beyond the common linear mathematical models used for calibrations by the competition.

7.5 PESTLE Analysis

A high-level PESTLE analysis is performed to support the initial market assessment, helping to understand contemporary market environment around food processing

innovation market, and position ZeroW anticipated outcomes in it. In the following sections, Political Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors impacting the SILL 2, SILL 4, SILL 5 and SILL 6 outcomes target markets are discussed.

7.5.1 Political factors

- The [European Food Safety Authority \(EFSA\)](#) is the independent agency set up in 2002 as a consequence of a number of food crises in the 90s. Its objective is to provide scientific advice on risks associated with the food supply chain. All the new food products and materials that get in contact with foods (such as for the food packaging) have to obtain approval from EFSA.
- The [Global Protocol on Packaging Sustainability \(GPPS\)](#), launched in September 2011, provides common principles and metrics in packaging in the context of sustainability to address environmental, economic and social impacts.
- Australia's [national science agency and innovation catalyst \(CSIRO\)](#) provide food processing expertise and facilities for new technologies. As example, they started research on HPP processing in 2001. They act as incubator for SMEs worldwide with an interest in installing and operating HPP facilities at commercial scale. Their benefits were valued at \$356.4 million in 2018.
- FLW policies should be in line with other food policy initiatives like the climate action, packaging, etc [30].
- The [Upcycled Food Association](#) have developed standards and certifications for upcycled foods and ingredients, which aim to increase public awareness and transparency for these products. Additionally, as upcycling enables the reintroduction in the FSC of food products that would have likely been discarded, it should be included in the food waste management hierarchy (Section 8.2.2.5) to urge policymaking and acceptability [69].
- The [Juice CSR Platform](#) is a sustainability initiative cofounded by the [European Fruit Juice Association \(AIJN\)](#) and [Sociability](#) with aim to provide a space for collaboration specially intended for the fruit juice industry. Its aim is to integrate social, environmental and ethical aspects of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in the industry, from production in the farm, through processing into juice and packaging to the final consumer.

7.5.2 Economic factors

- The European food & drink industry had a turnover of €1,205 billion with an added value of €246 billion in 2017. This market is highly diverse and fragmented, with a high number of SMEs; there are almost 290,000 companies in the sector, of which 99.2% are SMEs [31]. There are few very large companies (employing 250 or more persons), with significant market reach, accounting for 55.8% of the total value added in the food processing industry [66]. The high prevalence of small- and medium-sized companies is limiting investing capacity;

these companies will favour technologies that offer short-term, measurable benefits with faster ROIs.

- Prevention of FLW is encouraged through accreditation schemes, voluntary programmes (Champions 12.3, FAO's [Voluntary Code of Conduct for Food Loss and Waste Reduction](#), etc), and deployment of digital solutions.
- Packaging usage/consumption in the EU has decoupled from that of the gross domestic product (GDP) in recent years: packaging consumption/usage has increased by 10% while its waste decreased by 43%, compared to a 40% GDP growth between 1998 and 2008, showing progress towards sustainability and recycling [79].

7.5.3 Social factors

- The food industry is in general associated with high levels of failure of new products [80]. The adoption of new technologies in the food & beverage industry greatly depends on the consumers' acceptance and awareness of the benefits it brings, in terms of health and how the food is produced, even when they do not have a solid knowledge about the technology [67]. The same applies for packaging: decisions taken by food packaging companies are highly dependent on consumers' lifestyles and preferences, which are constantly evolving, determining which innovations will be successful [79].
- As upcycled foods use new processing technologies that may not be well known by consumers, food neophobia and technophobia may negatively affect acceptability [69]. Other factors influencing acceptance are demographics such as gender (women are less prone to accept them), education level and income (which have a direct correlation with acceptability); however, age does not seem to influence it [69]. These products can be healthier than conventional ones (higher content of proteins, antioxidants and fibre and lower glycaemic index) [69]. To improve acceptability of upcycled foods and ingredients, continuous communication on their advantages is key to gaining trust [69].
- Consumers are more aware of the environmental impact of the food packaging than that of food waste; thus, they may choose a food with environmentally friendly packages even though this may lead to higher levels of food waste. Additionally, the size of the packaging is often a problem for consumers as they feel portions are too large for their needs, and some of them are willing to pay slightly more for a smaller portioned package [71].

7.5.4 Technological factors

- The food processing industry is an early adopter of robotic technologies, where these are already extensively deployed to automate tasks [33]. There are currently 30,000 robots applied in the food and drink industry in Europe (45%

of which are located in Germany and Italy) with a 52% increase in sales between 2013-2017 [31].

- The current technological status of novel food processing technologies, including those employed by ZeroW SILLs, is listed below. In general, most of them are starting to be applied at commercial scale (TRL 8).
 - RF heating. This technology can potentially replace other technologies, such as microwave, in the industry. To achieve this, it is paramount to determine optimum RF frequencies required by a particular food or group of foods. Different food products may require different RF units [81]. Most commercial applications of RF relate to post-bake processing for cookies/biscuits and thawing/tempering of frozen food products. Other applications (disinfestation, pasteurisation/sterilisation, food drying, vegetable blanching) are still on research stage/pilot scale due to the high complexity of food composition [82].
 - Ohmic heating. This is still being studied as an alternative to conventional heating methods for food processing, with some commercial applications available (TRL 8 to TRL 9). Some drawbacks are still preventing the widespread implementation of the technology at industrial scale: electrochemical corrosion of the electrodes, presence of pathogenic bacteria in food with high content of fat granules, and high installation costs. It can be used in combination with other heating techniques to improve efficiency. Lower limitations than other processing innovations for scaleup can result in higher adoption levels at industrial scale. This will be possible given good monitoring, cleaning and maintenance to prevent electrode corrosion [83].
 - Ultrasound. This is a relatively new technology. For pasteurising applications, ultrasound is at TRL 8 with some commercial systems available, while for drying applications, the technology is at TRL 7. It still presents several disadvantages such as generation of free radicals, degradation of certain components, discolouration and off-flavours in treated foods. For this reason, the system needs to be tested to refine specific parameters for new food applications [84].
 - UV & PL. New technology with some commercial applications (TRL 8), especially for surface sterilisation of tools and equipment in the food industry. UV light has been recently used for pasteurisation of dairy products [84].
 - HHP. This technology is already widespread in the food industry with over 350 commercial systems deployed worldwide, with a processing capacity of over 1 billion tons of food every year (TRL 9), with applications in

sterilisation/pasteurisation [67]. Despite this, the costs of installation are still high, but these are expected to fall as the demand grows [84].

- PEF. Novel technology that already has some industrial applications, mainly for preserving liquid foods (TRL 8). The application requires the adjustment of many operation parameters: each new application requires testing and monitoring. It requires staff with good technical and scientific skills to operate it. PEF can be combined with ultrasound in some cases (i.e.: EU funded project SMARTMILK [84]).
- The incorporation of upcycled ingredients into a food product modifies its fundamental quality parameters (appearance, colour, texture, etc.) in a way that can be difficult to improve. This might have to be clearly indicated in food products containing upcycled ingredients. Adding carbon footprint labels (such as the ones from the [Carbon Trust](#)) may improve acceptability even when the fundamental parameters are affected [69].
- The packaging value chain is very complex, as decisions taken in one of the levels can affect other stages downstream of it. For example, the choice of a material for packaging can affect the end-of-life options once the product is consumed. Decisions must be taken for each case and taking into consideration all stages of the value chain. There are six areas to consider to determine the optimal packaging technology: material, design, production costs, consumer choice, use and end of life [79]. Current technological trends in the packaging industry include entirely recyclable packaging, application of innovations such as of augmented reality and cloud labelling in smart packaging, and edible packaging [85].

7.5.5 Legal factors

Food processing:

- [Regulation EC 178/2002](#) on general principles and requirements of food law (General Food Law Regulation). It lays down the principles, requirements and procedures required to ensure food and feed safety, and sets up an independent agency, EFSA, to oversee it.
- [Regulation \(EU\) 1169/2011](#) on provision of food information to consumers (FIC regulation), which sets the labelling requirements of food products. It includes a revision in the rules on date marking (“use by” and “best before”), whose inclusion is mandatory in food products. These vary greatly across the EU and are a cause of confusion for many consumers, and it is associated with around 10% of wasted food [86]. It is unlikely that intelligent labels will replace the requirement of date marking; however, they can improve accuracy about freshness, helping consumers decide and reducing FLW.

Food packaging:

- [Regulation EC 450/2009](#) on active and intelligent materials and articles intended to come into contact with food. This regulation establishes a pre-market approval system where active and/or intelligent materials cannot be commercialised unless the substances responsible for their function are included in the EC list of eligible substances. It should be noted that packaging, as well as active and/or intelligent substances must be accompanied by a written declaration of compliance at each stage of marketing.
- [Regulation EC 1935/2004](#) on Food Contact Materials (FCMs). The regulation requires that FCMs are not permitted to: 1) release constituents into food at harmful levels for humans; and 2) change food composition, taste and odour in unacceptable ways. It was amended in 2019 by Regulation (EU) 2019/1381 on transparency and sustainability of the EU risk assessment in the food chain, also called the Transparency Regulation.
- [Regulation EC 2023/2006](#) on Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) for materials and articles intended to come into contact with food. These rules apply to all stages, from manufacturing to distribution.
- [Regulation EC 10/2011](#) on plastic materials for food contact. This lays down the requirements for safety assessment of plastic monomers, starting substances and additives before use in manufacturing. The safety assessment considers the substance, relevant impurities and reaction/degradation products in the intended use. It does not cover the colourants used to dye the plastics, which remains subject to national laws.
- [Directive 94/62/EC](#) on packaging and packaging waste (PPWD) (December 1994) and amending Directives 2004/12/EC and 2013/2/EU. In December 2015, changes were proposed to harmonise it with the Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC (WFD), as part of the Circular Economy Strategy. The main objective of the PPWD is the reduction of the environmental impact of packaging waste. Additionally, this Directive appointed the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN) to create a series of standards; packages that are compliant with these are granted free circulation in the EU Economic Area [87].
- There is no specific regulation covering the inks that form part of the freshness indicator label. Compliance is achieved through the guidance provided by the following: Annex 10 of the Swiss Ordinance and applicable documents issued by the [European Printing Ink Association \(EuPIA\)](#).

Other regulations:

- [Regulation \(EU\) 1301/2013](#) on provisions concerning the Investment for growth and jobs goal, repealing regulation (EC) 1080/2006. This regulation sets the provisions common to the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), which intends to reduce imbalances between development between EU regions.
- [Regulation \(EU\) 1308/2013](#), which is establishing a common organisation of the markets in agricultural products and repealing Regulation (EC) 1234/2007. This is part of the reform of the main instruments of the CAP after 2013.

- Region-specific regulations affecting the uptake of ZeroW's proposed innovations under SILL 5, in Spain:
 - Reform Law 8/1984 of 3 July 1984 on Agrarian Law.
 - Law 1/1996 of 10 January 1996 on Internal Commerce in Andalusia.
 - Law 19/1995 of 4 July 1995 on the modernisation of agricultural exploitations.
 - Law 2/2011, of 25 March, on Agri-food and Fisheries Quality in Andalusia.
 - Law 8/2018, of 8 October, on measures against climate change and for the transition to a new energy model in Andalusia.

7.5.6 Environmental factors

- In the fruit processing industry, extraction yields are key aspects when determining the environmental impact of the production system used [65]. According to consumers' perceptions, an increased sustainability is linked with regionality and a decentralised production system. However, this may not necessarily be the case due to economies of scale, by which large-scale systems are often more sustainable due to more efficient transport and processing methods [65].
- There is a lack of research studies on the environmental impact of innovative technologies such as low-oxygen extraction and PEF applied to juice production, as well as for other applications/products [65].
- Food upcycling is a new concept that aims to reduce FLW by reintroducing these products back in the human food supply chain. It can be expected that this solution has a better environmental impact than other food waste management options, such as landfilling or incineration. However, LCA studies should be performed to objectively assess this [69].
- Packaging is often seen as a source of waste and environmental impact; however, it is key to ensure the quality of the contained food and thus, to reduce FLW. It is estimated that the food production process has up to ten times more environmental impact than that of the packaging itself. An optimum amount of packaging must be reached in order to obtain maximum sustainability while reducing FLW: in this context, under-packing has a greater environmental impact (in terms of more FLW generated) than overpacking (Figure 42) [79].
- The supply chain needs to reach a balance between safety and environment; in case of conflict between these two, health should take precedence [79]. Due to the complexity of the packaging value chain, sustainability issues must be addressed for each particular case [79].

Figure 42. Relationship between food packaging and waste in terms of environmental impact. [79]

7.6 Barriers to entry

Some of the barriers that innovations in the food processing sector may face when entering the market are listed here; the list includes the common barriers to entry, but also solution/SILL specific barriers that might impede the solution market placement.

- The implementation of novel food processing technologies into operative facilities often disrupt the production process, which may limit adoption [84].
- Strict regulatory requirements may delay market entry for novel food processing techniques and packaging materials.
- The food processing and packaging market is highly consolidated and new market entrants may require large capital investments. This may be difficult to achieve for SMEs [74].
- Consumers' lack of trust and reluctance to accept new technologies/processes can affect the market uptake of new foods, which may limit adoption by the food processing industry, as it is highly influenced by consumers.

Specific barriers associated to SILL 2 (innovative packaging for fresh salmon):

- Consumer acceptance of new sustainable materials may be limited. To overcome this barrier, current efforts are intended to ensure safety and use for food contact, in compliance with current regulations (Section 7.5.5).
- Low awareness about the advantages in the use of freshness indicators among end users at retail/wholesale/distribution stages of FSC. This will be mitigated by disseminating the advantages/benefits of smart packaging for end users.
- End-of-life management of packaging materials is complex. Separation of individual elements is required but it is not clear who should do it (consumers, waste operators, etc). This problem is aggravated when the food is not consumed before disposing it and the constituents of the package cannot be easily separated.

- Economic/Funding barriers: Higher-than-expected costs of development due to different variables intrinsic to the nature of the packaging such as: high costs of the biobased polymers; the increased cost for including the freshness label; and the associated costs to the processability for the novel materials. To overcome this barrier, the solution has to offer a good balance between costs and perceived benefits in terms of sustainability, FLW reduction and, ultimately, demonstrable cost savings by avoiding penalties/fines set in different countries to meet the objectives set by the EU Green Deal.
- Technical issues related to availability of materials, compatibility between the tray lid and the coated film (which will be thermoformed) and different logistic requirements for the new packaging design.
- Network effects: the value/utility of the solution will depend on the number of users.
- Issues gaining customers' acceptance. Unfamiliar product, new methodologies, solution too complex to understand by end users.
- Regulatory requirements. The label acting as freshness indicator developed by ITENE must comply with Regulation (EC) 450/2009 and be authorised for use as intelligent material. In case the components or substances used for making this label are not listed, an application must be submitted for the safety evaluation of the active or intelligent material by the EFSA.

Specific barriers associated to SILL 4 (mobile processing unit):

- The parking/placing requirements of the mobile processing unit may limit use. These are related to:
 - Container location conditions: large levelled parking area (approximately 16x6m) so the container can be kept completely horizontal; load capacity of minimum 15 tons; the subsoil must be composed of compacted gravel, sealed with paving stones or asphalt; access availability for delivery/collection; and access to power and water supply as well as sewage collection system.
 - Access roads: these have to be suitable for heavy transport vehicles (40 tons) and the loading area has to be compacted to permit a truck-mounted crane to unload the container (weighted around 5 tons).
- Low awareness of end users: New technology and service which may not be well known to primary producers, as one of the main customers. They may not be aware of the risks and benefits the new technology poses for them.
- Costs: If the price of the services is higher than deriving the produce to other uses (such as animal feed or composting), it is unlikely the new solution/service will be accepted.

Specific barriers associated to SILL 5 (“ugly food” identification):

- Technology concerns causing a need to optimise the proposed system to address the large demand/urgent requirement of the product.
- Costs can be limiting the adoption of the technology: this is a highly competitive market with a great number of clients, who may be initially reluctant to invest in innovative solutions.
- Barriers associated to the seasonality and the logistics of greenhouse cultivations. This is additionally emphasised by geographical distribution of the competitors (mainly located in Italy and the Netherlands) .
- High specificity of the technology, which has to be adapted for each type of fruit or vegetable. This could affect the price and the space requirements if a different system is needed for each product.

Specific barriers linked to SILL 6 (algorithm for optimisation of food processing lines):

- Final price of the solution. The food processing industry is comprised mostly by SMEs (>99%) [31] and their investment capacity is generally low; they require short-term, tangible benefits and short ROIs.
- Low digital skills of food operators may limit the adoption of the technology. Adequate training and including the end-users in co-designing the user interface will be required to overcome this barrier.
- A foreseen technical barrier can be the optimal integration with other main IT components such as Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) and Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES), avoiding the generation of IT silos.

7.7 ZeroW Food Processing Innovations Market Summary

In general, the main drivers governing food processing market comprise increased focus on enhancing production efficiency, optimised processes in terms of time, yield and environmental impact, and increased quality of produced food, while implementing practices to prevent, reduce and valorise FLW produced. Additionally, competitive landscape and expansion of new products reinforcing sustainability goals offers lucrative market opportunities for new processing technologies, with the special focus on digital transformation of food systems, and implementation of technologies that foster integration and interoperability among different IT systems. Novel food products supporting the [Sustainable food consumption](#) agenda and facilitating the shift towards healthy, sustainable diets are increasingly sought in the market. Summary of market dynamics associated to the ZeroW solutions proposed under Food Processing Innovations cluster are summarised in Figure 43.

<p>DRIVERS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urgent need for more resilient food systems including better preservation of food products. • Tightening safety and environmental regulations in the food industry. • Higher quality requirements for food among consumers.
<p>RESTRAINTS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The EU food and drink industry is highly fragmented with high numbers of SMEs; this may limit their capacity to invest in new technologies. • Consumers' perception of a new technologies may hinder adoption by the food industry.
<p>OPPORTUNITIES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The creation of public-private joint undertakings can reduce the costs of developing and introducing new technologies in the food industry. • Increased interest in sustainability will contribute towards the enhanced awareness of FLW and development of the solutions to prevent it.
<p>CHALLENGES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public perception about benefits and risks of a new technology is a key element for adoption/rejection by the food industry. • Novel food processing technologies require a skilled workforce. • Possible high implementation and operative costs may render new technologies uncompetitive.

Figure 43. Summary of market dynamics for cluster 3.

Narrowing down to the ZeroW proposed solutions, innovative, sustainable and smart packaging for fresh fish developed by SILL 2 brings the competitive holistic solution with the potential to increase fresh fish shelf-life and improve stock management at the retail level. Deployment of smart sensors as integral part of proposes solution distinguishes ZeroW innovation, as it provides real-time data for monitoring both shelf-life and quality of packed product. The mobile processing unit tested by SILL 4 and anticipated to be offered as a service empowers small- and medium-sized farms to utilise the product surplus; often these were not able to avail of the currently available commercial processing units, as they are large, expensive and in most cases stationary. SILL 5 designed solution promotes efficient control of produce quality, colour, size and shape, detecting eventual issues early. Additionally, inclusion of state-of-the-art sensors enables real-time, non-destructive on-line information on organic/non-organic product batches, preventing the FLW occurring due to misclassification and allowing for timely recovery practices. Finally, advanced algorithms for control and optimisation of the production processes will be developed by SILL6, offering non-destructive technology for determination of food quality parameters and subsequent optimisation of intermediate processing steps in fresh meat production.

All food related innovations, but especially those affecting the common food products directly, be it through the novel ways of processing or the novel final products, face an impediment imposed by consumers acceptance of novelty. This might refer to food neophobia (i.e. fear of anything new or unfamiliar), but also food technophobia (i.e. fear of advanced technology), and might include how food is produced as well as what ingredients are used. Consumers might not necessarily have the knowledge to understand the innovations introduced, hence hinder

market and commercial success of developed innovations. Informing, educating and nudging consumer towards more sustainable choices is crucial to overcome this, which is part of ZeroW systemic approach to zero FSC and addressed in ZeroW SILL 9 (detailed in Chapter 8). Another important barrier for adoption is related to the size of the companies that comprise the European food processing industry; these are mostly SMEs that may not have the necessary capital to invest in novel technologies as the ones proposed in the project. Incentives through governmental support may be required for these companies to benefit from the project's outcomes.

8 ZeroW Wholesale, Retail and Consumer Innovations

According to the FAO “Food waste is the result of purchasing decisions by consumers, or decisions by retailers and food service providers that affect consumer behaviour.” [43] As such, the innovations presented under this section are directly intended to address the food wasted by retailers, foodservices and consumers. In addition, an overview of current alternatives to minimise the negative impacts of wasted food is provided, as it is not possible to reach zero FLW and better solutions other than landfilling are necessary to tackle unavoidable waste.

8.1 ZeroW's proposed innovations

Three SILLs are directly involved in providing innovative solutions at retail and consumer levels:

- Food waste reduction through efficient food bank networks (SILL 7);
- Retail food waste valorisation through algae production for high-value applications (SILL 8);
- “Fork to Farm to Fork” (3F): Informing and nudging consumers to make better choices through reverse (dietetics) and forward (FLW, sustainability, affordability) optimisation (SILL 9).

8.1.1 SILL 7 – Food waste reduction through efficient food bank networks

Food waste is related to food insecurity; these two problems are addressed in many countries by food banks. However, food banks are often non-profit organisations run by volunteers. They rely heavily on donations for their food supplies. As retailers are increasingly focusing on limiting their food waste; consequently reducing their donations to food banks, which need to find alternative sources of food. However, sourcing food upstream the supply chain (primary producers, processing companies) is complex because it is often necessary to repack the products in easy-to-donate packages. To overcome these issues, this SILL will output:

- Supply and demand prediction tools to forecast the expected number of food bank customers, as well as FSC management and optimisation to predict the supply. These tools will use big data analytics;
- Handbook of food waste reduction strategies available for food banks;
- Decision support tool for waste reduction initiatives at food banks;
- Donation tool for donors on products that are ready for donation.

8.1.2 SILL 8 – Retail food waste valorisation through algae production for high-value applications

This SILL aims to address the food waste (FW) generated at warehouse and retail level, when all other FLW reduction strategies are exhausted and FW is created even after markdowns or donations to foodbanks. The main FW sources are fruits and vegetables and animal proteins that could be valorised following a circular economy approach. This SILL will address warehouse and retail FW by using the wasted food as feedstock to grow microalgae, with the following outputs:

- In-store food waste pre-treatment process;
- Hermetic container for transportation of the FLW in reverse logistics;
- Optimisation of the FLW logistics.

The microalgal biomass produced will be further utilised in different industries such as cosmetics and the sustainable packaging industry.

8.1.3 SILL 9 – Fork to Farm to Fork (3F)

SILL 9 aims to empower consumers to make fully informed decision based on all relevant aspects of food products such as FLW-impact, health, environmental impact and affordability. To foster this, SILL 9 will output:

- FLW labels for meals, meal packages, recipes, etc. showing impact on FLW of non-consumed food, and on other environmental factors and information on best practices for storage;
- A mobile application to obtain the scores of consumers' own recipes/diets.
- New recipes, fresh meal kits and semi-prepared packs of ingredients (such as pre-cut vegetables) with low impacts on FLW and the environment, with high nutri-score.

8.2 Market Overview

8.2.1 FLW at wholesale, retail and consumer stages

Globally, the retail and consumer levels of the FSC were responsible for 931 million tons of food waste (17% of food production) in 2019. Of these, the largest share corresponded to households (61%), followed by food services (26%) and retail (13%) [88]. Despite this, there is a lack of research into the causes and potential solutions

when compared with upstream phases. This happens because measuring wasted food at this stage is challenging and may lead to inaccuracies/underestimations. As a consequence, it is difficult to assess progress towards the set goals on food waste reduction [88]. Some of the issues are:

- Lack of enough data to measure the scale of the problem. When data is available, it is often old and lacks accuracy [88].
- Lack of a common methodology to measure food waste. The methods used are highly variable between countries and comparisons are difficult to make. A common methodology, shared between countries, is needed [88].
- Lack of sufficient data points to measure food waste at this stage of the supply chain, especially in medium- and lower-income countries [88].
- Different definitions of food loss and waste given in different countries and between policymakers and actors in the supply chain are exacerbating the issue of data variability [88].
- Not enough tools to adequately track food waste.
- In most definitions of food waste there is no differentiation between edible and non-edible wasted food. This limits the ability of stakeholders and policymakers to determine where the problems arise and hinder their ability to envision solutions. Separating these would help determine the balance of policies focusing on prevention of food waste (for edible parts), or on favouring circular uses (for non-edible/less eaten parts).
- The differentiation in the definition of food loss and food waste (when available) may lead to an underestimation of the scale of the problem [89]. For example, food that exits the human FSC at upper stages is considered food loss and not waste by stakeholders in the food supply chain [46], [88]. This hampers efforts to tackle the problem at those levels [88].
- It is considered that food waste at household stage is the result of a balance between consumers, producers/retailers, regulations and available technology. Spikes in demand, such as the one generated during the COVID-19 pandemic, may result in an increase of FLW. A retailing system optimised to prevent as much as food waste as possible (i.e. by limiting the amounts of food kept in supermarkets) is not well suited to respond to these situations; as a consequence of the pandemic, in the future such optimisations may be discouraged, increasing generation of FLW [90].
- Food wasted at household level has higher environmental impact as it is more probable for it to end up in landfills than other levels upstream the supply chain, which is one of the worst possible outcomes [90]. Additionally, at this point it has accumulated the impacts caused at previous stages of the FSC.

8.2.2 Existing solutions

8.2.2.1 Applications for food waste monitoring and management

These tools are aimed for retailers and food services (hospitality, restaurants, catering, etc) with the aim to assess the value of food wasted and elaborate strategies to minimise, recover or revalorise it, while raising awareness among end users.

Digital tools for food waste management offer:

- Integration between the waste disposal unit and data collection, as well as allowing connectivity to the network for online storage/analytics [91].
- Device to measure the weight/volume of food waste in the disposal unit [91].
- Data reporting capabilities to help stakeholders devise preventive strategies [91].

8.2.2.2 Dynamic pricing according to approaching expiry date

This solution is suitable for retailers and is addressing the issue of consumers not wanting to pay full price for a product that is nearing its expiry/display-until date. Marking down products that are nearing their expiry date is largely made manually by employees. Emerging technologies could make the process automatic, reducing burdens. The main limitation is the requirement of each item to be labelled individually, increasing investment/costs and limiting use (i.e.: it cannot be applied for highly perishable bulk products). The **ReFED**, a US non-profit organisation demonstrated that despite its high investment costs, data-driven solutions, such as automated dynamic pricing technologies to reduce FW could double retailer revenue [92]. However, while these types of solution may be reducing levels of FW at retail stage, it may be increasing it at consumer level when they buy products closer to their use-by date.

8.2.2.3 Food management solutions for households

Storage management. Consumers are often unaware of the best ways to store food products to prevent spoilage and subsequent food waste, especially in regards to fruits and vegetables. Better storage can be achieved by either including storage advice in the label/packaging, or by the development of digital applications for stock management. For correct conservation of certain food products, refrigeration and freezing are important to reduce household food waste. However, the location in the fridge where the food is placed can influence its final destination (i.e.: visibility is key for consumers not to forget about leftovers) [71].

Smart fridges. These aim to reduce waste by increasing the users' awareness of the food that the refrigerator is containing and when the contained food is about to expire. These are already being commercialised by companies such as Samsung, LG,

Siemens, etc. Some of them, such as the ones commercialised by Samsung, have built-in cameras that allow users to see the contents in the fridge, while others like those commercialised by Bosch, use sensors to automatically adjust optimum temperature, humidity and air circulation to prolong shelf-life of fresh produce. Freshness boosters, ethylene absorbers to prolong life of produce, can also be applied to conventional fridges to improve conservation capabilities.

8.2.2.4 Redistribution of surplus food

Redistribution of excess food can occur at all levels of the supply chain, from production to consumer stage. According to a study published by Wageningen University and ECORYS, foodbank members of the European Food Banks Federation (FEBA) distributed 501,000 tons of food to 6.6 million people in 2017. 16,200 people were involved, of which 86% were volunteers [93].

8.2.2.5 Alternative uses of food waste (recovery, reuse and recycling)

Food waste is often the result of interlinked conditions at different stages of the supply chain; as such, solutions covering several levels or even the totality of the chain are of special interest when addressing the problem [94]. Once food is wasted, there are several options to dispose of it; incineration (with or without energy recovery) or sending it to a landfill are the most common, but less preferable strategies (an estimated ≈ 1.3 billion tons of food waste end up in landfills every year globally [95]).

Recycling includes solutions to obtain other products of low value (biogases, compost, etc) or high value (components for cosmetics, nutraceuticals, etc). To be able to revalorise it, the food waste has to be homogeneous and in sufficient quantities; for these reasons they are normally applied for FLW generated at processing stage [96]. To enable recycling of food lost or wasted, the first step is to separate it from other wastes and collect it; how this is achieved can be challenging depending on the stage where the FLW is generated. Some EU Member States have implemented policies and collection systems to encourage its separation (Section 8.5.2 – Economic factors) [94].

An alternative management solution for FLW is the **biorefinery**, a process where food waste is used as a feedstock to obtain other high- and medium-valued materials. Biorefinery processes can be biological (use of enzymes/microorganisms), thermochemical (combination of high temperature and chemicals), and chemical (where a chemical is used as a solvent) [97]. The products obtained vary with the process and the type of food waste that is used as feedstock.

Biological treatments:

- Anaerobic digestion. Use of microorganisms to produce methane gas. It is used to treat organic waste with high moisture, and usually produce biogas (methane) and digestate as solid residue; the latter can be either disposed of on a landfill or be used as fertiliser [98]. The process comprises of four steps: hydrolysis, acidogenesis, acetogenesis and methanogenesis. These occur either sequentially or in a single stage [97]. Food waste is highly heterogeneous and this can affect the degradability, making it difficult to calculate its potential as substrate for the process [99]. A pre-treatment step is required to improve the yield. Some of the pre-treating options that have been researched are microwave, chemical treatment with HCl, heating, freezing/thawing and application of high pressures [99].
- Dark fermentation. Use of anaerobic bacteria in dark conditions to obtain hydrogen from food waste. This process is still in early stages of development and it is facing difficulties for industrial scale-up due to high production costs and low yields. Metabolic engineering (modification of the cellular metabolism of the microorganisms used in the process to produce the desired components) could help solve these problems [97].
- Electro-fermentation. Combination of fermentation with electro-microbiology, which takes advantage of the electrical properties of some microorganisms to produce hydrogen from organic waste. Two species of bacteria, *Geobacter sulfurreducens* and *Shewanella oneidensis*, are the most investigated. Its application for food waste valorisation is very recent and further studies are required before scaleup [97].
- Photo-fermentation. It uses light as additional energy source for photosynthetic bacteria, which produce CO₂ and hydrogen. This technology has great potential to treat wastewater from dairy production, breweries and sugar refining. This technology is more cost-efficient in hydrogen production than electrolysis (€2.83/kg H₂ vs. €4-24/kg H₂, respectively) [97].
- Composting. Process using microorganisms to aerobically degrade complex organic matter, including food waste, to simpler components that form compost, which is then used as biofertilizer. Composting can be done using one feedstock or a combination of them (co-composting). The process is time consuming, but it can be reduced by using biochar generated by pyrolysis of agricultural/faecal wastes. Main drawbacks of composting are the generation of GHG and strong odours, which may limit its implementation; however, several processes can reduce the emissions such as biofiltration, addition of lime or the reduction of ammonia in the compost [100].
- Growth of microalgae (heterotrophically) and insects. Food waste can be used as a substrate to grow these organisms. The biomass can then be used as food,

feed or as feedstock to obtain biobased products. The nutritional profiles of microalgae and insects are similar; however, microalgae naturally synthesize some essential poly-unsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) such as omega-3 fatty acids, while insects cannot (these should be provided in the diet) [101]. While there is potential for use of these organisms for recycling food waste and other organic matter, its market penetration can be limited due to health and safety concerns and limited public acceptance [101], as well as subject to regulatory approvals.

Thermochemical treatments. These are limited to food and other organic wastes with low water content. The resulting products vary depending on the process:

- Incineration (with or without energy recovery). The efficiency of the process will be determined by the moisture content of the feedstock; to improve it, a pre-treatment to dry the biomass may be required [98], [102].
- Pyrolysis. Two processes are differentiated: slow (or conventional) pyrolysis consists in the application of temperatures ranging 400-500°C during 5-30 minutes; or fast pyrolysis, involving temperatures of 800-1,300°C for 1-10 seconds. The yields of these two processes differ: slow pyrolysis produces higher rates of biochar while fast pyrolysis yields predominantly biofuels (60-75%) and, to a lesser extent, biochar (15-20%) and gaseous products (10-20%). Pyrolysis has been applied for treatment of single components, mainly to treat wastes from the food processing industry. It offers several advantages compared to biochemical treatments and other thermochemical processes, such as low processing times, less infrastructure requirements and low feedstock specificity. The resulting biochar can be used to improve the conditions of the soil or further processed into other high value-added products (activated carbon) [102].
- Gasification. Process involving high temperatures (700-900°C) and reaction of gases (such as CO₂, steam, nitrogen or a combination of them) with carbon contents of the food waste. Obtention of bio-syngas, a mixture of CO, CO₂ and nitrogen and residues (chars, ash, oils and tars) [102].

The food waste hierarchy, adopted for the [revised Waste Framework Directive](#) aims to prioritise waste management solutions with better economic, social and environmental outcomes (Figure 44).

Figure 44. Hierarchy for prioritisation of food surplus, by-products and FW prevention strategies. [103]

Due to the heterogeneous nature of FLW and the numerous stakeholders involved at different stages of the FSC, the hierarchy needs to be assessed for each type of food waste [103]. To support this, researchers have created the Food Waste Management Decision Tree (FWMDT), a collection of flowcharts to help assess each case-specific application of the waste hierarchy and conclude on the best food waste management alternatives for each food type [103].

8.2.3 Market size

SILL 7 is focusing mainly on producing the support tools to help the food banks reduce the FW and optimise their processes. Hence, solutions developed will most likely be exploited by other means and not commercialised. For this reason, market data for these solutions is not included in this section, while factors affecting exploitation are discussed in the following sections.

SILL 8 is developing a solution that could potentially be commercialised, related to an hermetic container and a reverse logistics operation to use FW as feedstock for microalgal cultivation. The technology to pre-treat the FW is already commercialised (<https://www.foodwasteinc.com/products/gc-400/>) and will be utilised as such. The biomass obtained will then be used to grow microalgae and produce high added value compounds with potential applications in the cosmetics or bioplastics industries. The use of FW as growth substrate for microalgae is a relatively new concept; as such, the specific market for a solution like the one proposed in the ZeroW is not there yet, but it is expected that the innovation will create an opportunity to establish new market segments. Although the validation of the solution proposed by SILL 8 will rely on the successful growth of microalgae, the innovation centres on previous steps, related to the way the FW is managed and valorised at retail level; for this reason, the market analysis focuses on the food

waste management market and not on algae/microalgae, as this market is considered to be out of primary focus.

One of the SILL 9 solutions will target designing meal kits that can potentially be sold at retail/foodservice level. These will contain healthy recipes and the ingredients required to cook them, in the quantities that are necessary to prevent FLW. Other possible solution developed by this SILL will most likely follow alternative exploitation routes.

Food Waste Management Market - This market is considering the services provided by organisations aimed to prevent, reduce and recycle the food wasted or discarded across the FSC. This includes waste collection, transportation, treatment and disposal. It is estimated that this market will grow from \$38.59 billion in 2020 to reach 83.23 billion 2030, globally. The main driver is the rapidly increasing foodservice industry [104]. The market is segmented by process, end user, application, waste type, method and region.

By end user, the segments that are of interest for SILL 8 are the food service providers and municipalities & households. Together, these two were valued over \$21.7 billion in 2017 and hold the largest market share, which will grow to a value of \$29.6 billion in 2023 [16].

By type of food wasted, the segment holding the largest share is the Fruit & Vegetable segment, which in 2022 accounts for approximately 29% of the total market, and is followed by the Fish & seafood segment with a share of 22.4%.

Meal Kit Service Market - This is a relevant target market for SILL 9, which was sized at \$15.21 billion in 2021, and will grow to reach \$64.44 in 2030, at a year-on-year growth rate of 17.4% (Figure 45) [105]. Growth is boosted by the growing demand for homemade meals and changing consumer behaviours.

Figure 45. Global market value of the Meal Kit Services from 2021 to 2030. [105]

8.3 Market Drivers & Dynamics

Factors that influences the ZeroW Wholesale, Retail and Consumer Innovations relevant markets, including opportunities driving market growth, as well as any potential restraints and challenges are discussed below.

8.3.1 Market Drivers

- ✓ Increasing attention from governments and public institutions about FLW, highlighting it as an unnecessary cause of exacerbation of the environmental impact of food production. This is leading to the development of new policies aimed to reduce FLW and associated impacts, increasing the demand and favouring development of new technologies that can tackle the issue.
- ✓ Wholesalers/Retailers play a pivotal role in the food supply chain; as such, actions at this level can have an impact at both upstream and downstream stages (i.e.: helping increase consumers' awareness, or by directly linking primary production with other uses to prevent FLW in case of surpluses) [30].
- ✓ Due to the large quantities of waste generated, coupled with the limited number of source locations (i.e.: supermarkets) and considerable data availability, retailers constitute good candidates to investigate how/why FW is produced and to test new solutions to prevent/manage it [106].
- ✓ Donation of surplus food for people in need is gaining popularity among FSC actors, mainly in the hospitality/retail sectors, increasing the demand for technological solutions that are able to connect surplus offers and demand [30].

- ✓ Some EU Member States are financing efforts towards modernising the systems involved in food donation and its monitoring with reporting purposes. This will further support the adoption of innovations in the sector [30].
- ✓ The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the need to have more resilient food systems and to reduce FLW. This is encouraging cooperation between public and private actors and increasing stakeholder's awareness on the need to innovate as a key element to prevent FLW.
- ✓ The increasing pressure to encourage the use of renewable energy sources will contribute to the transition towards the bioeconomy and circular economy. This trend is accelerating at the time of writing this report due to the conflict in Ukraine, which has highlighted the dependence of the EU on Russian-imported fossil fuels and the necessity to shift towards renewable energy sources [35]. This will favour the adoption of technologies to recycle food waste as renewable resource [95].

8.3.2 Market Restraints

- ✗ The emerging technologies intended to prevent FW or to enable alternative management of the food wasted (such as electricity production, utilisation as animal feed) can be more costly than conventional disposal, disincentivising uptake.
- ✗ Limited knowledge among stakeholders in the retail/foodservice sectors about associated benefits of reducing FLW, apart from the economic ones.
- ✗ Some of the alternative ways to manage food waste that are available for retailers / foodservice require better trained personnel and consequently more investment than simply sending the waste to the landfill (i.e. revalorisation/recycling require onsite separation of residues and disposal in different bins before sending to the waste treatment facilities [106]). This may discourage adoption.
- ✗ Food waste recycling for contribution to the bioeconomy requires the acquisition of new knowledge and skills, as well as a the creation of new markets to place the generated products. This may deter implementation [95].
- ✗ High costs and low demand pull-effect may delay the adoption of food waste recycling technologies [95].
- ✗ Limited/Variable availability and quality of food waste due to logistic, seasonal, technical or other issues may hamper its use as renewable source for recycling/revalorisation [95].
- ✗ Difficulties in separating the FW from the rest of municipal solid waste, especially at consumer/household level can limit management options [107].

8.3.3 Opportunities

- ❖ The development of smart cities will favour IoT- and machine learning-based solutions for waste management, among others such as transport, electricity / water supply, sanitation, etc., favouring adoption of these technologies.
- ❖ FW management technologies contributing towards the bioeconomy will create jobs and favour economic growth, attracting investments [95].
- ❖ Current global instability is causing an energy crisis with escalating prices on non-renewable energy sources such as gas and fuel. This situation will facilitate the switch to alternative, renewable energy sources, which include FW, with an increased demand for technologies that enable it.

8.3.4 Challenges

- ∇ Lack of awareness about FLW as a source of unnecessary environmental impact/GHG emissions: FW is not mentioned in any of the Nationally Determined Contributions to the Paris Agreement [88].
- ∇ Difficulty to assess the drivers of consumer FW [71] may hinder the development of solutions aimed to reduce it.
- ∇ The lack of standards for the manufacturing of biobased products may limit the market penetration of FW recycling technologies [95].
- ∇ The profitability of biobased products, including those generated from FW, is highly influenced by fluctuating oil prices [95].
- ∇ Lower competitiveness of FLW biobased products as they are more expensive than conventional ones [95].

8.4 Competitor Analysis

8.4.1 Competitor offerings

- **Shelf Engine**, US (<https://www.shelfengine.com/>). Grocery shelf optimisation and supply chain management using AI to predict demand of highly perishable food products, allowing retailers to optimise orders and minimise risk of spoilage and subsequent food waste.
- **Wasteless** (<https://www.wasteless.com/>) in collaboration with Capgemini, Toshiba TEC, Intel and Hanshow. AI-based solutions for food retail, based on dynamic pricing of products based on time left to expiry date that allow to maximise profit margins for end users.
- **Spoiler Alert**, US (<https://www.spoileralert.com/>). Analytics platform for unsold inventory, manufacturers, wholesalers and retailers. It analyses potential sources of food waste and provides suggestions on how to prevent it, including ways to donate it to charities/food banks. Mondelez, Nestlé, Campbells', Hello Fresh, etc. are some of their clients.

- **Whywaste**, Sweden (<https://www.whywaste.com/>). Date-checking app for retail stores that alerts when a product is close to expiration date. It allows to manage markdowns, promotions and log food waste in the same app. Claims that by using their solutions, retailers can reduce food waste by up to 50%.
- **Orbisk**, the Netherlands (<https://www.orbisk.com/#>). Automated food waste monitor for the food service industry. It works by placing the food to be disposed in front of a camera. The system takes a picture and automatically recognises the type of waste. The data is presented in the application.
- **Kitro**, Switzerland (<https://www.kitro.ch/>). Solution for restaurants and foodservices to track and manage waste using imaging technology to automatically identify, weigh and record every food item discarded. It allows to identify what food is more frequently wasted and allows to take corrective actions to prevent it, saving money. The company claims reductions of food waste of up to 70% [91].
- **Winnow**, UK (<https://www.winnowsolutions.com/>). Food waste management solutions for the hospitality/food service sector based on visual software and AI that automatically detect and weigh the food that goes to waste, recording and presenting it as a report.
- **LMK Group**, Sweden (<https://lmkgroup.se/>). They provide meal kits with ingredients and suitable recipes so all the ingredients can be used, with the aim to simplify their customers' everyday life and reduce food waste. The group connects producers directly with consumers, bypassing middlemen. Ingredients that do not reach the consumer are sent to charity or for composting. The LMK Group operates in Sweden, Norway and Denmark with the brands Linas Matkasse, Godtlevert, Adams Matkasse and RetNemt. The company reported revenues of SEK 1.2 billion (€116.6 million), with approximately 175 million meal kits delivered to households during 2020.
- **HelloFresh**, Germany (<https://www.hellofresh.com>). Company offering kits of fresh ingredients and recipes via subscription so all the ingredients delivered can be used to prevent FLW. They are currently operating in more than 10 countries.
- **Blue Apron**, US (<https://www.blueapron.com/>). Chef-approved kit menu options including recipes and ingredients. Price based on number of servings and the type of meal kit. They operate only in the US.
- **Gousto**, UK (<https://www.gousto.co.uk/>). Company dedicated to providing food boxes with recipes and the exact required ingredients necessary to make them. Subscription-based business model.
- **Northfork**, Sweden (<https://northfork.ai/>). Platform for grocery stores to sell products by recipe. Includes a nutritional calculator to help choose healthier and nutrient-complete recipes.

- **Nosh**, UK (<https://nosh.tech/index.html>). Food management app that tracks expiry or use-by dates for food items by scanning a product's barcode/ticket receipt, and also helps keep track of wasted food products to make informed decisions at the supermarket. The app also includes the "nosh shop" feature (which is being tested at the time of writing), allowing customers to shop groceries from local stores at a discount. Additionally, the app offers recipes based on existing inventory.
- **Magic Fridge**, France (<https://www.frigomagic.com/en/>). Mobile app offering users zero-waste recipes based on leftovers. It also includes a recipe planner and provides nutri- and eco-scores for each recipe.
- **MyFoodways**, Switzerland (<https://myfoodways.com/>). Mobile app created by Foodways Consulting, offering healthy and environmentally friendly recipes to the users, based on what is available at their homes. The app also provides information on the best ways to store food ingredients so they stay fresh for a longer time. Foodways Consulting advise companies about food waste and sustainability; this app is part of a series of digital tools intended to help its users to reduce food waste.
- **SHARE IT toolkit**, Ireland (<https://shareit.sharecity.ie/>) for sustainability impact assessment, created as part of the SHARECITY project. SHARE IT is a tool to evaluate, communicate and improve the sustainability impact of food sharing initiatives on food systems. It is offered for free. The SHARECITY project, which finished in 2021, assessed the sustainability potential of food sharing economies.
- **Seedtrace**, Germany (<https://seedtrace.org/>). Platform for food manufacturers to demonstrate and promote social and ecological impacts of their products to the consumer, as well as to allow traceability and offering consumer insights back to the food manufacturer.
- **CozZo**, Bulgaria (<https://cozzo.app/>). Application dedicated to reducing FW by offering a kitchen management system. Users can create shopping lists and manage the stock in the refrigerator or pantry, plan meals, track/report expiry dates, plan shopping, etc. The app has expanded beyond Bulgaria to Europe, North America, Australia and Southeast Asia.
- **Kitche**, UK (<https://kitche.co/>). App that helps households better manage their inventory to waste less food. It allows users to scan food products from the users' receipt and the app automatically classifies them and sets reminders to consume them before expiry date, as well as to keep track of the food wasted to understand the consumers' habits to prevent it in the future. Additionally, app includes smart recipes based on the food products available at home and dietary preferences.

- NoWaste, Denmark (<https://www.nowasteapp.com/>). Food management app that allows to organise food available in fridge, freezer and pantry according to expiry dates. The app includes a library with over 200 food items and uses a barcode scanner to quickly enter food products.

Other projects and campaigns:

- Campaigns for the use of leftovers in recipes and providing advice on best ways to preserve food at home: [Love Food Hate Waste](#) (UK) and [Matvett](#) (Norway).
- The Danish non-profit organisation [Stop Spild af Mad](#) ("Stop Wasting Food"³) is a member of the [EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste](#), and is collaborating in several projects aimed to reduce FLW and food insecurity, also offering educational tools.
- The [Samen Tegen Voedselverspilling](#) ("Together Against Food Waste foundation"³) is the movement of companies and public organizations in Netherlands that join forces for a common goal: to reduce food waste by half before 2030, keeping 1 billion kg of good food within the FSC in Netherlands.
- The [Farmlink project](#), US (<https://www.farmlinkproject.org/>). Starting in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic, the aim of this project is to set the infrastructure to prevent food waste by connecting producers with food banks to directly donate their excess produce with those in need.
- [Food Finders](#), US (<https://www.foodfinders.org/>). Non-profit organisation aiming to prevent food waste by redirecting surplus food from the food service businesses to food banks, missions, etc. They are operating in Southern California.
- [Yo no desperdicio](#) ("I don't waste"³), Spain (<https://yonodesperdicio.org/>). Initiative that launched in 2015 with the aim to create awareness among the public about the impact of food waste and propose ways to reduce it.
- The [Ploutos Project](#) (A Sustainable Innovation Framework To Rebalance Agri-Food Value Chains) aims to create opportunities for changes that can rebalance the value chain in the agri-food system towards more environmentally, socially and economically sustainable system. The [FoodShare](#) platform has been developed within the scope of the project, to facilitate the transfer of surplus food from farmers to socially disadvantaged groups in Serbia and North Macedonia.

³ English translation

8.4.2 ZeroW Solution and key differentiating points

The innovations proposed by ZeroW solutions aimed to tackle the lock-in effects at the Wholesale, Retail and Consumer level are quite specific and not necessarily comparable with commercially available solutions. The reason for this might lay in the fact that majority of innovations relevant to ZeroW are still in the infancy and not readily available in the market. Additionally, ZeroW innovations developed under SILL 7 and SILL 9 principally aim to provide royalty-free knowledge and best practices example to both food banks and general public.

That said, the systemic innovations anticipated under this ZeroW cluster of innovations are building on top of the state-of-the-art in the respective areas. As discussed above (Section 8.2.2.4) food banks are dealing with the increasing demand for food, intensified by external factors such as global health crisis or political instability (such as Covid-19 pandemic or conflict in Ukraine). At the same time, the strict regulations to be followed to ensure food safety, are imposing considerable challenges when redistributing food surplus and donating it to the food banks. Finally, health impacts of food donated and distributed to those in need have to be taken into account (i.e. what is considered healthy food, should donations of so called “junk food” be accepted, etc.). To mitigate all this, SILL 7 will work on proposing advanced methods to predict the number of people/households to apply for food bank support, enabling the better match of demand and supply. Additionally, optimisation algorithms to deal with the uncertainty that food banks face will be developed to aid food banks in providing equitable support for people in need.

Consumer trust in novel solutions is governing both adoption of innovation to reduce FLW but also foster better choices when health and sustainability are concerned. To govern this, SILL 9 will propose solutions to (i) educate consumers on healthier and FLW informed decisions (by creating food boxes and food labels); support the consumers in making sustainable choices (through a mobile app) and (iii) engage retailers in the process of informing and nudging consumers via food boxes and food discounts (Section 8.1.3). Solutions with the similar purpose exist in the market, as detailed in Section 8.4.1; however, contrary to the common downstream approach to FLW reduction, SILL 9 will employ a two stage approach to tackling FW. This approach revolves around the effects of dietary choices starting at “the Fork”, reverse-engineered to the sourcing, transportation and processing stages of the FSC, i.e. routed to ‘the Farm’, and finally back to the ‘the Fork’ by informing and nudging consumers to make a balanced food choices. ZeroW will offer a systemic solution to integrate models designing food labels based on consumer food waste, decision support system to minimise FW (including retail/wholesale) and an app supported by Dutch Nutrition Centre and EFSA to empower consumer in

making healthy and sustainable food choices. All models should be replicable in different organisation types.

Finally, process innovations anticipated by SILL 8 to valorise un-avoidable food waste offers unique optimisation of logistics and FLW handling. This involves applying integrated reverse logistics, cargo consolidation, collaborative transportation sharing, bulk packaging and on-board treatment of FLW. Designing the novel hermetic container to support process optimisation will underline a competitive advantage for the SILL 8 solution to be potentially offered as a commercial product/service.

8.5 PESTLE Analysis

PESTLE analysis is performed to support the initial market assessment, helping to understand the contemporary market environment around the wholesale, retail and consumer innovation markets, and position ZeroW anticipated outcomes in it. In the following sections, Political Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors impacting the SILL 7, SILL 8 and SILL 9 outcomes are discussed.

8.5.1 Political factors

- The UN's SDG 12.3 establishes the commitment to halve retail and consumer food waste by 2030. It also states the need to reduce FLW at all stages of the food supply chain.
- In the revised [Waste Framework Directive](#) (2019) Europe established a common definition of FW and accepted methodologies for its Member States to measure food waste across the supply chain. The aim is to reduce FW, monitor it and report its progress. As the requirements for reporting are very similar to those proposed by the SDG 12.3, Member States can fulfil both simultaneously [88].
- The EU Farm-to-Fork Strategy, part of the Green Deal, will require a series of commitments towards addressing health and sustainability issues in food and beverage trade and serving companies (i.e.: environmental footprint reduction, reformulation of food products for healthier diets, etc.). It will also identify alternative markets for food and ways to facilitate its recovery and redistribution to those that need it most [86].
- The [Circular Economy action plan](#), also part of the European Green Deal, aims to transition to a circular economy by developing initiatives along the entire life cycle of a product to prevent waste and to ensure that resources are kept in the economy for as long as possible. It will set legislative and non-legislative measures in different policy areas, including FW and recycling, making use of an efficient biomass conversion.
- The EU proposed legislative framework for [Sustainable Food Systems](#) aims to make the food supply chain more sustainable and integrate it into all food-related

policies (production, processing, distribution and consumption). The framework will include the [Sustainability Labelling](#), part of the Farm to Fork Strategy, aimed to empower consumers' decisions on sustainable food. It will provide information on nutritional, climate, environment and social aspects of foods [108].

- The [EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste](#) (created in 2016) supported the EC in the development of guidelines both to facilitate food donation and to use food no longer intended for human consumption as feed. It has also helped in improving date marking practices and in setting a common methodology for food waste measurement [86].
- The [Stop Wasting Food](#) movement (Denmark) is tackling food waste from multiple angles:
 - Annual event where volunteers collect surplus Christmas food from supermarkets and redistribute it to families in need.
 - Cofounded the REFOOD label (<https://refoodlabel.dk/>) for the food service industry, highlighting efforts to reduce food waste and encourage recycling.
 - Published the Leftovers Cookbook to educate consumers on alternative recipes that can be made with leftovers.
- Germany's strategy "[Zu Gut für die Tonne](#)" ("Too Good for the Bin"³) aims to raise public awareness about food waste by sharing tips and a mobile application with cooking recipes from top chefs.
- [Directive 2018/2001/EU](#) – the Renewable Energy Directive. It was revised in 2021, is aiming to accelerate uptake of renewable energy sources by at least 40% in 2030, doubling their current share, favouring adoption of innovations to recycle food waste for conversion to biogas.
- Manufacturing of compost and its use are regulated as fertilisers in national policies [100].

8.5.2 Economic factors

- In 2018 there were 2.67 million companies involved in the food wholesale, retail and services sectors at European level. These generated a turnover of €2.48 trillion with an added value of 424 billion and 16.4 million employees. This represents a large share in the EU economy with a contribution of 19.5% of all employment, 17% of turnover and 11.3% of value added in the European non-financial sector (in 2019). From a historical context, the sector's turnover has doubled in the period between 2005 and 2019 with an average annual growth rate of 2.9%. The industry is dominated by micro enterprises [66].
- In 2018, the European food and beverage service industry (restaurants, catering companies, etc) was comprised by over 1.9 million companies employing 10.7 million people, with a turnover of €562.7 billion and an added value of €240.4 billion. These hold a share of 8.5% of employees and 3.9% value added of the total non-financial businesses. The food and beverage activities sector holds the

largest share [109]. The industry is comprised by micro enterprises and SMEs; as such, it may be difficult for them to make heavy investments in solutions to prevent FLW and they might require support from other stakeholders. In this case, it is key to raise awareness about the economic benefits of preventing FLW through case studies and sharing of best practices [30].

- At wholesale/retail level, the estimated total cost of FW can be up to 2% of total sales; therefore, taking preventive measures could reduce economic losses [30].
- European households' expenditure on food and beverages accounted for €1.58 trillion or €3,530/person (21.5% of all expenditure) in 2019. 11.8% was spent in food, 6.9% on food services and 2.8% in beverages (both alcoholic and non-alcoholic). Historically, in the period between 2005 and 2019, spending in these types of products has remained mostly stable while prices have increased an average of 26.7% [66].
- The Waste Framework Directive recommends public bodies to use fiscal instruments as incentives for FW prevention, normally related to food redistribution or waste management (for example introducing the fee per kg of waste collected by the local municipality). Some Member States are also offering financial support to prevent FW, as well as funding innovative projects investigating solutions that contribute to circular food systems [30].
- Some countries are applying waste or incineration taxes or pay-as-you-throw (PAYT) to households. The objective is to cover waste management costs and incentivise FW diversion from the landfill to other uses [71]. FW separated for recycling purposes is encouraged as its collection is normally free of charge. PAYT schemes may include flat rates (in the form of periodic fees or taxes) and variable rates (depending on container size, number, weight, collection frequency, or combinations of these) [94]. The impact of these initiatives is significant, as can be observed in Figure 46 [94].

Figure 46. Impact of PAYT schemes on separation of food waste in EU capitals. [94]

- Food redistribution. The food retail sector leads the food redistribution process in Europe (Figure 47). The associated costs of this activity come from staff, storage, logistics, and others such as energy, website/IT solutions, the costs of purchased food, legal assistance and food safety control [110]. There has been an increase of almost 60% of food recovered and redistributed from FEBA members in the period between 2016 and 2020 [93].

Figure 47. Percentage of stakeholders along FSC participating in the food redistribution. [110]

In 2019 approximately 931 million tons of food waste were generated at retail, foodservice and consumer stages globally [88], and 1.32 billion tons across the entire value chain with an economic cost of \$900 billion [95]. At European level, 88 million tons were wasted annually along the entire FSC, representing 20% of the food produced in Europe, with an estimated value of €143 billion. More than half of all wasted food (47 million tons) is produced at households (Figure 48) [31], [86].

Figure 48. Food waste at different stages of the food supply chain (2012). [86]

The revalorisation of food waste implies costs; these should be lower than the market prices of the obtained products to make economic sense. Additionally, efforts towards preventing FLW upstream the FSC would result in a reduction of resources for waste management innovations downstream the FSC, potentially reducing their economic feasibility and interest [96].

Additionally, commercially scaled biorefineries for production of high-added-value products can lead to a reduction in the market prices of these products due to

overproduction, while the higher demand for feedstocks may increase their price; these two factors combined can affect the economic feasibility of industrial-scale biorefineries [97].

8.5.3 Social factors

- FLW is influenced by different factors affecting behaviours such as cultural context, perceptions and attitudes regarding food [95]. For many consumers, price is a key element when deciding what they consume, this can have big impact on whether they choose sustainable and healthy diets [66]. In this sense, they may be more compelled to buy food that does not meet cosmetic standards if it was priced at a lower price, compared to “perfect” food [89].
- FLW reduction on the consumers’ part can be achieved either by reducing purchase of food or by consuming all the food purchased. If consumers buy less food, a downward shift in demand may occur, pushing food sales and prices down, affecting producers’ welfare; if purchases are maintained, to prevent FW consumers need to consume all the food with the associated health issues it may bring (such as obesity) [90].
- There seems to be contradictions among the impact of raising awareness on FW among consumers; while some studies point out that it is necessary to change behaviours, other studies suggest that awareness alone will not reduce FW in a significant way due to the complexities that lay behind complex “wicked” problem such as FLW; as such, blaming the consumers would be unproductive [71].
- Demographics of FLW: older people (especially those over 65) and women tend to generate less FW. Single-person households and those with children tend to generate more food waste than family households without children [71].

Figure 49. Percentage of adults under food poverty, by age group. [66]

- FLW and food poverty: Reducing FLW contributes towards ending global hunger. In 2019, 6.8% of people in the EU could not afford a meal with meat (or vegetarian equivalent) every other day, representing the lowest share in the

period for which data are available (2010-2019). Women are more vulnerable than men (7.6% vs. 6.6%, respectively), while the elderly is the demographic group most at risk of food poverty (Figure 49) [66]. Worldwide, there were 690 million persons suffering from hunger, a problem that is being exacerbated by crises such as the Covid-19 pandemic [86], the raise in gas and energy costs and cost of living in general, etc.

- Consumer acceptance of carbon labels: according to a 2020 survey performed by the [Carbon Trust](#), two thirds of surveyed consumers think that labels indicating the carbon footprint of a product is a good idea. France, Italy and Spain are the countries where acceptance of carbon labels is highest. Sweden is experiencing the greatest increase in support when compared with previous surveys, but it is still low compared to other countries [111].

8.5.4 Technological factors

- Despite the acknowledged high impact of FW at retailer/consumer levels, there is little research assessing the viability of technologies for food waste management. Measurements of the food wasted in the foodservice industry is currently made manually, with a worker weighing the food to be discarded and logging it. Automating this process will result in improved quantification of FLW, allowing benchmarking and development of new standards and policies. The first systems leveraging IoT and machine learning in food waste management are beginning to be commercialised, but they are highly complex and may lack accuracy [91].
- Package size is often a problem for some consumers. Portioned and divisible packaging can be a solution to solve this issue [71]. Some companies are starting to offer meal kits, containing recipes and the exact ingredients necessary to prepare them, following a subscription business model (as stated in Section 8.4.1).
- Most of the technologies used for FLW revalorisation are still immature, only proven at laboratory scale. Industrial-scale feasibility is still not demonstrated. Industrial application would require high availability and logistics to manage FW streams and scaling up processes [96]. One of the main challenges comes from the high variability of FW streams; it is required to set up a system capable to analyse its composition and select the most efficient technology to treat each type of FW [97].

8.5.5 Legal factors

- Regulation EU 1169/2011 (FIC regulation) sets the labelling requirements of food products (more information in Section 7.5.5). This was revised as a part of the Farm to Fork strategy, with the aim to help consumers take better decisions in

regards to healthier and more sustainable food choices while preventing FW. The regulation includes a revision in the rules on date marking (“use by” and “best before”). Electronic labels (e-labels) are not likely to replace paper-based ones as this would prevent some consumers to access the information (i.e.: information is limited to those people owning a smartphone).

- [Regulation \(EU\) 1308/2013](#) (December 2013) provides the rules on marketing standards for fruit and vegetables. It defines different classes to sort fruits and vegetables based on their aesthetic attributes.
- The annexes of [Regulation \(EC\) 852/2004](#) on food hygiene regarding food allergen management, food redistribution and food safety culture, amended by [Regulation \(EC\) 2021/382](#) in March 2021. This aims to ensure safety in the food to be donated to charities. It defines the aspects to assess food safety when donating food, and the correct application of the use-by and best-before dates in food redistribution [112].
- [Regulation \(EC\) 853/2004](#) on specific hygiene requirements for food of animal origin, amended by [Regulation \(EC\) 2021/1374](#) in August 2021, authorises freezing of meat that is going to be donated to food banks and other charities at retail level, specifying the conditions when it is suitable.
- The Waste Framework Directive is taking action to prevent food waste by:
 - Requiring Member States to implement food waste prevention programmes, and assess effectiveness using a common methodology ([Commission Delegated Decision \(EU\) 2019/1597](#) on a common methodology and minimum quality requirements for the uniform measurement of levels of food waste along the entire food supply chain).
 - Directing Member States to encourage food donation for human consumption, rather than to use it for other purposes such as animal food or revalorisation to prevent FW [86].
 - Increasing awareness of consumers about the “use by” and “best before” dates [86].
- The F2F strategy will set legally binding targets of FLW reduction by Member States by 2023.
- Most EU member states have set legislative and non-legislative measures to reduce FLW. Some EU countries such as France and Italy are applying laws to prevent FW at retail level: in France, the law prohibits retailers to throw away food that is still edible, requiring them to sign contracts with food banks for regular donation, and fining those that do not comply. Italy provides incentives in the form of tax refunds to retailers that donate unsold food to charity [86]. These measures may drive the demand for solutions to improve efficiency in management of food banks.

8.5.6 Environmental factors

- Research shows that at retail level, bread and beef are the food types whose waste causes the highest environmental impacts. Solutions favouring prevention of wastage or alternative uses for these food types would have the greatest effect on sustainability and should be explored. For example, excess bread could be used as animal feed [106].
- Waste produced downstream the supply chain, and especially at households, has the greatest environmental impact: as it is the latest stage in the supply chain and has accumulated the impacts/footprints incurred in previous steps. It is estimated that FLW is responsible of around 4.4 gigatons of CO₂ annually [95], which represents 8-10% of total anthropogenic GHG emissions, most of which is produced at household level [88]. Additionally, it is a cause of air and water pollution, biodiversity loss and soil degradation. However, the environmental issues of FLW are not as important to consumers as other factors such as price. This means that campaigns focusing on the environmental issues caused by FLW may have a limited impact due to consumers' fatigue of receiving constant messages about it [71].
- The Carbon Trust measured the environmental impact of food redistribution using [FareShare](#) (the UK's national network of food redistributors). This study assessed the footprint generated by food redistribution operations, subtracting it from the avoided footprints of preventing the food from going to waste. Overall, 10,698 tons CO₂eq from 6,699 tons of food were avoided; while operations generated 1,510 tons CO₂eq (net impact of around 9,129 tons of CO₂eq prevented). Most of the carbon footprint generated came from transportation, while the food categories with the largest emissions were dairy and vegetables. The study also provided some recommendations to improve the measurement methodology. For example, addressing the necessity to include in the analysis the release of fugitive gases (F-gases) that are associated with the use of refrigeration to preserve certain food products, as these emissions can be significant [113].
- Food production is responsible for a great part of the manmade environmental footprint and its inefficiencies cause FLW, resulting in unnecessary use of resources. Furthermore, FLW management creates additional impacts: as food waste decomposes, it emits methane, a powerful greenhouse gas twice as potent as carbon dioxide.
- Composting is one of the fastest ways of revalorising FW; however, it releases GHGs: 1 ton of treated FW can generate up to 342kg CO₂ [100]. Coupling carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies to composting reactors can help reduce the environmental impact. Conversely, the compost used for soil modification can help sequester carbon and improve soil conditions. FW may contain small amounts of heavy metals, which can accumulate in the reactors and

contaminate the resulting compost, consequently leading to the soil and ground water contamination. Additionally, another cause of concern is the release of antibiotic-resistant microorganisms to the environment [100].

- Pyrolysis is an eco-friendly alternative for treatment of food waste. The biochar produced, with a 10-50% carbon content, is used as a method to directly sequester carbon. It can then be used to improve the soil in agricultural applications. However, some of the carbon sequestered in the biochar can be released to the atmosphere; it is estimated that 10-20% can be released to the atmosphere depending on different pyrolysis conditions, pH of the soil and climatic conditions [102].

8.6 Barriers to entry

- Separation of FW, mainly at the consumer stage, but also in foodservice/retail stages, is more difficult than upstream in the supply chain; FW is managed as municipal solid waste, mixed with other types of wastes. Separation and logistics issues can limit adoption of alternative FW management solutions [107].
- Lack of stakeholders' engagement in initiatives aimed to separate FW to recycle/revalorise it [94].
- SILL 8: There are regulatory barriers limiting the use of microalgae grown in cultures using FW. Currently, these cannot be used to obtain human food or animal feed. However, there are not known regulatory barriers for use in other industries such as cosmetics or bioplastics.

8.7 ZeroW Wholesale, Retail and Consumer Innovations Market Summary

Despite the large evidence on FW levels at wholesale, retail and consumer stages of FSC, lack of available solutions to systemically address these is evident. This is partly a consequence of difficulties to accurately measure food wasted at this stage (as compared to the measurements of the FSC upstream) and then propose and implement appropriate measures. Still, FW at this level is estimated to have greater environmental impact, due to the (i) higher probability for it to end up in landfills than FLW at other levels upstream the supply chain and (ii) accumulated impact across the entire FSC.

At present, available market solutions addressing lower stages of FSC are focusing on applications for FW monitoring and management, dynamic pricing according to the product expiry date, management solutions for household and finally redistribution of food surplus and alternative utilisation of FW. Summary of the market dynamics associated to markets relevant for ZeroW innovations under cluster 4 is presented in the Figure 50.

<p>DRIVERS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing attention from governments and public institutions about FLW. • The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the need to have more resilient food systems and to reduce FLW.
<p>RESTRAINTS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emerging technologies aimed to prevent FW can be more costly than conventional disposal. • Variable availability and quality of food waste may hamper its recycling/revalorisation. • Limitations in management options due to difficulties in separating food waste, especially at household level.
<p>OPPORTUNITIES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FW management technologies contributing towards the bioeconomy will create jobs and favour economic growth, attracting investments. • The escalating prices of oil and gas are facilitating the switch to renewable energy sources, including food waste.
<p>CHALLENGES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of awareness about FLW as a source of unnecessary environmental impact/GHG emissions. • Lower competitiveness of FLW biobased products as they are more expensive than conventional ones

Figure 50. Summary of market dynamics for cluster 4.

ZeroW SILL 8 solutions anticipate to address the market gap related to retail-fostered valorisation of FW, focusing on development of optimised reversed logistics for FW valorisation and FW alternative deployment. This implicates addressing the relatively new concept of FW use for microalgae growth; hence, similar solutions are not yet available at the market.

Introducing innovations at wholesale, retail and especially consumer stages of FSC is fundamentally impacted by consumer trust, social norms and policy/regulation requirements; the acceptance of such innovations will largely depend on education of general public, behavioural change and novel governance models. Taking this into account, ZeroW solutions anticipate to meet non-commercial actors needs associated to optimised food bank processes for efficient demand prediction and distribution of food, as well as nudging consumers behaviour toward more sustainable food choices.

Hence, the social aspect is one of the main drivers of this market; preventing the unnecessary waste of already produced food will aid governmental agendas on alleviating food insecurity and providing food for all, consequently offering major growth opportunities for FW management solutions [16].

9 Conclusions

ZeroW proposed solutions, as demonstrated in this report, are aiming at disrupting the relevant FSC sector, introducing systemic innovations and fostering the EC dual ambition of halving FLW by 2030 and enabling the near-zero FLW by 2050. Solutions anticipated by the project are expected to introduce systemic innovations in different dimensions, including, but not limited to technology, policy, business, behaviour, and to span across entire FSC, including pre-harvest stage, which commonly is not accounted for.

The ZeroW commercialisation approach centres on SILLs' activities, fostering commercial exploitation of viable and sustainable solutions and protecting the strategic IP. The ZeroW's commercial ambition is to deliver products and services aligned with identified market demands, consumer attitudes, FSC actors needs and policy trends. This document provides a foundational support for ZeroW exploitation and commercialisation strategy, reviewing market intelligence and relevant governing factors that might foster or impede potential commercial trajectory of anticipated ZeroW solutions. To cover all FSC segments in this broadly-scoped report, it was necessary to examine details of several markets being targeted with the proposed ZeroW solutions. Each of these markets are detailly described, in the sense of market size, drivers and dynamics, as well as existing solutions. Preliminary PESTLE analysis to capture the main factors impacting the proposed solutions as well as barriers for solutions entry are also researched. This research led to clear understanding of ZeroW proposed solutions key differentiation against available state-of-the-art and it is now available in the Market Analyses report to guide the commercial exploitation strategy. (Table 7 in Section 4.2 is provided to facilitate navigation throughout different sections of the document).

In general, governing strategies and policy recommendations, as well as ambitious targets set by regional, national, EU and global regulatory bodies are fostering the adoption of smart technologies, digital transformation of agri-food sector and just transition towards sustainable food consumption. To act on this and sustain their businesses in the highly competitive agri-food market, stakeholders along entire FSC are required to introduce innovations to increase production efficiency, optimise processes in terms of time, yield and environmental impact, and increase quality of produced food; this is to be accompanied with implementing practices to prevent, reduce and valorise FLW along FSC. Foundational challenges impeding the integrated F2F supply chain and restricting the implementation of FLW practices on broader European level (as opposed to sector specific and in local context) are (i) lack of common agreement on FLW terminology and uniform FLW definition, and (ii) unavailability of FLW data and data sharing practices. Additionally, as the European agri-food sector is mainly run by small- and medium-enterprises, the limited resources actors might have available to implement new practices and technology

are posing significant constraint in adoption of sustainable practices. Finally, (iii) introducing novelty into the agri-food industry is largely impacted by acceptance from both food producers/processors/distributors and consumers; demonstrating impact of the proposed innovations, gaining trust of end-users and educating the general public are key enablers of successful implementation of proposed innovation.

The **OFLW Platform** (along with supporting solutions - OFLW Data Space, BDIS and ZeroW Smart Applications), is an overarching output of the project with the potential to foster digital transformation of FSC. Similar holistic solutions are not available in the market, as the majority of the state-of-the-art focuses on narrower problems at discrete stages of the FSC, and mainly at retail level. In addition, such solutions are not best suited to address FLW at regional, national or European contexts. Challenges to adoption of such solution includes the complexity of FSC and issues related to data management and ownership; however, advances in big data analytics, Blockchain technologies, computing power and IoT, will foster the digitalisation efforts and sustainability in food systems, opening the market opportunities for digital solutions like OFLW Platform.

Sustainable agricultural practices are increasingly adopted in the European agricultural landscape, and **wasteless greenhouse solutions** as anticipated output of ZeroW fit well to the market need for PA that reduce FLW and foster more efficient production. ZeroW proposed solution incorporates the harvesting scheduling tool to optimise the harvest scheduling and yield planning, harmonising it with short-term predicted downstream demand, in effect avoiding the supply-demand mismatches and possible generation of FLW. To ensure widescale adoption, governmental incentives for implementation of smart agricultural and farming technologies are crucial, especially for the small-scale farms.

ZeroW food processing innovations encompasses several solutions. (i) The **innovative, sustainable and smart packaging** for fresh fish brings the competitive holistic solution with the potential to increase fresh fish shelf-life and improve stock management at the retail level; deployment of smart sensors as integral part of proposed solution distinguishes ZeroW innovation, as it provides real-time data for monitoring both shelf-life and quality of the packed product. (ii) The **mobile processing unit** anticipated to be offered as a service empowers small- and medium-sized farms to utilise the product surplus; often these were not able to avail of the currently available commercial processing units, as they are large, expensive and in most cases stationary. (iii) **Ugly food early identification** solution promotes efficient control of produce quality, colour, size and shape, detecting eventual issues early; inclusion of state-of-the-art sensors enables real-time, non-destructive on-line information on organic/non-organic product batches, preventing the FLW occurring due to misclassification and allowing for timely recovery practices. (iv) **Advanced**

algorithms for control and optimisation of the production processes are offering non-destructive technology for determination of food quality parameters and subsequent optimisation of intermediate processing steps in fresh meat production. Although governed by the need to increase production efficiency both to support growing population and to optimise the production processes in terms on time, yield and environmental impact to support the shift towards sustainable food systems, food processing innovations still face the barrier imposed by consumers acceptance of novelty. Additionally, adoption of novel and often time perceived as costly technologies might be hindered by the lack of available resources as the European food processing industry is majorly constituted of SMEs. Introducing innovations at wholesale, retail and especially consumer stages of FSC is fundamentally impacted by consumer trust, social norms and policy/regulation requirements. The anticipated ZeroW solutions aims to meet non-commercial actors needs associated to **optimisation of the food bank processes** in order to enable efficient demand prediction and distribution of food, as well as to foster **informing & nudging consumers towards more sustainable food choices**. Finally, for the un-avoidable FW created at the retail level after exhausting all other FLW reduction strategies (i.e. markdowns or donations to food banks), ZeroW anticipated solution proposes the novel way to **valorise the retail waste through algae production** for high-value applications. As a new concept, this solution anticipate development of novel hermetic container for treated FW, that coupled with the unique optimisation of reversed logistic and transportation will offer an innovative and integrated solution for retail FW treatment and revalorisation.

At the time of submitting this report (M12), ZeroW SILLs are still in preparation phase, and planned to start testing and validating activities in M14. Any additional understanding regarding ZeroW solutions and modifications of market analyses to possibly include additional market intelligence will be addressed in follow-up commercialisation deliverables. The detailed elaboration of ZeroW solutions commercial potential will be addressed through customer validation and solution alignment (to be reported in D7.2, due in M24), adoption of appropriate business models and development of cluster specific business plan (to be covered in D7.3, due in M46), while IP will be managed and commercially strategic IP protected through activities of task 7.4 (report due in M46). ZeroW exploitation strategy will be supported by ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem developed under the task 7.5, ensuring ZeroW outputs and commercial ambitions are sector-calibrated and market-relevant. A business ecosystem will also foster early outreach to relevant FLW actors, seeking and encouraging adopters at EU scale. All listed exploitation and commercialisation activities are to ensure post-project sustainability of ZeroW solutions.

10 References

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11 Annex I - Dependencies between different WPs

WP11 Project Management, WP9 Cooperation with EC services & other projects/initiatives, and WP10 Dissemination and communication, are horizontal WPs supporting the entire consortium in project delivery, cooperation with other FLW initiatives, and results communication.

Market Analyses_Template for Partners

Introduction

Market Analyses will be performed in the scope of WP7 with the aim to understand market opportunities for ZeroW solutions. The research will be principally pivoted around ZeroW SILLs, but also FLW industry sector, associated supply chains, the food commoditisation ecosystems, the food packaging actors, consumer interest groups and EU SME and industry sector.

ICP as a lead of Exploitation, sustainability and commercialisation of project outputs (WP7) will provide comprehensive report covering the market analyses of 4 clusters as identified in ZeroW Exploitation strategy (Fig.1).

Fig 1. ZeroW Exploitation Strategy and SILLs positioning.

The purpose of this template is to gather information on specific market segments ZeroW solutions will be targeting; WP7 Partners involved in solutions development/testing/validating are invited to provide input on a specific market segment relevant to their area of work. Figure 2 summarises the ZeroW GA principal project results (Table 8, GA), as well as results Partners identified in the SILLs onboarding workshop held on March 2nd 2022. This might help to indicate market segments where ZeroW expected results will fit.

ICP Market Analyses Template

Please fill in the following template. We understand this is early stage in the project and all solutions might not be clear yet; we ask you to keep in mind GA anticipated solutions and answer the following questions to the best of your knowledge.

MARKET RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE

Q1. Describe the solution(s) you are developing.

Please describe the solution you will develop/test within your organisation.

[This is to help us orienteer towards the specific market segment to be further researched as a part of comprehensive Market Analyses Report.]

Q2. Describe the problem your solution is solving in the context of FLW reduction.

Please elaborate on what FLW related problem your solution is targeting. Does your solution offer a novel/unique approach to the problem and if yes what?

[This is to help us understand the position of anticipated ZeroW solution(s) against other available products/services on the market.]

Q3. What is the market you are targeting/your key customer?

Please indicate where do you envisage your solution to fit within the market of food value chain. You can refer to the Clusters as identified in the ZeroW Exploitation Strategy, but you can be more specific as well.

Who specifically is the customer (please be as specific as possible)?

What (exact) benefit will they get from your solution (e.g. reduce X, increase Y)?

Do you plan on targeting specific EU region? If yes, please explain why.

[This is only preliminary and for the purpose of market analyses, detailed customer identification/validation will be performed further into the project.]

Q4. What is the exploitation route you intend to follow?

Please indicate how you intend to exploit solution you are working on.

[This is only preliminary and for the purpose of market analyses, detailed exploitation of the results will be discussed further into the project.]

- New/Improved Product
- New/Improved Process
- New/Improved Service
- Software
- Algorithms & Models
- Technical Assets
- Tools and Methods
- Research Databases
- Scientific Publications
- Consultancy/Training
- Other (please describe below)

Q5. Do you have knowledge of similar products on the market/close to being placed on the market?

If so, please name a few. Are you aware of their state-of-the-art? Please elaborate.

[This is to help us identify market competitors and understand their offerings].

Q6. If answer to Q5 was Yes, please explain how your solution is different to the other available ones.

Please elaborate on technology advances, contribution to FLW reduction, or any other advantages your solution is offering compared to already available ones.

[This is to identify key differentiating points between ZeroW solutions and competitors' solutions.]

Q7. If the answer to Q5 was No, do you have knowledge of other markets where solutions similar to yours have already been implemented?

For example, data platforms for information sharing in another industries or intelligent packaging for different purposes (i.e. for different food products or offering different functionalities).

[This is to foster understanding of overall novelty of the ZeroW solutions.]

Q8. Do you foresee any barriers for your solution to be placed on the market?

Barriers to entry into market can relate to any form of limitations hindering the placement of the specific new/improved solution to the market. This can refer to monetary/funding issues (high development costs, high set-up costs); technical issues (are there any technological hurdles to be solved before placing solution to the market; who owns the necessary key resources); cost advantages to the company (i.e. how cost-effective is to produce this); network effect (i.e. will the value/utility of solution depend on number of users). Think also about identified competitors, and how would they impact the entry of your solution, i.e. brand loyalty and customer loyalty schemes, advertising supremacy and brand recognition, predatory pricing models (do they offer unmatched low prices). How willing the

customers will be to accept your solution (e.g. unfamiliar product, new methodologies used, solution too complex for customers to understand)? Please add any other barrier you can predict.

[This is to foster preliminary understanding of commercial viability of ZeroW solutions. Please answer to the best of your understanding at this stage of the project; we will come back to this in the later stages as well.]

Q9. Are there any regulatory requirements to be fulfilled?

To the best of your understanding, is your solution in line with the current regulatory/policy requirements? If yes, please indicate requirement/policy in question.

If not, please describe what is not compliant and what would be necessary to acquire compliance.

[This is to guide research on regulatory requirements within each exploitation cluster and to ensure pivoting around anticipated ZeroW solutions.]

Q10. Any other insights you would like to share or any other topics you would like us to cover in market analyses?

Please let us know if there is anything else you would like to share in regards to the solution you are developing.

Likewise, if there is anything else you would like to see covered in the comprehensive market analyses, please indicate here.

**Please add more rows if necessary.*